

[2026]

**The Status of Biological Invasions and their
Management in South Africa**

[DRAFT FOR PUBLIC COMMENT]

1 **Note to reader**

2 We are inviting you to submit comments, corrections, and queries on this fourth status report on
3 biological invasions¹. We have prepared a standard form for commenting that you can fill in if you
4 wish, but if you would prefer to send in your inputs in your own format, please indicate the page and
5 line numbers to which your comment refers. Many of the technical details (and data on which the
6 report is based like the list of alien species) are available in the appendices and supplementary
7 material (links available on the last page). Please also consider commenting on these. If you are in a
8 position to provide additional information, we would be very grateful. We will aim to ensure all
9 contributors are appropriately acknowledged. If you do not wish to be named, please let us know. We
10 would like as many people and organisations to make inputs as possible, so please send on. We will
11 capture all comments received during this commenting period and track how they are responded to.
12 A database of these comments and the responses will be available on request once the report has
13 been released.

14 Comments to be sent to: IAS.report.SANBI@gmail.com By: 1 March 2026

15 Form for comments: <https://tinyurl.com/h7fxmu6u>

16 We are also very keen to find how we can make the report more useful for you and your organisation.
17 As such we would also be very grateful if you completed a questionnaire (should take 10 to 15
18 minutes) available at: <https://tinyurl.com/ycymbd3v> also by 1 March 2026

19 This is a draft report². The report is based on information up to the end of December 2025, while much
20 of this has been included there are still some analyses to be completed. Therefore, the results are
21 demonstrative of what the final report will look like rather than necessarily indicative of the current
22 state as it will be presented in the final report. Specific sections where work is on-going are flagged
23 either with a note in square brackets or in a footnote to the text.

24

25 Thank you in advance for your comments, we appreciate you taking the time to engage with us.

26

27 Yours sincerely,

28 | Dr Tsungai Zengeya

29 (on behalf of the fourth status report drafting team)

30 Kirstenbosch, 30 January 2026

¹The previous status reports are available to download at <http://iasreport.sanbi.org.za/>; and <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7414803>, links for on-line resources are available at end of this report. For a statement on the independence of this report see S0.1

²For a statement on editorial conventions see S0.2

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57

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176 Foreword by DFFE Minister

177 Preface by SANBI Board Chair

178 Preface by SANBI CEO

179 [Note: the foreword and prefaces are to cover the purpose and context of the report, the scope, legal
180 requirement, principal findings and their implications, and any personal reflections. Each to be ~2
181 printed pages including a photograph. These will only be added immediately prior to publication]

182 List of acronyms³

183	ASRARP	Alien Species Risk Analysis Review Panel
184	A&IS	Alien and Invasive Species as referred to either in the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations or the
185		NEM:BA A&IS Lists published under the regulations
186	CBD	the Convention on Biological Diversity of the United Nations
187	CIB	the Centre for Invasion Biology, until 2024 a Department of Science and Innovation-
188		National Research Foundation Centre of Excellence, since then part of Stellenbosch
189		University's School for Climate Studies
190	DFFE	the Department of Forestry, Fisheries, and the Environment
191	DoA	the Department of Agriculture
192	EICAT	the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)'s Environmental Impact
193		Classification for Alien Taxa
194	GBF	the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework of the CBD
195	NEM:BA	the National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act (Act No. 10 of 2004)
196	NEM:BA A&IS:	see A&IS
197	QDGC	quarter-degree grid cell
198	RAC	the Reference and Advisory Committee (of this fourth status report)
199	SANBI	the South African National Biodiversity Institute
200	SAPIA	the Southern African Plant Invaders Atlas
201	SEICAT	Socio-Economic Impact Classification for Alien Taxa
202	WfW	the Working for Water programme
203	ZAR	South African Rands
204		

³These acronyms are based on those used in the third report, they will be cross-checked and updated as needed for the second order draft

205 Glossary⁴

- 206 **abundance** (cf. **distribution**, **extent**): a measure of the number of individuals, coverage, or biomass of
207 an organism in a specified **site**.
- 208 **adaptive management**: a structured, iterative process that includes the setting of goals, regular
209 monitoring of progress towards the achievement of those goals, and, based on the findings of the
210 monitoring, the adaptation of management to improve its effectiveness or a revision of the goals.
211 Adaptive management is useful where the outputs and outcomes of management are uncertain, and
212 where an approach of learning-by-doing can reduce uncertainty over time.
- 213 **alien species** (cf. **extralimital**, **native species**): a species that is present in a **site** outside its natural
214 range as a result of human action that has enabled it to overcome biogeographic barriers.
- 215 **assessment**: a critical evaluation of information.
- 216 **ballast water**: “...water that is pumped into tanks to stabilise cargo ships...Water can be taken on in
217 large quantities in one harbour and then discharged in the next...When the water is taken on board or
218 when it is discharged there are species and their propagules (including pathogens and algae), that may
219 be spread around the world.” (Harrower et al. 2018)
- 220 **biodiversity**: the variability among living organisms from all sources including terrestrial, marine, and
221 other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity
222 within species, between species and of ecosystems.
- 223 **biological invasions**: the phenomenon of, and suite of processes that are involved in determining, the
224 transport of organisms to **sites** outside their native range by human activities and the fate of the
225 organisms in their new ranges. **Biological invasions** affect all regions and **biomes** of the world,
226 including marine, terrestrial, and freshwater environments.
- 227 **biological control** (syn. **biocontrol**): the use of specimens of one species for the purpose of preying
228 on, parasitizing on, damaging, killing, suppressing or controlling a specimen of another species.
- 229 **biocontrol**: see **biological control**.
- 230 **biofouling**: the phenomenon of organisms attaching themselves to submerged surfaces and that can
231 lead to spread within and between regions. If the submerged surface is specifically the hull of a boat
232 or ship the term ‘hull fouling’ is used (adapted from Harrower et al. 2018).
- 233 **biome**: a large naturally occurring community of plants and animals that have common characteristics
234 in similar physical environments, e.g., desert or forest.
- 235 **biosecurity**: measures that are taken to stop the **introduction** or **dispersal** of organisms harmful to
236 human, animal, or plant life.
- 237 **compliance**: The action or fact of complying with instructions, in this report such instructions primarily
238 refer to the provisions of NEM:BA.

⁴These definitions are based on those in the third report with consideration of definitions given in relevant South African and international legislation and reports, specifically the NEM:BA and its A&IS Regulations, the CBD (<https://www.cbd.int/invasive/terms.shtml>), and the IPBES IAS Assessment (https://www.ipbes.net/glossary-definitions?search_api_fulltext=&field_deliverable=Invasive+alien+species+assessment). These cover terms used in this fourth report and in the supplementary material to the fourth report. Note: this version has not been cross-checked, this will be done for the final draft.

239 **contaminant**: the accidental **introduction** of an **alien species** with an intentionally transported
240 commodity with which the organism has a specific, natural association.

241 **control**: any action taken to prevent the recurrence, re-establishment, re-growth, multiplication,
242 propagation, regeneration or spreading of an **alien species**.

243 **corridor**: the natural spread of an **alien species** into a new region through a human-constructed
244 transport infrastructure that connects previously unconnected regions, and in the absence of which
245 **dispersal** would not have been possible.

246 **dispersal** (syn. **spread**): movement of organisms that is facilitated either intentionally or accidentally
247 by humans, or that occurs naturally.

248 **distribution**: the **extent** and **abundance** of a species over a given **site**.

249 **eradication**: the complete removal of all individuals and propagules of a population of an **alien species**
250 from a particular **site** to which there is a negligible likelihood of reinvasion (for the purposes of this
251 report the **site** is either continental South Africa or the Prince Edward Islands). If there is a likelihood
252 of reinvasion or that possibility was not explicitly assessed the term extirpation would be preferred,
253 in such cases other populations might be close by or pathways of introduction and dispersal are still
254 operating such that the probability of re-invasion is probable or not known.

255 **escape** (cf. **release**): the **spread** of an **alien species** that was intentionally **introduced** and kept in
256 captivity or cultivation to sites outside of captivity or cultivation. Includes both natural spread and the
257 accidental or intentional illegal human-mediated **dispersal** of live organisms from the site of captivity
258 or cultivation.

259 **established** (syn. **naturalised**.): **alien species** that sustain self-replacing populations for several life
260 cycles or over a given period of time without direct intervention by people, or despite human
261 intervention.

262 **extent** (cf. **abundance**, **distribution**): the broad-scale area over which an organism occurs. The spatial
263 scale over which extent is measured needs to be specified. The occupancy of sites at a fine-spatial
264 scale is often equivalent to the **abundance**.

265 **extralimital**: see **native-alien populations**

266 **impact**: the effect of an **alien species** on the physical, chemical, and biological environment. It can
267 include both negative and positive effects.

268 **incursion**: an isolated population of a pest, weed, or **alien species**, that usually has a limited spatial
269 extent and has been recently detected at a **site**. In general, the **management** of incursions is referred
270 to as incursion response.

271 **indicator**: a set of measurements that give specific information about the state of something.

272 **interventions**: the full variety of actions taken in response to biological invasions, including direct
273 actions, i.e., **control**, and indirect actions like **monitoring**, **regulation**, and research.

274 **introduced**: see **Introduction**.

275 **introduction**: the movement of an **alien species** (either accidentally, intentionally and legally, or
276 intentionally and illegally) by human activity, to a region outside its native range. Introductions can
277 also refer to species which were introduced to one country by humans and spread naturally to
278 neighbouring countries. In the context of introductions, the term 'accidental' is preferred to the
279 synonymous term 'unintentional'.

280 **introduction pathway prominence**: an indicator used to assess the status of **introduction pathways**.
281 The indicator assesses the introduction opportunities that are available for alien organisms to be

282 introduced to a country from other regions. The indicator considers introduction opportunities in
283 terms of how socioeconomically active the pathways are (e.g., amount of ballast water released),
284 rather than how many organisms are introduced through a pathway.

285 **invasion**: see **biological invasions**.

286 **invasive alien species**: see **invasive species**.

287 **invasive species**: **alien species** that sustain self-replacing populations over several life cycles, produce
288 reproductive offspring, often in very large numbers at considerable distances from the parent and/or
289 site of introduction, and have the potential to **spread** over long distances. **Invasive species** can be
290 plants, animals, fungi, and micro-organisms and are found across the world throughout freshwater,
291 marine, and terrestrial environments.

292 **monitoring**: a systematic process of collecting and analysing information to track progress towards
293 reaching stated goals, that facilitates the assessment of the efficacy of **interventions**.

294 **native-alien populations** (syn. **extralimital**; cf. **alien species**, **native species**): a population of a taxon
295 that is native to a part of South Africa, but that was founded by individuals moved by direct human
296 agency, over a biogeographical barrier, to an area beyond the species' native range (i.e., it can be
297 considered a biological invasions) (see Box 2.1). This does not include **native species** that have
298 extended their distribution by **natural dispersal**.

299 **native species** (syn. indigenous species, cf. **alien species**, **native-alien population**): species that are
300 found within their natural range where they have evolved without human intervention (intentional or
301 accidental). Also includes species that have expanded their range as a result of human modification of
302 the environment that does not directly impact dispersal (e.g., populations are still considered native
303 if they result from an increase in range as a result of watered gardens, but are considered alien if they
304 result from an increase in range as a result of spread along human-created corridors linking previously
305 separate biogeographic regions).

306 **naturalised**: see **established**, the term naturalised has been deprecated.

307 **natural dispersal** (syn. **unaided**): the **dispersal** of an **alien species** through natural spread from a
308 region where it was previously introduced through human assistance or action, to another region
309 where it is not native. Includes both self-propelled movement and movement with natural biotic (e.g.,
310 birds) and abiotic vectors (e.g., wind or water).

311 **pathway** (cf. **vector**): a broadly defined term that refers to the combination of processes and
312 opportunities that result in the movement of **alien species** from one place to another. Includes the
313 cause or reason why the organism is transported, the route along which it is transported, and the
314 **vector** that carries the organism.

315 **permit**: an official document issued in terms of Chapter 7 of National Environmental Management:
316 Biodiversity Act, 2004 (Act no. 10 of 2004).

317 **pest**: an organism that causes negative impacts. The affected sector might be specified, so an
318 agricultural pest will **impact** negatively on agricultural production. Pests can be **alien** or **native species**,
319 and are usually taken to refer to animals, with pest plants often rather referred to as weeds and pest
320 fungi or microbes referred to as diseases.

321 **policy**: a high-level overall plan, adopted by the Executive Authority, for achieving identified outcomes
322 through specified methods or principles that guide decision-making. A **policy** on **biological invasions**
323 would be a high-level plan which identifies goals concerning **biological invasions** in South Africa and
324 identifies the **interventions** that should be used to achieve those goals.

325 **regulation:** 1) a law or rule made by the Executive Authority in terms of original legislation to regulate
326 conduct (in this case the **NEM:BA A&IS Regulations**); 2) the act of regulating, i.e., to govern or direct
327 according to rule, or to make regulations (authoritative rules) for certain conduct.

328 **release** (cf. **escape**): the intentional **introduction** of an **alien species** to a site outside of captivity or
329 cultivation. This refers to both legal and illegal introductions, however if a legally introduced **alien**
330 **species** is illegally released outside of captivity or cultivation then it is classified as an **escape**.

331 **returns on investment:** the amount of value that is gained as a result of a particular amount spent on
332 an intervention. This can be calculated as a benefit: cost ratio whereby each rand spent (the cost) is
333 set against the amount of rands gained (benefit). An intervention is technically cost-effective if the
334 benefit: cost ratio is greater than one, although more generally cost effectiveness is about maximising
335 the ratio.

336 **risk:** the likelihood and consequence of an event, in this report the event is a **biological invasion**

337 **risk analysis:** the process of identifying and assessing the likelihood and consequence of an event, as
338 well as considerations as to how to manage and communicate the **risk**.

339 **risk assessment:** a component of **risk analysis** that focuses on evaluating the likelihood and
340 consequence of an event taking place. In the context of this report, such an event is the likelihood of
341 an **alien species** becoming an **invasive species** and the negative **impacts** that would result. Note in the
342 2020 **NEM:BA A&IS Regulations** the term **risk assessment** is used as a synonym for **risk analysis**, i.e.,
343 risk management considerations are included.

344 **site:** a defined spatial area, for example a protected area (as defined by the National Environmental
345 Management: Protected Areas Act, 2003); or an administrative unit (with national and provincial
346 administrative boundaries as defined by the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996).

347 **spread:** see **dispersal**

348 **status:** the state, condition or stage of affairs at a particular time.

349 **strategy:** a high-level plan for achieving management goals in a specific time frame under conditions
350 of uncertainty.

351 **stowaway:** the accidental **introduction** of an **alien species** attached to or within a transport vector or
352 their associated equipment and media. The organism is transported by chance, and there is no
353 specific, natural association with the vector.

354 **taxon** (pl. **taxa**): a group of organisms that all share particular properties (usually evolutionary history).
355 The grouping can be below, at, or above the species level.

356 **threat:** the negative impacts that may occur if an event happens (cf. **risk** where the likelihood is
357 explicit). In this context this refers to the negative **impacts** resulting from a component of the **invasion**
358 **debt** being realised.

359 **unaided:** see **natural dispersal**.

360 **unregulated introduction:** an **introduction** that was not approved by the relevant South African
361 authorities under the relevant regulations prior to the date at which it arrived in the country.

362 **vector** (cf. **pathway**): the physical means or agent that transports the alien species. Can be both
363 human mediated (e.g., ballast water, clothing, animal feed, or land vehicles) or natural (e.g., wind,
364 water, birds).

365 **Water Management Area:** an area established as a management unit in the national water resource
366 strategy within which a catchment management agency conducts the protection, use, development,
367 conservation, management, and control of water resources.

368 Summary of key messages⁵

369 Biological invasions are a major threat to South Africa’s water security, exacerbate fires, threaten
370 sustainable agriculture, and are having ongoing major negative impacts on South Africa’s unique and
371 globally important biodiversity. This phenomenon is not unique to South Africa nor to any one part of
372 the country, and thus addressing biological invasions requires integrated governance from
373 international to local levels. Of immediate concern, however, is that the number of alien species is
374 increasing, the area invaded is growing, but South Africa’s response has been declining.

375 These issues are addressed in detail in the report ‘The Status of Biological Invasions and their
376 Management in South Africa’. The key messages from this report are summarised here in the form of
377 a single headline followed by explanatory text with cross-references (in curly brackets) to the relevant
378 sections of the report. Each statement is also ascribed one of four confidence levels (*inconclusive*,
379 *unresolved*, *established but incomplete* and *well established*) as per the guidelines of the
380 Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2018).

381 The messages are grouped around five themes with corresponding indicators for each theme: A) how
382 alien species are introduced and move around the country (‘pathways’); B) the status and impacts of
383 alien species (‘species’); C) how sites are invaded and impacted (‘sites’); D) what has been done to
384 address the problem (‘interventions’); and E) the monitoring framework. These messages are
385 specifically intended to help gauge progress with management and advise those tasked with
386 developing policy responses, though the messages should also provide useful general insights to all
387 those interested and affected by biological invasions.

388

⁵This summary of key-messages is produced as part of fulfilling SANBI’s mandate under the NEM:BA (Act 10 of 2004) and its A&IS Regulations of 2020 to submit a report on the status of invasive species and the effectiveness of measures to combat them to the Minister of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment every three years. This is the fourth such report and presents an update on issues identified in the previous reports. For citations to this summary please cite the full report: SANBI and CIB. 2026. The status of biological invasions and their management in South Africa in 2025 [DRAFT FOR PUBLIC COMMENT]. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Kirstenbosch and Centre for Invasion Biology, Stellenbosch. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17697657>

A1: There are a wide range of opportunities for introductions, and new alien species continue to arrive every year through several pathways

A2: Alien species are spreading around South Africa, with this spread being facilitated by humans and occurring naturally

B1: The process of collating a list of alien species in the country has been substantially improved and documented, this will promote transparency, and facilitate management and regulatory decisions

B2: The adoption of standard practises to integrate biodiversity data means data on species occurrences can be used as the basis for models and indicators to monitor biodiversity status and change

B3: Knowledge of the distribution and abundance of alien plant species has improved; but structured surveillance remains essential to inform management and track trends

B4: Invasive species, in particular trees and freshwater fishes, have 'Major' negative impacts on people and nature across the country

C1: Invasions are distributed across the country including in protected areas

C2: Country-wide assessments indicate that invasive plant species are widespread, with several biomes and strategic water catchment areas experiencing substantial and increasing levels of invasion despite ongoing control efforts, except for taxa subjected to biological control

C3: The impact of invasions on water resources, rangeland productivity, and biodiversity are severe; workflows to track these impacts are vital for prioritising interventions but are currently not in place

D1: Funding for the management of biological invasions has declined steeply

D2: South Africa has an innovative regulatory system to address biological invasions, but its implementation is limited

D3: Intentional legal introductions are well regulated. The National Border Management Authority (BMA) became operational in 2023; but inspections for environmental threats have declined and illegal and accidental introductions continue

D4: The ongoing absence of monitoring systems limits South Africa's ability to improve the management of biological invasions

D5: Biological invasions have been effectively managed in a few cases, with biological control proving particularly successful

E1: South Africa has a sophisticated range of processes to address biological invasions but the monitoring of these is currently insufficient to evaluate their effectiveness

E2: Integrated governance will be crucial to improve the effectiveness of interventions

391

A) How alien species are introduced and move around the country

392

Head-line indicator	Trend ⁶	Confidence	Notes
1. Rate of introduction of new unregulated species	→	low	Over the last decade (2016–2025) approximately four new taxa were introduced per year either accidentally or intentionally but illegally. This is similar to previous estimates

393

Indicator	Trend	Confidence
1.1. Introduction pathway prominence	→	medium
1.2. Introduction rates	→	low
1.3. Within-country pathway prominence	not assessed	NA
1.4. Within-country dispersal rates	not assessed	NA

394

395 **A1: There are a wide range of opportunities for introductions, and new alien species continue to** 396 **arrive every year through several pathways**

397 New alien species continue to arrive every year in South Africa (*well established*) {1.1, 1.2}, with the
398 rate of their introduction remaining stable at around four per year (*established but incomplete*) {1.1,
399 1.2}. Besides biological control agents, the new species detected since December 2022 have been
400 accidentally introduced through several pathways (e.g., with imported plants and their products, and
401 through shipping) (*established but incomplete*) {1.2}. Pathways related to intentional introductions are
402 better regulated than in the past, but still pose a threat (*established but incomplete*) {4.1, 4.7}. For
403 example, records from social media show a range of alien pet birds are escaping from captivity; and
404 several studies have highlighted the size and diversity of the aquarium trade, and the various types of
405 introductions that it can facilitate (*established but incomplete*) {1.1, 1.2}. While biocontrol agents have
406 often significantly reduced the negative impacts of invasions (*well established*) {4.8}, other new alien
407 species are adding to the range, complexity and intensity of the negative impacts caused (*established*
408 *but incomplete*) {2}. The opportunities for invasive species to arrive are expected to increase as the
409 volume of trade and travel increases; appropriate biosecurity can ensure such trade is sustainable.

410

⁶→ no change; ↗ an increase; ↘ a decrease

411 **A2: Alien species are spreading around South Africa, with this spread being facilitated by humans**
412 **and occurring naturally**

413 Many pathways are providing opportunities for the within-country dispersal of alien species, and while
414 the extent of this role and how it has changed recently is not known, it is clear that alien species are
415 being moved around the country in a myriad of ways (*well established*) {1.3, 1.4}. For example, South
416 Africa plays a large role in the international pet trade, breeding animals (particularly alien birds) for
417 export and local use; and alien plants are moved around the country through formal and informal
418 trade, and by animals such as baboons and birds (*established but incomplete*) {1.3, 1.4}. Consequently,
419 alien species continue to spread and native species are being introduced to places outside of their
420 native ranges, causing negative impacts, and putting valuable assets at risk (*well established*) {2}.
421 Preventing both native-alien populations and the further spread of existing alien species will require
422 a greater focus on tracking and managing species movements within the country.

423

B) The status and impacts of alien species

424

Head-line indicator	Trend ⁷	Confidence	Notes
2. Number of invasive species that have 'Major' impacts	↗	low (many taxa still need to be assessed)	National assessments using IUCN's Environmental Impact Classification for Alien Taxa framework show significant impacts, with 19 species having been assessed as causing 'Major' or 'Massive' impacts. Complementary assessments using risk analyses and findings from the IPBES IAS Assessment confirm that these species cause widespread harm across multiple sectors of society. However, as only few taxa have been formally assessed, the need for more studies and assessments on the impact of invasive species has been highlighted as a research priority for South Africa.

425

Indicator	Trend	Confidence
2.1. Number and status of alien species	↗	high
2.2. Extent of alien species	↗	medium
2.3. Abundance of alien species	↗	medium
2.4. Impact of alien species	↗	low

426

B1: The process of collating a list of alien species in the country has been substantially improved and documented, this will promote transparency, and facilitate management and regulatory decisions

427

428

There has been significant progress in collating a list of alien species in the country, the process and

429

list of alien species, with information, where available, on their distributions, impacts and

430

management has been documented (*established but incomplete*) {2, 4.1, 4.5, 4.8}. The development

431

of documented and repeatable workflows ensures it is clear why species are included on the list and

432

facilitates updates to the lists (*established but incomplete*) {Appendix 4}. To date the list includes

433

records of over 3 800 alien species present in South Africa, at least a third of which are recorded as

434

invasive (*established but incomplete*) {2.1}. As data are captured and collated these numbers will

435

increase: key sources still need to be verified and integrated into the list (particularly species in

436

cultivation); and many alien species are yet to be detected and documented. A comprehensive list will

437

facilitate tracking the *number and status of alien species* over time, feeding into management planning

438

and facilitating regulatory decisions.

⁷→ no change; ↗ an increase; ↘ a decrease

439 **B2: The adoption of standard practises to integrate biodiversity data means data on species**
440 **occurrences can be used as the basis for models and indicators to monitor biodiversity status and**
441 **change**

442 Biodiversity monitoring requires access to rapid, reliable, and repeatable monitoring data that can be
443 used to inform policy, decision-making, and interventions. The process of mobilising and analysing
444 spatial data has been improved by adopting practices from other global initiatives that have developed
445 pipelines to integrate biodiversity data into data cubes that can be used for models and indicators of
446 biodiversity monitoring (*established but incomplete*) {2.2, 3.1}. These data cubes and workflows have
447 assisted with the automation and standardisation of the process and how the status reports are
448 communicated.

449 **B3: Knowledge of the distribution and abundance of alien plant species has improved; but**
450 **structured surveillance remains essential to inform management and track trends**

451 There is limited data to estimate the extent and abundance of alien species in South Africa (*established*
452 *but incomplete*) {2.2, 2.3}. Several atlasing and remote sensing projects have provided estimates of
453 the abundance of selected invasive plant taxa in water catchments and terrestrial biomes {2.3}. Data
454 from the surveys indicate that most of the taxa have increased in cover despite mechanical and
455 chemical control efforts, but there were decreases in cover for taxa under biological control
456 (*established but incomplete*). There is however no national long-term structured monitoring project
457 to track plant invasions across South Africa. Ensuring the long-term sustainability of structured
458 surveillance efforts and integrating these with other monitoring projects (e.g., citizen science
459 observations), will support management planning and facilitate regulatory decisions.

460 **B4: Invasive species, in particular trees and freshwater fishes, have ‘Major’ negative impacts on**
461 **people and nature across the country**

462 The negative impacts of invasive species on biodiversity and people’s livelihoods are known to be
463 substantial (*established but incomplete*) {2.4}. Eleven (11) tree or shrub species, five fish species, two
464 grass species, and one invertebrate species have been assessed to cause ‘Major’ or ‘Massive’ negative
465 impacts at a national level (*established but incomplete*) {2.4}. This number is based on 36 assessments
466 using the IUCN’s Environmental Impact Classification for Alien Taxa methodology. Complementary
467 assessments using risk analyses and findings from the IPBES IAS Assessment confirm that these species
468 cause widespread harm across multiple sectors of society. The need for more studies and assessments
469 on the impact of invasive species has been highlighted as a research priority for South Africa. The
470 development and implementation of country-level species-specific management strategies informed
471 by impact assessments would help protect biodiversity and ensure that ecosystem services essential
472 to human wellbeing are maintained.

473

C) How sites are invaded and impacted

474

Head-line indicator	Trend	Notes
3. <i>Extent of area that suffers 'Major' impacts from invasions</i>	not reassessed	Biological invasions continue to cause impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human livelihoods by reducing South Africa's water resources, degrading pasturelands, and exacerbating fire. These estimates, however, have not been recently revised.

475

Indicator	Trend	Confidence
3.1. <i>Alien species richness</i>	↗	low
3.2. <i>Relative invasive abundance</i>	↗	low
3.3. <i>Impact of invasions</i>	not reassessed	

476

C1: Invasions are distributed across the country including in protected areas

477

Invasive species are distributed across the country, with most broad-scale administrative units and biogeographical regions being invaded by a variety of taxa (*established but incomplete*) {3.1}. Most alien species are found in the Western Cape, Eastern Cape, and KwaZulu-Natal (*established but incomplete*) {3.1}, and around major urban centres (*established but incomplete*) {3.1}. This is likely because some species are commensal with humans, most were first introduced to urban centres, and because of greater sampling around urban areas (in particular there has been a rapid, recent increase in observations from citizen scientist platforms such iNaturalist) (*established but incomplete*) {3.1}. Robust and reliable monitoring systems that consistently track the distribution and abundance of alien species across the country are, however, lacking and thus the extent of invasions and the effectiveness of interventions cannot be assessed with a high degree of certainty. Data on the distribution and abundance of alien species need to be collected, collated, and integrated into national and global databases to facilitate the planning of interventions.

479

C2: Country-wide assessments indicate that invasive plant species are widespread, with several biomes and strategic water catchment areas experiencing substantial and increasing levels of invasion despite ongoing control efforts, except for taxa subjected to biological control

480

There are a few country-wide estimates for the relative abundance of invasive species. Estimates are available for invasive plants in protected areas managed by the South African National Parks and CapeNature and invasions in these protected areas were found to be minor to extensive (*well established*) {3.2}. The National Invasive Alien Plant Survey (2008–2023) provided estimates for selected plant species in terrestrial biomes and water catchment areas in South Africa. The Indian

497 Ocean Coastal Belt (11%), Fynbos (5%), Albany Thicket (3%), and Grassland (3%) biomes exhibited the
498 highest proportions of invaded land. Six water catchment areas, which also serve as strategic water
499 source areas, recorded relatively high invasive plant cover (4–10%).

500 **C3: The impact of invasions on water resources, rangeland productivity, and biodiversity are severe;**
501 **workflows to track these impacts are vital for prioritising interventions but are currently not in place**

502 A handful of influential historical studies have indicated the severe impacts of invasions on water
503 resources, rangeland productivity and biodiversity. These studies showed that: i) invasive trees use 3–
504 5% of South Africa’s surface water runoff each year; ii) invasive plants reduce the value of livestock
505 production from natural rangelands by ZAR 340 million per year; and iii) biological invasions are
506 responsible for 25% of all biodiversity loss, placing them as the largest impact to South Africa’s
507 biodiversity after cultivation and land degradation (*established but incomplete*) {3.3}. These negative
508 impacts have not recently been reassessed, and workflows are required to improve the applicability
509 and repeatability of the methods. Systematically quantifying and monitoring impacts on sites would
510 facilitate the prioritisation of interventions; provide the justification for government investment to
511 control biological invasions; and provide important background to communicate the severity of the
512 issue to society.

513

514

D) What has been done to address the problem

515

Head-line indicator	Trend	Notes
4. <i>Level of success in managing invasions</i>	Not reassessed	Interventions are in place to address all facets of managing biological invasions, but funding is insufficient and declining. Despite local successes, invasions are increasing in extent and impact when assessed at a national scale.

516

Indicator	Trend	Confidence
4.1. <i>Quality of regulatory framework</i>	→	medium
4.2. <i>Money spent</i>	↘	medium
4.3. <i>Planning coverage</i>	→	medium
4.4. <i>Pathways treated</i>	→	low
4.5. <i>Species treated</i>	not assessed	NA
4.6. <i>Sites treated</i>	not assessed	NA
4.7. <i>Effectiveness of pathway treatments</i>	→	low
4.8. <i>Effectiveness of species treatments</i>	not assessed	NA
4.9. <i>Effectiveness of site treatments</i>	not assessed	NA

517

D1: Funding for the management of biological invasions has declined steeply

518 Funding provided by the DFFE's Working for Water programme was 54.5% less than in the preceding
 519 three years (*established*) {4.2}. National conservation agencies (South African National Parks and the
 520 Isimangaliso Agency) received 60% of this money, and as a result provincial conservation agencies
 521 experienced even steeper declines in funding, with some receiving no funding at all. In addition,
 522 funding from DFFE for research and implementation of biological control has been discontinued. A
 523 review of funding revealed that historic spending was 4% of that predicted as necessary for complete
 524 control to be achieved (*established but incomplete*) {4.2}. Additional funding will have to be found and
 525 efficiently used if significant impacts are to be avoided.

526

D2: South Africa has an innovative regulatory system to address biological invasions, but its implementation is limited

527

528 The National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act's Alien and Invasive Species Regulations
 529 and Lists were revised in 2020 and came into effect in 2021. A process has been set up to ensure that
 530 regular, transparent changes informed by evidence can be made to the lists in future (*established but
 531 incomplete*) {4.1}. Capacity shortages have significantly restricted the government's ability to address
 532 most aspects requiring monitoring of compliance with the regulations. Monitoring the effectiveness
 533 of the regulations and engaging with stakeholders would help identify additional measures to improve
 534 the regulations and their acceptability.

535 **D3: Intentional legal introductions are well regulated. The National Border Management Authority**
536 **(BMA) became operational in 2023; but inspections for environmental threats have declined and**
537 **illegal and accidental introductions continue**

538 All legal introductions of new alien taxa require import permits, with permits issued only if the risks
539 are demonstrated to be sufficiently low (*well established*) {4.1}. A major development to improve the
540 integrated governance of South Africa's biosecurity and to prevent illegal and accidental introductions
541 was the establishment of the BMA in 2020 (becoming fully operational in 2023) (*well established*)
542 {4.4}. However, most pathways are either not managed or are partially managed (management
543 focuses on specific species or is not national in scope), the effectiveness of pathway interventions is
544 not monitored, and the number of inspections for environmental threats has declined since 2022
545 (*established but incomplete*) {4.4, 4.7}. Consequently, illegal and accidental introductions are
546 continuing (*established but incomplete*) {1.2, 4.7}. Increasing capacity would help prevent future
547 harmful introductions.

548 **D4: The ongoing absence of monitoring systems limits South Africa's ability to improve the**
549 **management of biological invasions**

550 Many species have been subjected to ongoing control interventions but it is not possible to quantify
551 the number of species involved as information is not reported. The area under management is also
552 not consistently reported, precluding an estimation of the indicator for sites managed.

553 **D5: Biological invasions have been effectively managed in a few cases, with biological control**
554 **proving particularly successful**

555 Invasive species have been brought under control in some cases (*established but incomplete*) {4.4–
556 4.9}. In particular, investment into biological control of invasive species has resulted in at least 17
557 species being brought under permanent control and caused reductions in many other invasions (*well*
558 *established*) {4.8}. Several species that are under biological control have decreased in cover at a
559 national level over 15 years, while all other surveyed species that were not subjected to biological
560 control have increased in cover despite ongoing mechanical and chemical control efforts. From these
561 studies it is clear that effective control options are often available, but are reliant on sufficient
562 resources to implement them. Interventions aimed at preventing the introduction of new invasive
563 species, and eradicating or controlling those that have already become established, will deliver
564 positive returns on investment, provided that they are implemented timeously and efficiently.
565 Investments in control are economically justified in terms of avoided costs. Biological control can
566 deliver particularly effective control. Given that funding will remain inadequate, it is important to
567 prioritise those interventions that will have the greatest impact, so as to avoid ongoing increases in
568 negative impacts.

569 **E) Monitoring the status and management of biological invasions in South Africa in the context of**
570 **what is needed to improve the effectiveness of interventions**

571

572 **E1: South Africa has a sophisticated range of processes to address biological invasions but the**
573 **monitoring of these is currently insufficient to evaluate their effectiveness**

574 [details and links to be added in the final report, including on gaps in the collection, collation, and flow
575 of information that if filled would allow for interventions to be evaluated; and in light of the results of
576 the survey questionnaire]

577 **E2: Integrated governance will be crucial to improve the effectiveness of interventions**

578 [details and links to be added in the final report; linking to the 2023 IPBES IAS Assessment]

579 **Noteworthy invasions (2023–2025)**

580 The invasions noted below are indicative of invasions in South Africa over the period covered by the
581 report. This selection was made by the status report team and is not intended to imply that these taxa
582 must be prioritised for management.

583 ***Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *canariensis* (Fusarium wilt)**

584 Fusarium wilt, a plant disease caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *canariensis*, was first recorded in
585 South Africa from samples taken in November 2023 from three ornamental *Phoenix canariensis*
586 (Canary Island date palms) individuals displaying symptoms at the V&A Waterfront in Cape Town
587 (Balocchi et al. 2024). Believed to be a recent introduction, Fusarium wilt is most often spread through
588 the movement of contaminated plant material, and the use of
589 contaminated tools. A second plant pathogen, *Nalanthamala*
590 *vermoesonii*, was also identified for the first time in South Africa from the
591 same samples. This pathogen can cause pink rot disease in a diversity of
592 palms, however, it is often a secondary infection, associated with other
593 primary and more serious diseases such as Fusarium wilt. There is no
594 known effective treatment for Fusarium wilt and infected palms inevitably
595 die. While *P. canariensis*, an alien ornamental in South Africa, is the main
596 host for Fusarium wilt, other palms used as ornamentals [*P. sylvestris*
597 (silver date palm)] and in agriculture [*P. dactylifera* (date palm)] are also
598 susceptible, so too is the native species *P. reclinata* (wild date palm).

An ornamental palm showing symptoms of Fusarium wilt at the V&A Waterfront in Cape Town—Paul Barker

599 ***Amathia verticillata* (spaghetti bryozoan)**

600 The alien marine bryozoan *Amathia verticillata* was first discovered on a jetty in the Langebaan Lagoon
601 Marine Protected Area in November 2023 (Ackland et al. 2025).
602 *Amathia verticillata* is likely native to the Caribbean Sea and is invasive
603 in many parts of the world. *Amathia verticillata* probably arrived
604 within Saldanha Bay via biofouling, and subsequently spread through
605 fragmentation. It is now abundant at the head of the tidal lagoon and
606 has been found in meadows of the endangered seagrass *Zostera*
607 *capensis*. As the species has caused mass mortality in seagrass beds in
608 parts of the world where it is invasive, its overlapping distribution with
609 *Z. capensis* within Langebaan Lagoon is a cause for concern.

Amathia verticillata (spaghetti bryozoan) on Kraaibaai West Coast National Park Jetty—Sarah Ackland

610 ***Membranipora membranacea* (sea mat)**

611 A second alien marine bryozoan was identified in March 2024 on
612 heavily encrusted kelp that washed up on Muizenberg beach in False
613 Bay (Steyn and Robinson 2025). This bryozoan is native to Europe and
614 was likely introduced through shipping – either through hull fouling or
615 the release of ballast water (cf. Harrower et al. 2018 for the definition
616 of these pathways). Kelp encrusted with this bryozoan washed up again
617 in October 2024, suggesting that *M. membranacea* is established
618 within the bay. The species has invaded kelp forests in the north-west
619 Atlantic, where it has caused mass kelp mortality and the loss of entire
620 kelp forests, with cascading effects on food webs and ecosystem
621 functioning. Of particular concern are the kelp forests within Table
622 Mountain National Park Marine Protected Area, which has been
623 established precisely to protect such ecosystems.

Membranipora membranacea (sea mat) encrusting *Ecklonia maxima* washed up on Muizenberg beach in Cape Town—Clara Steyn

624 ***Pinus* species (pines)**

625 Pines have historically been extensively planted for forestry across the Cape Floristic Region (CFR).
626 Escapes from these plantings (termed ‘wilding’ pines) have invaded large areas—over 900 km² in the
627 CFR mainly of *Pinus pinaster* (cluster pine) and *P. radiata* (Monterey pine). These invasions pose
628 significant threats to water resources and the CFR’s unique biodiversity, and increase the risk of
629 damaging wildfires. Pines in the Cape are a
630 classic example of conflict species that can
631 deliver benefits and cause harm. A recent review
632 (Martin et al. 2025) identified several
633 opportunities to sustainably accommodate
634 these trees, including deploying biological
635 control, using less invasive hybrids, practicing
636 triage by prioritising areas for focussed
637 interventions, and improving compliance with
638 regulations. Ensuring optimal outcomes will
639 remain challenging.

Pine trees (*Pinus* species) in the Cape Floristic Region—Andrew Turner

640

641 **Agapornis species (lovebirds)**

642 Lovebirds are pretty, affectionate parrots; they are the most popular parrots in the global bird trade
643 (Chan et al. 2021). South Africa is an important global player in the trade of lovebirds with significant
644 large-scale breeding operations in the country (Emre Can et al. 2019; Chan et al. 2021; Shivambu et
645 al. 2024b), although the socio-economic benefits have not yet been
646 quantified. *Agapornis* species that are frequently exported or sold include
647 alien species like *A. fischeri* (Fischer’s lovebird) and *A. personatus* (yellow-
648 collared lovebird), and the native species *A. roseicollis* (rosy-faced
649 lovebird). Of concern, however, are records from social media (Shivambu
650 et al. 2024a) and citizen science platforms (e.g., iNaturalist) that show
651 lovebirds escaping or being released from captivity, with some populations
652 likely to have established, including native-alien populations of *A.*
653 *roseicollis*. Alien *Agapornis* species can hybridise with the native *A.*
654 *roseicollis*. Stakeholder engagement with breeders and traders,
655 particularly around the threat of hybridisation with native species is
656 needed, and the option for permitting under the A&IS Regulations could
657 be explored (cf. Table S4.1).

The native lovebird *Agapornis roseicollis* (rosy-faced lovebird) for sale in South Africa—
Katelyn Faulkner

658 **Drosophila suzukii (spotted wing drosophila)**

659 *Drosophila suzukii*, a fruit fly native to Asia, has been introduced to many parts of the world, where it
660 is a significant agricultural pest, causing damage to unripe berries and stone fruits. Due to its potential
661 to invade and the associated economic risks, a pro-active survey was initiated in South Africa in 2021
662 (Steyn et al. 2025). The survey was funded by Hortgro and the South African Table Grape Industry, in
663 collaboration with Insect Science, and comprised a network of over 70 traps placed in the main fruit
664 growing areas of the Western Cape (Steyn et al. 2025). The pest was eventually recorded, however,
665 from a trap opportunistically placed in April 2022 near a farm office in Misgund, Eastern Cape (Steyn
666 et al. 2025). *Drosophila suzukii* has subsequently been recorded in eight provinces, including the
667 Western Cape (Steyn et al. 2025). The rapid action taken following the detection of *D. suzukii*, such as
668 the initiation of a national multi-industry trapping network and the establishment of the Monitoring
669 Centre of Excellence at FruitFly Africa, aims to ensure the pest is kept under control and any impacts
670 reduced.

671

672 **Invasions in the Table Mountain National Park**

673 Alien plant invasions have been managed in the Table Mountain National Park (TMNP) since the 1940s
674 (Macdonald et al. 1986). The TMNP has received generous funding from the Working for Water
675 programme since 1995—with ZAR 115 million (unadjusted for inflation) spent 2010–2022; and 22 875
676 ha treated (the whole of the TMNP is 24 500 ha) 2002–2020 (with an average of 4.2 follow up
677 treatments). This level of funding has resulted in good
678 progress towards reducing invasions to a level that can
679 be maintained sustainably (Cheney et al. 2020). This
680 example shows that management can be effective if
681 funding is sustained, though providing similar levels of
682 funding to target other protected areas will be
683 challenging [cf. amounts spent on provincial nature
684 reserves in the Cape Floristic Region (van Wilgen et al.
685 2025)].

Effective control of alien plants in the Table Mountain National Park—Nicola van Wilgen

686 **Introductory Chapter: Processes used to construct this report**

687 Lead authors: John R. Wilson, Tsungai A. Zengeya, Katelyn T. Faulkner, Brian W. van Wilgen, Masingitla
688 P. Mtileni

689 **0.1. Background, context, and process**

690 **0.1.1. The importance of biological invasions to South Africa**

691 Biological invasions are amongst the leading causes of global change—they have had profound
692 negative impacts on people and nature for centuries; are currently a significant drain on South Africa’s
693 economy and are negatively impacting native biodiversity; and pose a major threat to both the quality
694 of life of future generations and the globally unique flora and fauna that are an integral part of this
695 country. The problem is complex and set to grow. Invasive species come from many different taxa,
696 invade different habitats, and cause various types of impacts sometimes in ways which are not yet
697 fully understood but that will have profound effects on the ability of ecosystems to deliver services to
698 people.

699 Thankfully, however, targeted interventions can be highly cost-effective, and so, while interventions
700 can be complicated and costly, by working together as a society we can protect our biodiversity and
701 natural capital from biological invasions (cf. IPBES 2023). The nature of the impacts and the types of
702 responses needed mean that biological invasions are a significant cross-cutting issue for South Africa
703 that is managed by a range of stakeholders using a variety of approaches. This requires integrated
704 governance, and relies on mechanisms to assess progress at a strategic level (i.e., a status report; cf.
705 Chapter 5).

706 **0.1.2. The mandate, purpose, independence, and structure of the fourth status report**

707 The issue of biological invasions has received significant recent global attention with the release of the
708 Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services’s ‘Thematic
709 Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their control’ in September 2023 (IPBES, 2023⁸;
710 hereafter the IPBES IAS Assessment); and the discussion around international targets for biodiversity,
711 specifically the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) Target 6 on biological
712 invasions.

713 *Target 6: Reduce the Introduction of Invasive Alien Species by 50% and Minimize Their Impact*
714 *Eliminate, minimize, reduce and or mitigate the impacts of invasive alien species on biodiversity*
715 *and ecosystem services by identifying and managing pathways of the introduction of alien species,*

⁸<https://www.ipbes.net/ias>

716 *preventing the introduction and establishment of priority invasive alien species, reducing the rates*
717 *of introduction and establishment of other known or potential invasive alien species by at least 50*
718 *per cent, by 2030, eradicating or controlling invasive alien species especially in priority sites, such*
719 *as islands.*⁹

720 The fourth status report sits firmly within this context, but the specific mandate for the status report
721 originally arose from section 11 of the A&IS Regulations of 2014 that were published 1 August 2014
722 and promulgated in October 2014. Revised regulations were published 18 September 2020 and
723 promulgated 1 March 2021, with section 13 stating:

- 724 (1) *The Institute*¹⁰ *or a body designated by the Institute must, for the purpose of reporting as*
725 *contemplated in section 11(1)(a)(iii) of the Act, submit a report on the status of listed*
726 *invasive species to the Minister within three years of the date on which these regulations*
727 *come into effect, and at least every three years thereafter*¹¹.
- 728 (2) *A report contemplated in sub-regulation (1) must contain a summary and assessment of—*
729 *(a) the status of listed invasive species and other species that have been subjected to a risk*
730 *assessment; and*
731 *(b) the effectiveness of these regulations and control measures based* *inter alia* *on*
732 *information from—*
733 *(i) notifications received from owners of land regarding listed invasive species*
734 *occurring on their land;*
735 *(ii) permits issued for listed invasive species;*
736 *(iii) Invasive Species Monitoring, Control and Eradication Plans received from organs*
737 *of state and management authorities of protected areas; and*
738 *(iv) emergency interventions and enforcement actions involving listed invasive*
739 *species.*
740 (3) *In preparing a report contemplated in sub-regulation (1), the Institute must carry out the*
741 *research and monitoring necessary to identify the matters contemplated in sub-regulation*
742 *(2).*

743 More broadly, however, the status report aims to strengthen the links between research, policy, and
744 management by detailing the current status and providing support to decision makers that is policy
745 relevant but not policy prescriptive (see Chapter 5). In this sense, the status report will play an
746 important role evaluating progress towards the goals of South Africa's forthcoming national strategy
747 on biological invasions¹². This status report is produced by SANBI in collaboration with many partners

⁹<https://www.cbd.int/gbf/targets/6>

¹⁰The South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI)

¹¹As the latest version of the regulations came into effect in March 2021, this would imply by March 2027, but to maintain triennial cycles in line with the original 2014 A&IS Regulations, the date is taken to be October 2026. It takes time to compile, revise, and produce these reports. Therefore, a cut-off date is needed, after which no new data are considered. This fourth report is thus entitled 'The status of biological invasions and their management in South Africa in 2025', as it reports on the status up to the end of 2025, and published in 2026.

¹²South Africa's draft National Invasive Species Strategy and Action Plan (NISSAP) is discussed in Section 4.1

748 (primarily the CIB), but the intention is for the report to be an independent assessment (see S0.1 for
749 a discussion on measures taken in an effect to ensure the independence of the report).

750 Reports have been produced every three years based on data up to the end of December 2016, 2019,
751 and 2022 respectively. The reports are structured around an indicator framework that explicitly
752 considers biological invasions in terms of pathways, species, sites, and interventions (Figure 0.2). This
753 indicator framework provides a transparent and objective method for the establishment of baselines
754 against which to assess trends, set realistic management targets, highlight important gaps in the
755 evidence needed to support decision-making, and support international reporting (see Section 5.7).

756 The report is comprised of chapters based on this framework (i.e., on pathways, species, sites, and
757 interventions). Each chapter starts with key findings, then for each indicator a summary of the status
758 and then a discussion of key changes and recent noteworthy events, often with case studies in the
759 form of text boxes. In addition, for this report, an additional chapter specifically focusses on
760 monitoring. The purpose of the chapter is to highlight what monitoring is on-going and what is
761 required to better understand and manage biological invasions in South Africa. The report concludes
762 with a chapter on key gaps. Much of the detail underlying the production of the report is contained
763 within the appendices and supplementary material available on-line (links to them are on the last page
764 of the report).

765 Like the IPBES assessments, the status report also presents key messages with an evaluation of the
766 confidence with which each message is made and links through to relevant material in the chapters
767 that provides the underlying evidence. A new feature in this fourth report is a section on noteworthy
768 invasions. These are both new species recently found in South Africa and those for which new
769 information has become available highlighting impacts or successful control measures.

770 **0.1.3. Synopsis of previous reports and the major goals of the previous reports**

771 Over the production of the preceding status reports, there have been major improvements in how
772 data are presented, how changes are tracked (Table S0.1), and the degree to which the information
773 presented is consistent with international best practice. The development of documented and
774 repeatable workflows has ensured that it is now clear why species are included on the list of alien
775 taxa, and the workflows facilitate reviews and updates. The focus for the next phase is to ensure that
776 all historical data sources are incorporated into the list of alien taxa and to put systems in place to
777 incorporate new information as it becomes available. The process of developing the report is
778 discussed in the context of the list of alien taxa presented in Zengeya et al. (in press). In the following,

779 we provide a synopsis of the different reports noting the key changes made for each report (cf. Table
780 S1 of Zengeya et al. 2025).

781 The first report was largely based on the mandated requirement for reporting on alien taxa listed
782 under the A&IS Regulations. But as it was the first such report anywhere in the world, much of the
783 structure had to be developed. Following the FAIR data principles, the information produced was
784 'Findable' and 'Reusable' but was not 'Accessible' or 'Interoperable'. The primary goals¹³ of the first
785 report were to:

- 786 ✓ Initiate the process of compiling the report
- 787 ✓ Develop indicators and test whether they were fit for the purpose
- 788 ✓ Initiate the process for sourcing information and engaging specialist contributors

789 A major lesson during writing the second report was the importance of having processes so that
790 updates to reports can be made more easily and so that changes could be tracked. The second report
791 had a greater focus on specifying sources of information and ensuring information was 'Accessible'
792 and 'Interoperable'. The primary goals of the second report were to:

- 793 ✓ Ensure data were curated in a manner that was FAIR and tidy
- 794 ✓ Adjust indicators and protocols
- 795 ✓ Develop a method to track changes over time
- 796 ○ Test the indicators (this was addressed in the third report, specifically for the Prince Edward
797 Islands)
- 798 ○ Expand efforts to access data (this is on-going)

799 When the third report was produced, standards had been tested and processes more clearly codified.
800 There was greater focus on making the data tidy and FAIR, including through systematic inclusion of
801 the evidence underpinning the information. Information was not carried over from previous reports
802 if supporting evidence was not available. A greater number of sources were incorporated. The primary
803 goals of the third report were to:

- 804 ✓ Produce a defensible list of alien taxa
- 805 ✓ Pilot indicators for selected case studies
- 806 ○ Contribute to the national strategy on biological invasions [this was achieved within the
807 relevant time-frame, but will be on-going until the National Invasive Species Strategy and

¹³ fully achieved (✓), partially achieved (○)

- 808 Action Plan (NISSAP) is completed at which point the goal will be to provide a strategic
809 assessment of the NISSAP]
- 810 ○ Assess impacts for key taxa [this is an on-going process linked both to the process of producing
811 risk analyses in support of the A&IS Lists (see Section 4.1) and to developing international best
812 practice]
 - 813 ○ Develop processes to work on impacts on sites (it was found to be very difficult to replicate
814 previous studies estimating site-level impacts, see Section 3.3; this is a significant on-going
815 gap, see Chapter 6)
 - 816 ○ Develop processes to get estimates of the effectiveness of management (data tracking
817 effectiveness are scarce and information that has been collated is often very hard to interpret
818 in terms of invasion-specific outcomes, see Sections 4.7–4.9; specific focus is needed on this
819 from the ground up, Chapter 5)

820 **Table 0.1.** The specific goals for this fourth report. These goals are in addition to meeting the mandated
821 requirements and building on the previous goals.

Goal	Details	Main sections where the issue is addressed
Review indicators nationally and globally to improve national processes	South Africa has an international obligation to report to the CBD on progress on biological invasions. Indicators are being developed to evaluate progress towards the targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KM-GBF) with desirable properties of indicators proposed. The indicator framework used in this report needs to be evaluated in these contexts and considering experiences to date.	Section 0.2.2 Section 5.7
Review of gaps identified as part of IPBES IAS Assessment	There is a need to evaluate issues raised in the IPBES IAS Assessment within the South African context and to learn from the IPBES process.	Section 0.3 Chapter 6
Stakeholder consultation to improve the report	Given that this is the fourth report, many of the systems have been tested and revised. It is important at this stage to reflect on how the reports are being used, and what end users would like the reports to address.	Section 5.2
Review and update the list of alien taxa	Ensure taxonomy and nomenclature are clearly specified. Incorporate more data sources. Develop processes to integrate with international and national databases.	Sections 0.4, 2.1
Develop workflows for selected indicators	While some of the report processes have already been codified as workflows, a sustainable repeatable reporting process will require more systems to be set up particularly if the goal of developing a dashboard is to be achieved.	Section 0.4 Appendix 2
Integrate biodiversity data into report processes	Ensure information can be readily incorporated and analysed. Specifically this was addressed by trialling data pipelines developed as part of the B-Cubed project ¹⁴ .	Section 5.3 Box 2.2

¹⁴<https://b-cubed.eu/>

822

823 **0.1.4. Aspects not covered**

824 The aspects not covered are similar to those in previous reports. Four broad aspects not covered are
825 highlighted here.

826 As the status report's primary function is to report on environmental issues, there is a limited focus
827 on the socio-economic problems caused by biological invasions. The most damaging invasive species
828 are human diseases. These are not included in this report. Similarly, pests and weeds are a major
829 threat to food security, a central goal of sustainable development, but are not within this report's
830 remit unless such taxa also impact on, or threaten, natural ecosystems. Saying that, there is an
831 increasing recognition that biodiversity and health are inextricably linked. Moreover, in some
832 situations, interventions are only effective if environmental health, animal health, plant health, and
833 human health are considered in concert (the One Health and One Biosecurity approaches; see Box
834 1.2). Without well-established metrics and indicators to monitor such linkages, and in the absence of
835 detailed cross-cutting case studies that explicitly consider biological invasions, these issues are not
836 addressed in any depth in this report. If these reports are to holistically address biological invasions,
837 future reports will need to jointly consider the status and management of biological invasions that
838 affect all sectors.

839 Secondly, there is a suite of native species that can have undesirable impacts that are similar to the
840 impacts caused by alien species, but which are precipitated by changes in land use or other aspects of
841 global change. Examples include bush encroachment by native plants and the spread of many native
842 bird species into urban areas. These taxa can present problems that require management, but such
843 management needs to be in the context of the taxa being within their native ranges. The report does,
844 however, cover taxa that are native to one part of South Africa but alien to another part of the country
845 [as defined by Nelufule et al. (2022)].

846 Thirdly, the last report included a section (Chapter 5) on the status and management of biological
847 invasions on the Prince Edward Islands (the PEIs: Marion Island and Prince Edward Island). The chapter
848 was subsequently expanded, used as a test of the indicator framework, and published (Fernández
849 Winzer et al. 2025b). One recommendation was that regular (annual) updates on the status of
850 biological invasions and their management on the PEIs are needed and should be led by those
851 responsible for the islands. As such, this report does not include an update on the situation on the
852 PEIs, but such an update might be appropriate for this report series if reports are produced less often
853 (e.g., every decade).

854 Finally, it is important to note that the national status report is intended to be policy relevant but not
855 policy prescriptive. As such, specific recommendations are not provided. The focus is on reporting on
856 the status with an assessment of what is preventing improvements in the status or in how the status
857 is assessed, rather than outlining actions that are necessary to achieve a specific goal (cf. the NISSAP
858 and Chapter 5).

859 **0.1.5. Road map for this report**

860 The process to compile the report was broadly similar to the previous reports (Figure 0.1), with largely
861 the same core team, consisting of the South African National Biodiversity Institute as the lead institute,
862 the Centre for Invasion Biology as a collaborating partner, and various managers, researchers, private
863 individuals, and institutions providing information and comments on draft reports.

864 Review of release of 3rd report and essential workflows identified: The SANBI-CIB drafting team
865 reflected on the report launch and how it was received, and in particular identified the need for closer
866 engagement with affected government departments. It was noted that by providing an opportunity
867 to evaluate the findings and develop appropriate responses ahead of the report launch, affected
868 agencies would be in a better position to respond to and uptake the findings. The drafting team also
869 identified essential workflows for the production of the report that needed to be set up during this
870 report cycle (Section 0.4).

871 A reference and advisory committee (RAC): a RAC was established to provide oversight of the process
872 and review documents produced. The first meeting of the RAC was on 30 July 2025 at which a zero-
873 order draft (consisting of an annotated table of contents) was approved. The first draft of the status
874 report was sent to the RAC on 30 September 2025¹⁵ for review – they were given a month to comment.
875 The RAC evaluated the status report team’s responses to the comments received at the second
876 meeting of the RAC on 5 December 2025. Following public review of the second draft, a final draft was
877 produced and sent to the RAC on 31 March 2026. The RAC met for a final time in April 2026 to discuss
878 the final draft, and particularly the key messages. The Chair of the RAC reviewed how the comments
879 received during all rounds of review had been addressed, i.e., acted in a review editor role.

880 Collate and review available information: Information was incorporated into the report primarily from
881 published literature and unpublished information provided by stakeholders. Information contained in
882 the report is based on data available to the report writing team as of the end of December 2025. As

¹⁵Throughout the draft versions of the report, the tense used is as it is intended to be in the final report, i.e., in the past tense rather than the future tense.

883 part of this report cycle, and to further develop the list of alien taxa as part of the report, three linked
 884 journal special issues on 'Developing lists of alien taxa in the Global South' were produced (Box 2.1).

885

886 **Figure 0.1.** Key steps in the production of the report 'the Status of Biological Invasions and their Management
 887 in South Africa'. The Minister is the South African Minister of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment; the RAC
 888 is the research and advisory committee; and SANBI is the South African National Biodiversity Institute.

889

890 Stakeholder engagement: Stakeholder engagement was an on-going process linked to the other
891 activities. Initially the drafting team engaged directly with specialists to obtain information that was
892 not readily accessible and identified stakeholders to be contacted for input and review. Stakeholders
893 identified previously and those who provided comments on previous reports were asked for updates
894 (see S0.3 for details and a draft letter). New potential contributors were contacted on an ad hoc basis
895 as information became available and in response to the public consultation. Contributors came from
896 academic institutions; research institutes and science councils; national, provincial, and local
897 government departments and protected areas; and from private individuals who were interested and
898 affected. Contributions from the identified stakeholders were in the form of data provision,
899 commenting on drafts, and assisting with writing up case studies.

900 All feedback was recorded and the comments responded to in line with international best practice
901 (IPBES 2018). The comments received and the responses from the status report drafting team were
902 documented and are available for scrutiny from SANBI on request.

903 Public review and stakeholder questionnaire: The second draft was completed by the end of
904 December 2025. Given it was not appropriate for the draft to be sent for review over the festive
905 period, the draft was sent for public comment during the period 30 January to 1 March 2026. The
906 request for review was submitted to: a South African list server on biological invasions
907 (invasives@wordlink.co.za); heads of relevant national and provincial government departments;
908 heads of relevant academic departments and institutions; and professional societies and forums
909 (including the Royal Society of South Africa; the Akademie vir Wetenskap en Kuns; the Zoological,
910 Entomological, and Botanical Societies; Birdlife South Africa; and the Wildlife and Environment Society
911 of South Africa). A copy of the draft for public comment was attached to the formal notice and was
912 available for download online (<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17697657>). Comments were
913 received from ...¹⁶.

914 In previous report cycles there have been multiple rounds of public review. This was largely as the
915 structure of the report was still being formulated, and so the first round of comment was focussed on
916 structural issues and what the report should include. The later round of public comment was focussed
917 on the specifics of the content. To engage stakeholders with the broader structure and purpose of the
918 report as well as guiding future reports, a questionnaire was circulated in parallel to the public review
919 of the fourth report.

¹⁶the number of people and institutions commenting to be added later.

920 From finalisation to report release: The final draft was produced on 31 March 2026 and discussed with
921 the RAC. All remaining content issues were concluded, and the report was finalised on 31 May 2026.
922 The final report was sent in June 2026 to the SANBI Graphics team for copy-editing, layout, design,
923 and printing. The report was then submitted to the SANBI Board in September 2026 for their
924 consideration at a meeting in October 2026. After board approval, the SANBI CEO submitted the report
925 to the Minister of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment, and, at the same time, a copy of the report
926 was submitted to the key national government departments that are responsible for addressing
927 biological invasions (the DFFE, the BMA, and the DoA). This provided those departments with an
928 opportunity to prepare for responding to media enquiries or public concerns and to seek clarification
929 from the report drafting team as needed, noting that no changes could be made to the report during
930 this period. To maximise publicity and media uptake of the report, the report is intended to be
931 released to the public in early January 2027 in time for the fresh news cycle of the year though that is
932 ultimately at the discretion of the Minister. As with previous reports, information will be submitted to
933 the South African State of the Environment Report process (<http://soer.environment.gov.za/soer/>).

934 Reflect on the process: After the public release of the report, the status report team will consult key
935 stakeholders including members of the RAC to reflect on the process used to compile the report and
936 to identify areas of improvement for subsequent reports.

937 **0.2. Indicators**

938 This report is structured around 20 indicators and 4 high-level indicators (Figure 0.2; Wilson et al.
939 2018). The technical details on scoring the indicators and the high-level indicators are available in
940 factsheets (Appendix 1) and the supplementary material to each chapter.

941 The indicator framework has been updated in two ways. First indicators are now assigned to
942 categories according to the theory of change approach (Section 5.3), noting that the pathway
943 indicators are of two types—those that are invasion-specific outcomes and those that are
944 corresponding pathway-specific drivers that may affect these outcome indicators (e.g., ‘1.1.
945 *Introduction pathway prominence*’ potentially affects ‘1.2. *Introduction rates*’). There are many drivers
946 that affect biological invasions (Hulme et al. 2023), and in future reports it might be desirable to
947 evaluate how the drivers in South Africa interact to impact biological invasions. There is also the
948 potential to link to other existing indicators (e.g., the ‘Biodiversity Habitat Index’ cf.
949 <https://geobon.org/ebvs/indicators/>) that might be acting as drivers of invasion (e.g., by increasing
950 habitat invasibility).

951

952 **Figure 0.2.** Indicator framework used in this report. This is based on Wilson et al. (2018) updated to link to the
 953 theory of change framework (see discussion in Section 5.3 and an example in Chapter 5). The thin arrow
 954 represents a close link between specific indicators, the broader arrows represent a link between all the
 955 indicators in a particular type and the indicators in another type. A factsheet for each indicator specified here is
 956 available in Appendix 1.

957 Second a link is made explicitly between the indicators on invasion-specific outcomes (that were
 958 developed and are used specifically for this report) and indicators of broader environmental and socio-
 959 economic outcomes that may be affected by biological invasions. The indicators related to broader
 960 outcomes are developed as part of other monitoring and reporting processes, but in some cases would
 961 be expected to be robust indicators of the value of successfully managing biological invasions [e.g.,
 962 invasive trees significantly increased the fire danger index during the June 2017 wildfires in the
 963 southern Cape (Kraaij et al. 2018)]. As for the past reports, these broader outcome indicators are
 964 discussed in part (e.g., when discussing '3.3. *Impact of invasions*'), but a more systematic process of
 965 selection, inclusion, and discussion in this report will need to be a focus of future reports.

966 Notably, the baselines proposed in previous reports needed to be revised in some instances (e.g., due
 967 to errors in the original values). This means that it is not always appropriate to compare values
 968 between the reports, and in some cases the report calculated the values that should have been in
 969 previous reports. Changes over time from these revised baselines are presented and discussed in this
 970 report, and differences in the calculation methods used between the reports are noted in the
 971 supplementary material.

972

973 **0.2.1. Indicator factsheets**

974 Indicator factsheets were developed and published in Wilson et al. (2018) based on the guidelines of
975 the Biodiversity Indicator Partnership (2011), with the addition of a section on how to define a
976 confidence level for each metric. There are several additional enabling processes that are vital for
977 successful interventions, specifically accessibility of data and information, research, organisational
978 and human capacity, and public awareness and engagement. However, indicators for these are not
979 included as they are not used for measuring the outputs or outcomes of the interventions.

980 For this report, the factsheets have been updated and revised (Appendix 1). In particular, examples of
981 each indicator are based on those used in this report or previous reports. The type of each indicator
982 is also now specified using two metrics: the DPSIR (driver, pressure, state, impact, and response)
983 framework; and a 'Theory of Change' framework [input, process, output, outcome (invasion-specific),
984 outcome (broader)]. Details of the latter are discussed in Chapter 5.

985 Vicente et al. (2022) developed eight desirable properties of indicators used to monitor biological
986 invasions—established, spatially explicit, scalable, temporal, uncertainty appraisal, taxonomic
987 representativeness, invasive alien species (IAS) specific, and reproducible. The indicator factsheets
988 now also include an analysis of the degree to which each indicator adheres to these properties (see
989 S0.4 for details of the methodology).

990 **0.2.2. International indicators**

991 The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (K-MGBF) Target 6 has the following headline
992 indicator.

- 993 • *'6.1 Rate of invasive alien species establishment'*. This indicator is similar to one of the high-
994 level indicators in this report *'1. Rate of unregulated introduction of new species'*. However,
995 the data used to calculate the headline indicator for Target 6 must take sampling effort into
996 account otherwise misleading patterns will emerge (McGeoch et al. 2023). Data gaps exist
997 (Section 6.4) and proxies of survey effort have not been routinely captured. Improved
998 institutional co-ordination would assist (e.g., with the Department of Agriculture for new
999 agricultural pest introductions). The indicator in South Africa's National Status Report on
1000 Biological Invasions differs from the headline indicator, work and capacity are required to
1001 bridge the gap, noting the stated concerns about the appropriateness of the indicator (see
1002 Section S0.6 for more details). For more details see the corresponding information on the GEO
1003 BON indicator *'Rate of invasive alien species establishment'*
1004 (<https://geobon.org/ebvs/indicators/rate-of-invasive-alien-species-spread-indicator/>).

1005 There are several additional component indicators:

- 1006 • *'Rate of invasive species impact and rate of impact'* is linked to the report indicator *'2.4 Impact*
1007 *of alien species'*. Processes are being developed to calculate the indicator based on work
1008 piloted in South Africa (Boulesnane-Guengant et al. 2025) and as part of the B-Cubed project
1009 (Chapter 5). Once developed these processes will be tested and applied in future reports.
- 1010 • *'Rate of invasive alien species spread'* is linked to several of the indicators of the report *'1.3*
1011 *Within-country pathway prominence'*, *'1.4 Within-country dispersal rates'*, and *'2.2. Extent of*
1012 *alien species'*
- 1013 • *'Number of invasive alien species introduction events'* is linked to *'1.2 Introduction rates'*.

1014 There are three complementary indicators:

- 1015 • *'Number of invasive alien species on national lists as per the Global Register of Introduced and*
1016 *Invasive Species'*. There is a GRIIS page for South Africa published on GBIF
1017 (<https://cloud.gbif.org/griis/resource?r=south-africa-griis-gbif>) although this was last updated
1018 in 2020. A workflow will be developed to convert South Africa's national list into the GRIIS
1019 format and to stream-line the process for information to be fed through to update information
1020 on the GRIIS website.
- 1021 • *'Trends in abundance, temporal occurrence and spatial distribution of non-indigenous species,*
1022 *particularly invasive, non-indigenous species, notably in risk areas (in relation to the main*
1023 *vectors and pathways of spreading of such species)'* this relates to *'3.1 Alien species richness'*
- 1024 • *'Red List Index (impacts of invasive alien species)'* this is one metric used for the indicator *'3.3*
1025 *Impact of invasions'*. The relationship between the Red Lists index and EICAT are also
1026 discussed in Van der Colff et al. (2020).

1027 **0.3. IPBES IAS Assessment**

1028 The implications of the IPBES IAS Assessment for South Africa were recently reviewed by Wilson et al.
1029 (2025). Most of the key messages of the IPBES IAS Assessment resonate strongly with the perceived
1030 situation in South Africa, with three differences highlighted: a) South Africa has shown significant
1031 progress with managing and regulating biological invasions (e.g., Wilson and Kumschick 2024); b) the
1032 available evidence does not suggest that rates of introduction have increased drastically over the past
1033 few decades (see Section 1.2); and c) there is only one example of a successful nationwide eradication
1034 to date (Davies et al. 2020; Wilson et al. 2013; cf. Section 4.8). However, in line with the findings of
1035 this report, the evidence base was scored as low in many cases.

1036 The following is part of the summary of Wilson et al. (2025):

1037 *Trends and status of biological invasions in South Africa are similar to those seen globally, but there*
1038 *are some distinct local nuances. South Africa has: 1) a long history of invasions with negative impacts*
1039 *caused especially by invasive trees and freshwater fishes, whilst invasive marine invertebrates have*
1040 *transformed large parts of the coastline; 2) a long history of control (biological control was first*
1041 *implemented in 1913) with large-scale state-run invasive species management programmes currently*
1042 *in place; 3) a comprehensive regulatory system (e.g., that provides provision for beneficial invasive*
1043 *species to be used under permits); 4) relatively high levels of awareness and engagement (at least*
1044 *among some stakeholder groups); and 5) a well-connected community of practice. Efforts to limit*
1045 *introductions (intentional or unintentional) are, however, difficult given South Africa's extensive and*
1046 *porous borders and the pressing need to increase trade. Regulatory and implementation efforts aimed*
1047 *at prevention are improving, with the newly established Border Management Authority aiming to*
1048 *integrate biosecurity interventions at ports of entry. Such integrated governance is, we argue, needed*
1049 *more broadly if affected sectors, society groups and stakeholders are to be effectively included in*
1050 *decision-making and management. A more systematic flow of information from observation to action*
1051 *is essential, as is better feedback between research, policy and implementation at all scales. Biological*
1052 *invasions will continue to pose threats, but many of these can be effectively mitigated through*
1053 *focussed interventions. Co-ordinating such interventions in the context of other cross-cutting global*
1054 *change challenges and initiatives is a cost-effective way of protecting and improving livelihoods,*
1055 *human health, quality of life and biodiversity.*

1056 **0.4. Workflows**

1057 A goal of this report is to develop workflows for key report processes (Table 0.2). In so doing, the
1058 intention is for the report process to become sustainable and repeatable. The longer-term plan is to
1059 develop an on-line resource with indicator values updated as soon as new information becomes
1060 available (i.e., a dashboard). Such a dashboard can be used to produce reports on demand and form
1061 the basis of both semi-automated annual reports and less frequent comprehensive reports; noting
1062 that such reporting will need to be in line with regulatory requirements—currently triennial reports
1063 are mandated. The workflows are also designed to ensure data are FAIR¹⁷ and tidy (Wickham 2014) in
1064 line with international best practice (IPBES 2018) and to facilitate the integration with other national
1065 and international processes.

¹⁷ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable

1066
1067
1068
1069

Table 0.2. Summary of workflows developed or proposed as part of the national status reports on biological invasions and their management in South Africa. [Note: as several of the workflows are still under development, updated versions of all workflows have not been included as part of this draft report, the current link to Appendix 2 points to the workflows outlines in SANBI and CIB (2023)].

Workflow	Description	Status
<i>Introduction pathway prominence</i>	The process needed to gather information on indicator 1.1. <i>Introduction pathway prominence</i> that addresses which pathways are operating into South Africa and estimates the volume of transport along each pathway	Updated and automated where possible
<i>Tracking data sources and adding data as published</i>	The process to collate all information sources used in the production of the report, categorise them according to the nature of the source, and ensure sources are presented in a manner that is easy to access. The steps to systematically check for new sources of information, evaluate them, and, as appropriate, filter through either to the ' <i>Adding alien taxa and enrichment data to the species list</i> ' workflow or to assign values to other indicators are outlined. This workflow does not currently include processes to contact stakeholders for information (cf. Figure 0.1 and Section S0.3)	Updated and expanded
<i>Adding alien taxa and enrichment data to the species list</i>	The list of alien taxa includes 38 variables (Zengeya et al. 2025, in press), with information for any one taxon coming from multiple, sometimes conflicting sources. A process has been developed to evaluate data sources, translate them into the variables used in the list of alien taxa (intermediate files are created and stored), and to update the list itself	Updated
<i>The permit database</i>	The DFFE issues permits to conduct otherwise prohibited activities on taxa listed under the A&IS Regulations. The workflow explains the steps to transfer the information in the DFFE's database of permits into a tidy, redacted form that can be published	Updated
<i>Money spent</i>	Information on the amount of money spent on interventions to address biological invasions is sourced primarily from various government departments	Revised
<i>Alien taxa impact assessment</i>	Based on the IUCN's EICAT scheme and the SEICAT scheme, the workflow outlines the process to collate published information and interpret it in a standardised format that can be incorporated into the list of alien taxa	Not updated
<i>Workflow to check sources for new introductions</i>	Various checks are done to identify taxa which have been recorded as present in the country since the last report. The workflow also outlines the process to incorporate such information into the list of alien taxa and aims to link to other processes for addressing new detections	New
<i>Species treated</i>	Information is sourced primarily from various government departments on which taxa have been subjected to interventions	New
<i>Introduction status and degreeOfEstablishment</i>	Information on the stage at which an alien taxon is along the introduction-establishment-invasion continuum within South Africa is gathered and systematically interpreted along with the data (this is a specific routine within the ' <i>Adding alien taxa and enrichment data to the species list</i> ' workflow)	New
<i>Integration with the National Biodiversity Assessment (NBA)</i>	To ensure information can flow between reports. The intention is to include data translation tables linked to how data are presented in the status report to how data are presented in the NBA	Future

Workflow	Description	Status
<i>Integration with the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and the Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species (GRIIS)</i>	To ensure information can flow between the national status report and international databases. The intention is to include data translation tables linked to how data are presented in the status report to how data are presented in the GBIF and GRIIS	Future
<i>Sourcing, capturing and reporting information for the Prince Edward Islands (PEIs)</i>	Workflow to populate the indicators for the PEIs. The workflow was part of Chapter 5 of the third report (SANBI and CIB, 2023)	Not updated as not used in this report

1070

1071 Some of these workflows required specific protocols where the intention is for these to be applied
1072 outside of the report. For example, a protocol has been set up to evaluate whether a taxon is absent
1073 or present in South Africa in cases where the evidence is ambiguous (Matthys et al. 2025).

1074

1075 1. Pathways

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1079 Findings for pathways

- 1080 • There continue to be opportunities for introductions through a wide range of pathways, with
1081 no qualitative changes to these opportunities. Quantitative increases for some pathways
1082 represent a return to the levels of activity experienced prior to the COVID 19 pandemic.
- 1083 • The size and diversity of the aquarium trade, and the range of introduction opportunities it
1084 provides has been highlighted by recent research.
- 1085 • New alien species that have been illegally or accidentally introduced continue to be detected
1086 every year, with the rate of introduction remaining stable (~four new species per year).
- 1087 • Alien species have been introduced through a wide variety of pathways, but besides biological
1088 control agents, all new alien taxa that have been recorded in the last three years are likely to
1089 have been accidentally introduced, including several plant parasites, and contaminants of the
1090 aquarium trade. Intentional illegal introductions are still a concern.
- 1091 • Many pathways provide opportunities for within-country dispersal. However, the magnitude
1092 and role of most pathways is not known. For those pathways for which data were obtained,
1093 within-country activity has returned to pre-pandemic levels.
- 1094 • Alien taxa are dispersing within the country in a myriad of ways. Recent studies show within-
1095 country movement is a mix/combination of natural dispersal (e.g., self-propelled and
1096 mediated by vertebrate vectors) and human-mediated dispersal (e.g., with contaminated soil
1097 and plants, though biofouling on ships or boats, and the formal and informal plant trade).
- 1098 • As an example of these trends, South Africa plays a large role in the international pet trade,
1099 breeding animals (particularly alien birds) for export and local use. Records from social media
1100 show alien pet birds are escaping from captivity.

1101 Gaps for pathways

- 1102 • There are major gaps in our knowledge on *introduction rates*, with pathways and dates of
1103 introduction missing for many introduced taxa, particularly plants and fungi. Estimates or
1104 useful proxies of search effort are required for more reliable estimates of rate of introduction
1105 and for reporting on Target 6 of the GBF
- 1106 • Insufficient information on how taxa are moved or are moving within the country

1107

1108 For all pathway indicators, the pathway classification framework of the Convention on Biological
 1109 Diversity was used (CBD 2014). The pathways are shown in Figure 1.1 and details on the pathways,
 1110 including descriptions and definitions, are provided in Harrower et al. (2018). Specific details of values
 1111 are provided in Appendix 5 and methodological changes from previous reports and details of how the
 1112 calculations were made are outlined in the Supplementary Material (e.g., Table S1.1).

1113 **1.1. Introduction pathway prominence**

1114 *Introduction pathway prominence* assesses, based on socio-economic data, the opportunities
 1115 available for alien organisms to be introduced to South Africa from other countries. This indicator does
 1116 not consider how many introductions these opportunities have resulted in. If effective biosecurity is
 1117 in place, then a large or increasing *introduction pathway prominence* (e.g., increasing food imports) is
 1118 not a concern in terms of biological invasions.

1119 There have been no changes to *introduction pathway prominence* (Figure 1.1). There have, however,
 1120 been some noteworthy events and research:

1121 In 2023, one of the official ports of entry between Botswana and South Africa (Zanzibar), was
 1122 withdrawn (Figure 4.3). South Africa still has many official ports of entry - eight maritime ports, ten
 1123 airports and 53 land border posts – through which people, goods, and transport vessels can officially
 1124 enter the country (Figure 4.3).

1125 Aquaculture has been promoted over recent years (Van Deventer et al. 2019), and production
 1126 increased year-on-year between 2015 and 2022, however, there was a 24% decline in production
 1127 between 2022 and 2023 (Figure S1.3). This change may be temporary and thus was not considered to
 1128 be a qualitative change to the indicator (*introduction pathway prominence* remains ‘Moderate’).

1129 Between the 2022/2023 and 2024/2025 financial years, there was a ~24% increase in the number of
 1130 aircraft arriving from regional or international destinations (Figure S1.16). Similarly, there was a 39%
 1131 increase in the number of people entering South Africa between 2022 and 2023 (Figure S1.19). These

1132 recent increases represent a return to levels of activity prior to the COVID 19 pandemic and do not
1133 constitute a change in the indicator (*introduction pathway prominence* remains ‘Moderate’ for the
1134 airplane pathway, and ‘Major’ for the people and their luggage pathway).

1135 Recent research on the ornamental plant trade in southern Africa has shown that it is transboundary
1136 in nature, with South Africa acting as the leading supplier for the sub-region (Rodríguez-Cala et al.
1137 2025a). Nonetheless, the *introduction pathway prominence* for the ornamental pathway remains
1138 ‘Moderate’.

1139 The size and diversity of the aquarium trade; and its potential role in facilitating both fish introductions
1140 and invasions, and introduction and spread of fish parasites has been highlighted. A national survey
1141 of the alien ornamental fish sold at pet shops showed that at least 312 fish species belonging to 77
1142 families and 182 genera are traded (Vezi et al. 2024). Notably, the number of species in the trade is
1143 similar to that recorded in trade in large, developed regions, such as Europe, the USA, and Canada.
1144 Most of the traded fish were freshwater species (214 species, 68%), but marine species (69 species,
1145 22%), and species from transitional environments (30 species, 10%) are also sold. The trade is
1146 dominated by fish that are native to tropical regions (88%), and by small-sized, relatively cheap species
1147 [e.g., *Betta splendens* (Siamese fighting fish), *Carassius auratus* (goldfish), and *Poecilia reticulata*
1148 (guppy)]. Three alien monogenean parasites *Dactylogyrus lampam*, *Dactylogyrus tapienensis*, and
1149 *Dactylogyrus viticulus* were recorded on *Barbonymus schwanenfeldii* (tinfoil barb) imported into South
1150 Africa from Sri Lanka and Thailand as ornamental fish; with the fish imported from their native range
1151 (Thailand) having a greater number and diversity of parasites (Molokomme et al. 2023). Similarly,
1152 three of 18 species of freshwater ornamental Cichlidae imported from Indonesia, Sri Lanka, and
1153 Thailand, were found to be infected with the nematode *Capillaria pterophylli*, with a high prevalence
1154 (> 50%) in some species imported from Indonesia (Molokomme et al. 2025). This research confirmed
1155 the previous finding that the pet trade has a ‘Moderate’ *introduction pathway prominence*, and that
1156 the parasites on animals pathway has a ‘Major’ *introduction pathway prominence*.

1157

1158

1159 **Figure 1.1.** Current status of the introduction pathways and changes to the pathways that have been recorded
 1160 during 2023–2025. #: number of taxa introduced; # since Dec 2022: change to the number of taxa introduced
 1161 since December 2022 (↗ increase; → no change); IPP: introduction pathway prominence (Min: minor; Mod:
 1162 moderate; Maj: major; PNP: pathway not present; ? not known); IPP since Dec 2022: change to introduction
 1163 pathway prominence since December 2022 [↗ increase; ↘ decrease; → no change; ? not known; – not
 1164 applicable (first estimate or new pathway)].

1165 **1.2. Introduction rates**

1166 *Introduction rates* considers the number of new alien taxa that have been introduced over all time to
1167 South Africa from other countries through each of the introduction pathways.

1168 New alien species recorded in South Africa since December 2022 potentially entered the country
1169 through six introduction pathways. All were accidental introductions [nursery material contaminants,
1170 seed contaminants, as parasites of plants, as stowaways in the ballast water or on the hulls of ships,
1171 and potentially with people and their luggage (Figure 1.1)].

1172 For most pathways there was relatively little change, with most introductions being plants introduced
1173 for ornamental/horticultural purposes (25% of taxa with known pathways) or agriculture (9%),
1174 contaminants or parasites of animals or plants and their products (16%), or stowaways on ships (9% -
1175 includes terrestrial species on the ship, as well as aquatic species in ballast water or on the hull) (Figure
1176 1.1). However, directed research based on social media reports of pet bird escapes (Shivambu et al.
1177 2024a); and on historical records of bark and ambrosia beetles (Nel et al. 2025) resulted in notable
1178 increases in the number of known introductions through the pet (now 9% of taxa with known
1179 pathways), timber trade contaminants (now 3%), and packing materials (now 2%) pathways. However,
1180 these were species that had been recorded before December 2022. For example, Nel et al. (2025)
1181 represented the first report of the bark beetle *Phloeosinus armatus* in the country, but the species
1182 was first recorded from samples taken in 2019. *P. armatus* originates from the eastern Mediterranean,
1183 has been introduced to several countries around the world, and is a pest on various species of
1184 Cupressus (Nel et al. 2025). Recent work has further highlighted the role the aquarium trade is playing
1185 in introducing alien species, with two new species, the freshwater planarian *Girardia sinensis* (first
1186 recorded in 2022; Trembath et al. 2023) and the freshwater snail *Sinotaia cf. quadrata* (first recorded
1187 in 2019; Miranda et al. 2022), likely being introduced as contaminants of the aquarium trade (though
1188 the snail was potentially introduced as a food source for humans). Plant parasites continue to be
1189 introduced with imported plants, with several new concerning species having been detected since the
1190 December 2022, for example, *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *canariensis* (Fusarium wilt) and *Nalanthamala*
1191 *vermoesonii* (pink rot), which were both detected from samples taken in 2023 from ornamental palms
1192 at the V&A Waterfront in Cape Town (Balocchi et al. 2024).

1193 In terms of new regulated introductions (i.e., legal introductions), four new biological control agents
1194 have been released against invasive plants (Figure 1.1). See Figure 5.2 and Ivey et al. (2021) for details
1195 of how such introductions are regulated. Over the period 2023–2025 no other permits were granted
1196 to import any alien species that were not already legally in the country.

1197 **1.3. Within-country pathway prominence**

1198 *Within-country pathway prominence* considers the opportunities available for the movement of
1199 organisms within the country, and does not take into account how many dispersal events these
1200 opportunities result in. As in previous reports, data for within-country pathway prominence were not
1201 available for most pathways, and so the indicator could not be populated.

1202 The data that were obtained showed that there has been a return to pre-pandemic levels of activity.
1203 For example, the number of scheduled aircraft arriving at South African airports from domestic
1204 destinations increased by 10% between the 2022/2023 and 2024/2025 financial years (Figure S1.21).
1205 Similarly, the number of passengers arriving at South African airports from domestic destinations
1206 increased by 22% between the 2022/2023 and 2024/2025 financial years (Figure S1.23). In both cases
1207 these numbers are comparable to those before the pandemic (within 10%).

1208 Recent research has highlighted the role South Africa plays in breeding alien animals for the legal
1209 international pet trade and the risk that poses. Large numbers of many species (385 alien species and
1210 114 native species) are being exported from South Africa to other countries, the majority of which are
1211 bred in captivity (Shivambu et al. 2024b). The vast majority are alien birds (peaked at ~ 500 000
1212 individuals in 2021), but alien mammals (peaked at ~2500 individuals in ~2018) and reptiles (peaked
1213 at ~500 individuals in ~2022) are also exported (Shivambu et al. 2024b). Over the last two decades
1214 South Africa has built a huge aviculture operation through investment in captive facilities (Chan et al.
1215 2021), and it was estimated in 2015 that there were over 1 600 breeding facilities in the country
1216 (Martin 2018). There are, therefore, large numbers of individuals of alien species being bred in
1217 captivity, and while many are exported, some are incorporated into the local pet trade – for example
1218 local breeders are the most common supplier of small alien mammals to South African pet shops
1219 (Shivambu et al. 2022). It is, therefore, not surprising that many of the highly exported species have
1220 escaped and established populations. For example, the alien lovebird *Agapornis personatus* (yellow-
1221 collared lovebird), the second most exported species (Shivambu et al. 2024b), has established several
1222 populations (Symes et al. 2021); and native-alien populations¹⁸ of *A. roseicollis* (rosy-faced lovebird),
1223 the fifth most exported species, have been recorded (Symes et al. 2021; Nelufule et al. 2023).

1224 There have been several studies on pathways that provide opportunities for the movement of alien
1225 plants within the country:

¹⁸ alien populations of species that are native to another part of South Africa (Nelufule et al. 2022).

1226 Hedges serve a range of functions in both urban and rural homesteads (e.g., firewood provisioning,
1227 signalling ownership and constraining livestock movement, windbreak, privacy, aesthetics) in the
1228 central Eastern Cape, and alien species are often used in homestead hedges, with 65% of hedges
1229 containing alien species, 24% of which were invasive (Sifanele and Shackleton 2025). Hedges were
1230 more common in urban areas (44% of homesteads) in comparison to rural areas (26%), and urban
1231 homesteads had a higher number of alien species in their hedges.

1232 Institutions, such as universities, could be facilitating plant invasions. A study at Tshwane University
1233 of Technology recorded 94 alien plant species, including 43 that are listed in the A&IS regulations
1234 (Nelufule et al. 2024). Over half (51%) of these species were introduced for horticultural purposes,
1235 with many going on to form established populations. Almost half (46) of the recorded species were
1236 also found outside of the University grounds - indicating potential spill over or spread between the
1237 University and outside areas (Nelufule et al. 2024).

1238 **1.4. Within-country dispersal rates**

1239 *Within-country dispersal rates* considers the number of alien taxa that have dispersed within the
1240 country through the pathways of dispersal, including both taxa alien to the country, and those that
1241 have formed native-alien populations. As for previous reports, data for within-country dispersal have
1242 not been collated for taxa that are alien to the country (see Chapter 6). Work to update data on native-
1243 alien populations (see Nelufule et al. 2023) is ongoing (see Box 1.1 for details on a tool that will assist
1244 with this task). Therefore, the indicator cannot be populated. However, based on the reviewed
1245 literature, alien and native taxa are dispersing within the country through a wide range of pathways
1246 [at least 31 of the 44 pathways (70%)].

1247 In some cases, human-mediated dispersal is likely driving movement:

1248 *Dematophora necatrix*, a soilborne fungus that causes white root rot in a wide range of hosts, was
1249 recently recorded for the first time on native trees during tree health surveys in botanic gardens in
1250 Cape Town and Mbombela (Balocchi et al. 2025). While the fungus could have spread to these new
1251 locations in several ways, it most commonly spreads through contaminated soil and/or plants. Further
1252 spread into nearby natural populations of native species is a concern.

1253 The marine bryozoan *Membranipora membranacea* was recently (2024) recorded for the first time in
1254 the country on Muizenberg beach, but was likely introduced to Table Bay Harbour, with its subsequent
1255 spread, against the prevailing currents, likely aided by vessels (Steyn and Robinson 2025).

1256 The role vertebrates play in dispersing seeds of alien plants has been highlighted in several studies:

1257 Troops of baboons in Hogsback forage more frequently in human-modified than natural habitats, and
1258 it is estimated that they transport seeds > 5 km during daily foraging events, with an estimated ~ 450
1259 000 seeds, including those of alien species [e.g., *Acacia mearnsii* (black wattle), *Cotoneaster pannosus*
1260 (silver leaf cotoneaster), *Pinus patula* (patula pine), *Rubus cuneifolius* (American bramble), and
1261 *Solanum mauritianum* (bugweed)] being dispersed over seven months (Pamla et al. 2024). The
1262 baboon movement patterns suggest that alien plant seeds are being dispersed into the natural forest
1263 (Pamla et al. 2024).

1264 Observations and video footage from the montane grasslands of South Africa has revealed that in
1265 these areas various animals serve as seed dispersers for *C. pannosus* (Moloi et al. 2024). Mammals
1266 which can have gut retention times that range from hours to weeks, may serve as long-distance
1267 dispersal vectors of *C. pannosus*, while birds likely serve as short-distance dispersal vectors - the
1268 maximum gut retention time for birds that eat the fruits was ~15 minutes [e.g., *Onychognathus morio*
1269 (red-winged starling)] (Moloi et al. 2024).

1270 Another study in the grassland similarly showed that various vertebrates likely serve as dispersal
1271 vectors, with 100 000 seeds found in 11 295 faecal samples associated with 43 vertebrate species
1272 (Vukeya et al. 2025). Invaded sites had significantly higher seed rain than non-invaded sites, with the
1273 seeds found in the faecal samples from invaded sites being predominantly of alien species (Vukeya et
1274 al. 2025). At these sites birds were predicted to disperse seeds of *Pyracantha angustifolia* (yellow
1275 firethorn) and *Opuntia engelmannii* (small round-leaved prickly pear) more than 15 km, while
1276 mammals were predicted to disperse the seeds a maximum of 8.6 km, however, the study highlighted
1277 that both the quality and quantity of dispersal events needs to be considered, as while ingested *P.*
1278 *angustifolia* seeds were viable (47% viability), *Opuntia engelmannii* seeds were rarely (5.4% viability)
1279 (Vukeya et al. 2025).

1280 Many alien species are moving within the country through a mix of natural and human-mediated
1281 dispersal:

1282 The marine bryozoan *Amathia verticillata* (spaghetti bryozoan), was likely introduced to Saldanha Bay
1283 via biofouling and then spread via fragmentation, to where it was first recorded on a jetty in the
1284 Langebaan Lagoon Marine Protected Area within the West Coast National Park (Ackland et al. 2025).

1285 Invasive plant richness recorded from two powerline servitudes in Limpopo was greatest closer to
1286 human settlements, with the servitudes possibly acting to either facilitate the spread or establishment
1287 of invasive species (Dalu et al. 2023).

1288 A study of trees on the sidewalks and in the front gardens of houses in the town Prince Albert showed
1289 that gardeners showed a preference for planting alien species (65% of planted species were aliens,
1290 and 63% of planted individuals were aliens) (Milton and Dean 2025). However, most trees were not
1291 planted but were self-seeded, with more frequently planted species more likely to self-seed. However,
1292 seedling distribution for fleshy fruited trees was also partly explained by bird dispersal.

1293 Long-distance, within-country dispersal events aided by humans (e.g., as a contaminant on
1294 transported nursery plants, and as a stowaway on boats), as well as short-distance natural dispersal
1295 events likely facilitated the rapid spread and high connectivity of *Harmonia axyridis* (the Harlequin
1296 ladybird) populations, which shows little genetic structure across the country (Collop et al. 2024).

1297 Although *Ligustrum* species (privets) are not common in the formal plant trade, they may be informally
1298 traded and are commonly found in gardens, which serve as sources of propagules that are being
1299 dispersed by water bodies (e.g., rivers) and animals (Shepard et al. 2025).

1300 Similarly, alongside established populations of *Cortaderia* species (pampass grass), cultivated
1301 populations, and formally and informally traded inflorescence are likely contributing to the spread of
1302 the two *Cortaderia* species (*C. selloana* and *C. jubata*) in the country (Mbele et al. 2025). Until recently,
1303 only sterile cultivars of *Cortaderia* were permitted to be sold in nurseries, yet seeds from cultivated
1304 populations and formally traded inflorescence had germination rates of 69% and 15%, respectively
1305 (Mbele et al. 2025). Seeds from informally traded inflorescence, which were likely collected from
1306 established populations (germination rate of 70%), had germination rates of 32% (Mbele et al. 2025).

1307 **1.5.High-level indicator: 1. *Rate of unregulated introduction of new species***

1308 The high-level indicator *rate of unregulated introduction of new species* estimates the total number of
1309 new alien taxa introduced accidentally or illegally each year.

1310 Over the last decade (2016-2025), 40 new alien species, that were either illegally or accidentally
1311 introduced (i.e., unregulated introductions), have been recorded—an average of four new alien
1312 species per year (Figure 1.2). Although this is slightly less than the number recorded between 2013-
1313 2022 (43 new alien species – an average of 4.3 per year), this number is likely an underestimate and
1314 will increase due to delays in reporting (Figure 1.2).

1315

1316 **Figure 1.2.** Number of new alien taxa recorded in South Africa over time: A, over the last eight decades; B, during
 1317 the last decade. These are alien taxa not previously found or known to be present. The low number of recent
 1318 unregulated introductions (shaded in grey) likely reflects delays in detecting and reporting alien taxa. Based on
 1319 experiences from the past three reporting cycles, the number of recent unregulated introductions are likely
 1320 severely under-reported, and the number reported will increase as new data become available (cf. Table S1.5).
 1321 These data provide the basis for scoring *Rate of unregulated introduction of new species* and part of reporting
 1322 on Target 6 of the GBF.

1323 **1.6. Trends in pathways since 2014**

1324 [work in progress]

1325 **Box 1.1 A simple, global scheme for classifying the movement of organisms in the Anthropocene**

1326 To achieve target 6 of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) and reduce
 1327 introductions, biosecurity and surveillance to manage pathways of introduction and within-country
 1328 dispersal need to be implemented (IPBES 2023). However, we have limited understanding of how alien
 1329 species are moving around the country (cf. Sections 1.3, 1.4) and thus such actions within the country
 1330 cannot be directed to where they are needed most. Although the introduction pathway classification
 1331 framework of the CBD (CBD 2014) has guided the monitoring and reporting of introduction pathways
 1332 (see Figure 1.1), the relevance of the framework for within-country dispersal is limited as it focuses on
 1333 introductions across political or biogeographical boundaries, and does not adequately capture natural
 1334 dispersal (Faulkner et al. 2020). To address this, a simple, global, policy-relevant scheme for classifying
 1335 the movement of organisms in the Anthropocene was proposed (Faulkner et al. 2024). The scheme
 1336 extends the introduction pathway framework, and classifies dispersal into ten categories associated
 1337 with active dispersal by humans, human-mediated natural dispersal, and natural dispersal. It is largely
 1338 interoperable with the introduction pathway framework, but splits natural dispersal into several
 1339 categories (Box Figure 1.1). Each category is linked to high-level management actions (including
 1340 potential biosecurity interventions) and responsible parties. Consequently, the scheme will assist with
 1341 the monitoring, reporting, and strategic management of alien species movements irrespective of
 1342 whether the focus is on introductions into or within political or biogeographical boundaries

1343
 1344 **Box Figure 1.1** The scheme for classifying dispersal in the Anthropocene (A) expands the widely used
 1345 introduction pathway classification framework (B), so that it addresses all types of dispersal that might need
 1346 management or regulation (specifically, the introduction of alien species to a region, the movement of alien
 1347 species within a region, and the movement of native species within a region).

1348 **Box 1.2 One Health and One Biosecurity**

1349 Animal, environmental, human, and plant health are interconnected, and, in many cases, attempts to
1350 manage one aspect without considering the other aspects are ineffective. To address this, the concept
1351 of One Health has been developed as a partnership between the Food and Agriculture Organization
1352 of the United Nations (FAO), United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the World Health
1353 Organization (WHO), and the World Organisation for Animal Health (FAO, UNEP, WHO, and WOA, H,
1354 2022). However, despite the 1st World One Health Congress taking place in 2011, the environment is
1355 still poorly represented, and there are very few studies that explicitly link the concept of One Health
1356 to the concept of biosecurity (Hulme 2025). Hulme (2020), recognising that addressing biological
1357 invasions is cross-cutting and measures to address them require integrated governance (IPBES 2023),
1358 defined the concept of One Biosecurity as an *“an interdisciplinary approach to biosecurity policy and
1359 research that builds on the interconnections between human, animal, plant, and ecosystem health to
1360 effectively prevent and mitigate the impacts of invasive alien species”*. Environmental agencies work
1361 to prevent the introduction of alien taxa that pose a threat to nature; agricultural agencies work to
1362 prevent the introduction of agricultural pests; and health agencies work to prevent the introduction
1363 of pathogens and their vectors (including emerging infectious diseases). There is a need for such
1364 efforts to be integrated as many of the methods, approaches, and goals are the same (Ogden et al.
1365 2019; Box Figure 1.2). The integration of biological invasions into One Health thinking in South Africa
1366 is still very much in its infancy, though opportunities exist with the development of the national
1367 strategy on biological invasions, via structures like the Border Management Authority, and through
1368 more collaboration with neighbouring countries on shared threats. Better integration will be
1369 complicated but is essential if interventions are to be effective.

1370

1371 **Box Figure 1.2.** Activities to address biological invasions that would benefit from a One Biosecurity approach.
 1372 There is an opportunity in South Africa (and southern Africa and Africa more generally) to map this onto
 1373 current strategies and action plans to identify areas where synergies are possible. Reproduced from Figure 5,
 1374 Hulme et al. (2025).

1375 2. Species

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1377 Contributing authors: tbc

1378 **Findings for Species**

- 1379 • The number and status of alien species in South Africa was recently updated. The list now
1380 includes over 6000 taxa, of which over 3500 are present outside of captivity or cultivation and
1381 719 taxa are invasive.
- 1382 • Only a few alien species are widespread, the majority are still localised and found in low
1383 numbers. However, the recorded extent of most species has markedly increased and will
1384 continue to increase unless effective control is put in place. In particular, data on the
1385 abundance of selected invasive plant taxa in water catchments and terrestrial biomes from
1386 the National Invasive Alien Plant Survey (2008–2023) indicate most taxa have increased in
1387 cover despite mechanical and chemical control efforts, but there were decreases in cover for
1388 taxa under biological control.
- 1389 • Recent national impact assessments (conducted in line with the IUCN’s EICAT framework)
1390 have found several species to cause ‘Major’ or ‘Massive’ impacts. Complementary
1391 assessments using risk analyses and findings from the IPBES IAS Assessment confirm that
1392 these species cause widespread harm across multiple sectors of society.

1393 **Gaps for Species**

- 1394 • Data on the distribution and abundance of alien species need to be collected, collated, and
1395 integrated into national and global databases to facilitate the planning of interventions.
- 1396 • Impact assessments have been conducted for only a few alien taxa in South Africa. The
1397 systematic quantification of the impacts of biological invasions and the collation of such
1398 information in formal impact assessments would: facilitate the prioritisation of interventions
1399 targeting particular species and particular sites; provide the justification for government
1400 investment to control biological invasions; and provide important background to
1401 communicate the issue to society.

1402

Invasion-specific outcomes

2. Number of invasive species that have 'Major' impacts

2.1. Number and status of alien species

2.2. Extent of alien species

2.3. Abundance of alien species

2.4. Impact of alien species

1403

1404 **2.1. Number and status of alien species**

1405 The list of alien taxa for South Africa was updated in 2025 (Appendix 6; Zengeya et al. in press) and
1406 now includes over 6000 taxa, of which there is evidence that 3825 taxa are present, the presence of
1407 1642 taxa is doubtful¹⁹ and 714 taxa are recorded as absent²⁰ (Table 2.1, Section S2.1). Over half of
1408 the taxa that are present are plants, confirming the assertion that South Africa is a hotspot for plant
1409 invasions. Doubtful taxa were mostly plants (presumed to be in cultivation, but there are no recent
1410 records). Only about a third of taxa have been assessed for their introduction and establishment status
1411 in South Africa as of December 2022, 719 of those taxa are invasive, 120 taxa are known to be
1412 established but not invasive, and 329 taxa are present but not established (Figure 2.1).

1413 **Table 2.1.** The number and occurrence status of alien taxa in South Africa as of September 2025. For more
1414 details, including taxa assessed, scored as absent, and their regulatory status, see Table S2.1 and Appendix 6.

Taxa	Doubtful	Confirmed as present
Animals	343	1387
Bacteria	0	4
Chromista	0	13
Fungi	6	105
Plants	1293	2315
Protozoa	0	1
Total	1642	3825

¹⁹ Taxa were assessed as doubtful if there is some evidence of the taxa having been present in South Africa, but there is doubt over the evidence or whether it is still present as of December 2025, including taxonomic or geographic imprecision in the records. A protocol to classify presence in cases where there is uncertainty has been developed, and will be implemented more in future (Matthys et al. 2026)

²⁰ Taxa that were assessed as absent were either biocontrol agents that were released to control invasive plants but that did not establish, taxa listed as prohibited in at least one version of NEM:BA A&IS Lists, and or taxa included in previous status reports but there is no evidence that they are present

1415 **Figure 2.1.** The introduction and establishment status of alien species in South Africa as of December 2022 as
 1416 per the Unified Framework for Biological Invasions (Blackburn et al. 2011). Absent (A0–A1)—taxa that have
 1417 never been introduced beyond the limits of their native range to [a part of] South Africa (A0) or were introduced
 1418 but no longer present (A1); Present (not established) (B1–C2)—includes a range of taxa from those in quarantine
 1419 to those that are reproducing outside of captivity or cultivation but where there is no clear evidence of having
 1420 formed self-sustaining populations; Established (C3–D1)—taxa where there is establishment, and possibly
 1421 spread, but there is no clear evidence of forming self-sustaining populations at a significant distance from point
 1422 of introduction; and Invasive (D2–E)—taxa with populations that are self-sustaining at a significant distance from
 1423 the point of introduction. Selected species that are not present in South Africa (A0 and A1) are included in the
 1424 list and report for various specific reasons, e.g., they were included on the prohibited lists of versions of the A&IS
 1425 Regulations (cf. Section S2.1).
 1426

1427

1428 The process to create and curate the list of alien taxa in South Africa has improved over time and was
 1429 recently reviewed by Zengeya et al. (2025). Key developments include improvements in how data
 1430 were presented, how changes were tracked, and the degree to which the information was consistent
 1431 with international best practice. The development of documented and repeatable workflows ensured
 1432 clarity on why a species was included on the list and facilitated reviews and updates. The perspective
 1433 has also provided recommendations for those developing national lists of alien species (See Table S2.3
 1434 for how these have been addressed in this report; and Box 2.1 for related recent papers). National
 1435 lists of alien species are never complete or perfect. Lists are dynamic and need constant updating as
 1436 new alien species are discovered, populations die out or are extirpated, and as new information
 1437 becomes available. Therefore, this list, like all lists of alien taxa, represents a snapshot of the situation.
 1438 The presence of many alien taxa needs to be confirmed and documented; many data sources still need
 1439 to be incorporated into the list; and it is likely that many alien taxa have not, as yet, been recorded
 1440 (see Section S2.1 for further details on progress made to update the list).

1441 As examples, recent discoveries of alien marine taxa (Ackland et al. 2025; Steyn and Robinson 2025),
1442 many alien taxa in captivity or cultivation (Glen 2002, Hoy et al. 2021), medicinal plant trade (e.g.,
1443 Williams et al. 2021; Williams et al. 2022), aquarium trade (e.g., Vezi et al. 2024) still need to be added.
1444 Similarly, many groups and habitats have been under-sampled. For example, information on most
1445 microorganisms is either not incorporated, is hard to incorporate as issues of nativity are unresolved,
1446 or there simply has been no sampling (e.g., few ecto-mycorrhizal fungi have been incorporated to
1447 date, despite their large conspicuous fruiting bodies; see examples in Goldman and Gryzenhout,
1448 2019). Thus, the list provides an underestimate of the number of alien taxa in the country, and this
1449 number will increase as new and historical data sources are verified and incorporated, and as new
1450 alien taxa are recorded and reported. These limitations mean that the list is not yet a complete
1451 baseline of the knowledge of which alien taxa are present in South Africa. As such, differences
1452 between this list and the lists from previous reports (e.g., addition or removal of a taxon) need to be
1453 carefully interrogated, as they do not necessarily mean that there has been a true change (sensu
1454 Zengeya et al. 2025).

1455 **2.2. Extent of alien species**

1456 **2.2.1. Number of broad-scale regions occupied per species**

1457 Occurrence data were updated based on data published by the Global Biodiversity Information Facility
1458 (GBIF; data accessed [11 September 2025]) for 3072 taxa. Similar to previous reports, many taxa are
1459 localised invaders, but a few taxa are widespread (Figures 2.2, 2.3). The process of mobilising and
1460 analysing spatial data has been improved by adopting practices from other initiatives on compiling
1461 lists such as the Biodiversity Building Blocks for Policy (B-Cubed) project (Groom et al. 2025, [https://b-
1462 cubed.eu/](https://b-cubed.eu/)). The B-Cubed project has developed pipelines to improve integration of biodiversity data
1463 into data cubes that can be used for models and indicators of biodiversity monitoring. These data
1464 cubes and workflows have assisted with the automation and standardisation of the process and how
1465 the status reports are communicated (see Box 2.2).

1466
 1467 **Figure 2.2.** The extent of alien taxa at the provincial scale as of September 2025. This is based on occurrence
 1468 records from Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and Southern African Plant Invaders Atlas (SAPIA)
 1469 for mainland South Africa.

1470 **2.2.2. Number of quarter degree grid cells (QDGCs) occupied per species**

1471 Most alien taxa have relatively restricted distributions (fungi and mammals), but some taxa are
 1472 widespread [e.g., birds and plants occupy more than 500 out of about 2000 quarter degree grid cells
 1473 (QDGCs) covering South Africa; Figure 2.3]. Many taxa showed an increase in extent since 2022 (Figure
 1474 2.4; and Table S2.4 for details of those plant taxa that have shown the greatest increases in recorded
 1475 ranges). As noted in previous reports, the integration of GBIF with widely used citizen science
 1476 platforms such as iNaturalist has improved the reporting of occurrence data for alien taxa. For
 1477 example, iNaturalist contributed over 90% of the GBIF occurrence records of alien fungi taxa in South
 1478 Africa (Fig. 2.3).

1479

1480

Figure 2.3. The distribution of alien taxa in quarter degree grid cells (QDGCs) in South Africa.

1481

1482

1483 **Figure 2.4.** The extent of alien taxa in South Africa (December 2022 vs September 2025). The values shown are
 1484 the number of quarter degree grid cells (QDGCs) where taxa have been historically recorded. The possibility that
 1485 taxa are no longer present in a QDGC is not assessed, as such, taxa cannot have a decreased extent. Data are
 1486 from Southern African Plant Invaders Atlas (SAPIA) (accessed 17 March 2020) and Global Biodiversity
 1487 Information Facility (GBIF) [accessed 11 September 2025].

1488

1489 **2.3. Abundance of alien species**

1490 In previous reports, estimates of the abundance of alien species were based on two sources of data
 1491 on terrestrial plants – a 1998 report to the Water Research Commission (Versfeld et al. 1998) and the
 1492 National Invasive Alien Plant Survey (Kotzé et al. 2010). This situation has not changed. There have
 1493 been some recent developments, for example, a recent analysis of the National Invasive Alien Plant
 1494 Survey has shown that the level of invasions is increasing in important water catchments, and in most
 1495 terrestrial biomes in South Africa (Kotzé et al. 2025). The study was initiated in 2007 and included 14
 1496 dominant invasive plant taxa. The survey was completed in 2008 and repeated between 2016 and
 1497 2023. Plants on average increased in extent by 10.6% between the two surveys leading to an estimated
 1498 1.6% of the country being invaded by the end of the second survey (i.e., 2023). Trees in the genera
 1499 *Acacia*, *Eucalyptus*, *Pinus*, and *Neltuma* (formerly *Prosopis*) accounted for almost three quarters
 1500 (72.4%) of the cover (Table 2.2). Most of the taxa increased in cover between the two surveys, and
 1501 decreases in cover were only recorded at a national scale for taxa that had been subjected to biological

1502 control, while taxa that did not have biological control all continued to increase in cover despite
 1503 mechanical and chemical control efforts. The highest declines in cover were in the Cactaceae species
 1504 (–29%), followed by *Acacia saligna* (–18%) and *Hakea* species (–16%). Selected wattle species (*Acacia*
 1505 species), *Eucalyptus*, and *Neltuma* species increased by 22, 18, and 10% respectively between the two
 1506 surveys. Another study using remote sensing in selected river catchments (Luvuhu, Sabie-Crocodile,
 1507 Tugela, and uMzimvubu) found that about 10% of the catchment areas were covered in alien trees
 1508 either in the form of plantation forestry or invasive stands (Rebelo et al. 2025).

1509 **Table 2.2.** Changes in the extent of invasion (condensed ha) by 14 alien plant taxa at a national scale in South
 1510 Africa from two successive surveys done in 2008 and 2023 respectively. A condensed hectare (mean % cover ×
 1511 area occupied) is the equivalent area occupied at a canopy cover of 100% (i.e., 50% cover on 10 ha = 5 condensed
 1512 ha).

Taxa	First survey (2008)	Second survey (2023)	% Change
<i>Acacia cyclops</i>	65421	64422	-1,5
<i>Acacia saligna</i>	54535	44454	-18,5
<i>Acacia</i> species	503278	527904	4,9
<i>Arundo donax</i>	10124	10958	8,2
Cactaceae	59121	42050	-28,9
<i>Chromolaena odorata</i>	74833	77133	3,1
<i>Eucalyptus</i> species	243407	285569	17,3
<i>Hakea</i> species	22047	18601	-15,6
<i>Lantana camara</i>	37593	39818	5,9
<i>Melia azederach</i>	27101	28450	5,0
<i>Neltuma</i> (= <i>Prosopis</i>) species	94552	106772	12,9
<i>Pinus</i> species	96847	98974	2,2
<i>Populus</i> species	43598	45401	4,1
<i>Solanum mauritianum</i>	43221	47466	9,8

1513

1514 **2.4. Impact of alien species**

1515 Previous reports have highlighted that biological invasion are a major threat to South Africa’s
 1516 biodiversity, economy, and sustainable development. However, they have also highlighted that there
 1517 are few studies that formally document impacts (see Section S2.5; van Wilgen et al. 2022a; Zengeya
 1518 and Wilson 2023). This situation has not changed. National-level EICAT assessments have been
 1519 completed for 36 species (Table 2.2), three taxa were recorded as having had ‘Moderate’ impacts, 18
 1520 ‘Major’ impacts, and *Oreochromis niloticus* has had a ‘Massive’ impact. The seemingly high proportion
 1521 of taxa with harmful impacts is, however, an artefact as taxa known to cause impact were prioritised
 1522 for assessment. As efforts to collate information on the impacts of alien species using standardised
 1523 protocols increase, a more complete picture will emerge. Few national-level SEICAT assessments have
 1524 been done in South Africa (see Section S2.5). [to be updated to reflect studies done as of December
 1525 2025]

1526 Up to December 2025, 170 taxa had risk analyses completed using the Risk Analysis Framework for
 1527 Alien Taxa (RAAT) framework, including 148 of the 560 taxa listed under the A&IS Regulations (Table
 1528 S4.1). The RAAT framework evaluates environmental and non-environmental impacts of alien species
 1529 using methods that are similar to EICAT and SEICAT assessments. However, while the risk analyses
 1530 provide indications of potential impacts, they are not as comprehensive as a full EICAT and SEICAT
 1531 assessments and are regarded with low confidence. 48 of these taxa had environmental impacts that
 1532 have been recorded in South Africa, of which 30 taxa were estimated to have ‘Minimal Concern’.
 1533 ‘Minor’ or ‘Moderate’ impacts, 15 ‘Major’ and three taxa (*Acacia cyclops*, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*,
 1534 *Oreochromis niloticus*) have ‘Massive’ impacts. Several native plant taxa have been displaced or
 1535 become locally extinct as result of competition from *Acacia cyclops* (e.g., Le Maitre et al. 2011) and *A.*
 1536 *cyclops* has caused chemical, physical, and structural changes to ecosystems that have resulted in the
 1537 local extinction of at least one native taxon (Milton 1981; Milton and Siegfried 1981; van Wilgen and
 1538 Richardson 1985). *Mytilus galloprovincialis* has outcompeted and displaced native benthic
 1539 communities in intertidal zones (Sadchatheeswaran et al. 2015, 2018), *Oreochromis niloticus*
 1540 hybridises and supplants native *Oreochromis* species (D’Amato et al. 2007; Firmat et al. 2013).

1541 35 species that had completed risk analyses had socio-economic impacts recorded in South Africa. 28
 1542 of these taxa were estimated to have ‘Minimal to Moderate’ impacts, and seven taxa (*Bemisia tabaci*,
 1543 *Cenchrus setaceum*, *Cinara cupressi*, *Nerium oleander*, *Pathenium lysterophorus*, *Psittacula krameria*)
 1544 have ‘Major’ impacts. For example, fountain grass *Cenchrus setaceum* causes damage to infrastructure
 1545 such as roads, railways and waterways (Milton et al. 1998, Rahlao et al. 2010) and the Rose-ringed
 1546 parakeet *Psittacula krameria* is considered a serious agricultural pest (Hart and Downs 2014).

1547 **Table 2.2.** The number of taxa that have impact assessments for South Africa in terms of the Environmental
 1548 Impact Classification for Alien Taxa (EICAT) as of September 2023 (see Table S2.5 for more details). Only four
 1549 taxa (all trees and shrubs), have impact assessments for South Africa in terms of the Socio-Economic
 1550 Classification of Alien Taxa Scheme (SEICAT). [Note: to be updated to studies done as of December 2025]

Group	Data Deficient	Minimal Concern	Minor	Moderate	Major	Massive	Total
Grasses, annuals, and vines	7	0	2	2	2	0	13
Trees and shrubs	0	1	0	1	11	0	13
Freshwater fishes	0	0	0	0	4	1	5
Freshwater invertebrates	4	0	0	0	0	0	4
Terrestrial invertebrates	0	0	0	0	1	0	2
Total	11	1	2	3	18	1	36

1551
 1552 83 taxa had environmental impacts that have been recorded in global introduction range but not in
 1553 South Africa. 62 of these taxa were estimated to have ‘Minimal Concern’. ‘Minor’ or ‘Moderate’
 1554 impacts, 19 ‘Major’ and two (*Rattus rattus*, *Robina pseudoacacia*) have ‘Massive’ impacts. Eighty-five

1555 taxa had socio-economic impacts that have been recorded in their global introduction range but not
1556 in South Africa. Seventy-seven of these taxa were estimated to have ‘Minimal Concern’. ‘Minor’ or
1557 ‘Moderate’ impacts and seven had ‘Major’ impacts. Two taxa had ‘Massive’ impacts—*Vespula*
1558 *germanica* (the German wasp) that impacts human health (Kerr and Sharp 2008) and *Chondrilla juncea*
1559 (skeleton weed) that is known to affect crop production (Panetta and Dodd 1987).

1560 Biological invasions were also highlighted as a major global threat to biodiversity and sustainable
1561 development by the IPBES IAS Assessment (IPBES 2023). A dataset, Global Impacts Dataset of Invasive
1562 Alien Species (GIDIAS), was created to document the positive, negative, and neutral impacts of
1563 invasive species on nature, nature’s contributions to people, and good quality of life (Bacher et al.
1564 2023). The GIDIAS dataset has records of impacts assessments for 102 invasive species on nature for
1565 South Africa. 45 of these taxa have either led to decreased performance of individuals of native species
1566 and or reduced population sizes of native species, while one taxon (*Micropterus dolomieu*) has led to
1567 the local or global extinction of native species (Woodford et al. 2005). Only a few taxa have impact
1568 assessments for South Africa in terms of nature’s contributions to people (8 taxa) and good quality of
1569 life (4 taxa) (See Table S2.6 for more details).

1570 A few studies have been done on the impact of alien species in the past three years (since 2022). [to
1571 be updated]

1572 **2.5. High level indicator: 2. Number of species that have ‘Major’ impacts**

1573 Impact assessments for South Africa (based on the IUCN’s EICAT framework) have found that 19
1574 species have caused ‘Major’ or ‘Massive’ impacts. Complementary assessments using risk analyses
1575 and findings from the IPBES IAS Assessment confirm that these species cause widespread harm across
1576 multiple sectors of society. However, as only few taxa have been formally assessed, the need for more
1577 studies and assessments on the impact of invasive species has been highlighted as a research priority
1578 for South Africa (Chapter 6).

1579 The number of invasives that have ‘Major’ impacts will increase as more impact assessments are
1580 conducted. The formal assessment of the impact of alien species provides the rationale for regulation
1581 and management, can improve compliance and implementation of intervention measures, and assist
1582 to resolve conflicts. However, impact assessments are hampered by a lack of reliable data for most
1583 species. If this situation persists, regulations will continue to be vulnerable to legal challenges.

1584 **2.6. Trends in number and status of species since 2014**

1585 [Note: to be completed in the final report]

1586 **Box 2.1 Lists of alien taxa in the Global South—three joint journal special issues**

1587 Lists of alien taxa are essential for linking evidence to action (Wilson et al. in review). However, the
 1588 recent IPBES IAS Assessment identified significant gaps in the completeness and availability of lists of
 1589 alien taxa in the Global South (IPBES 2023). To address this, and as part of the need to develop
 1590 processes for the lists of taxa in South Africa, three joint special issues were developed and published
 1591 early in 2026. The special issues were based on data collected from over 40 countries and consist of
 1592 11 papers in African Biodiversity & Conservation www.abcijournal.org (addressing African issues), 6
 1593 papers in Bioinvasiones <http://bioinvasiones.org/> (addressing issues in Latin America and the
 1594 Caribbean), and 12 papers in NeoBiota https://neobiota.pensoft.net/topical_collection/270/
 1595 (addressing issue of broader interest or from other regions). The papers compare lists of invasive taxa
 1596 from different countries; present lists for particular countries, types of taxa, and environments
 1597 (including social wasps, horticulture, marine ecosystems, and protected areas); and develop
 1598 workflows and protocols to assist with the creation of lists (e.g., guidance as to how to incorporate
 1599 information from citizen science and molecular databases, and to address uncertainties). Those
 1600 relevant to South Africa are listed in Box Table 2.1.

1601 **Box Table 2.1** Papers published in the special issues ‘Developing lists of alien taxa in the Global South’ that
 1602 address invasions in South Africa, a further four papers look at invasions in continental southern Africa. For the
 1603 full list of paper published see
 1604 https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1XwqEoKNNKarwmUVrhL6R6fftPmNlf_P42vmi71BR7Y/.

Reference	Title	How it was or will be used in the report
Faulkner (in press)	An automated workflow to standardise taxon names for South African alien species lists	The workflow was used to standardise names for South Africa’s list of alien taxa (cf. Appendices 2 and 6).
Fernández Winzer et al. (2025a)	From detection to action—a proposed workflow to ensure first reports of alien species from molecular analyses are acted upon	The workflow identified several taxa that were thought to be absent from South Africa, but appear to be present. The intention is for the workflow to be incorporated into the workflow: <i>Tracking data sources and adding data as published</i>
Gildenhuys et al. (2025)	Deriving inventories of non-native plant species from iNaturalist: Insights from urban centres of the Western Cape, South Africa	The workflow provides a method to develop inventories of alien plants from urban centres; it will in future reports be used to assist with estimating ‘3.1 Alien species richness’
Matthys et al. (2025)	Argument maps can support decisions to declare the presence of alien species: South Africa as a case study	The intention is to incorporate argument maps into the workflow ‘ <i>Introduction status and degreeOfEstablishment</i> ’ to address cases where presence in South Africa is uncertain (specifically the fields <i>occurrenceStatus</i> and <i>occurrenceStatusConfidence</i>).
Nelufule et al. (in press)	The role of citizen scientists in managing invasive alien plant species and aiding early detection in Kloofendal nature reserve, Johannesburg, South Africa	An example of how citizen science groups can be used to compile lists of alien species of alien plants (cf. Chapter 5); and how these lists can be used to support appropriate management interventions (cf. Chapter 4)

Reference	Title	How it was or will be used in the report
Nelufule et al. (in press)	A comprehensive checklist of alien and invasive plant species within protected areas of the City of Johannesburg, Gauteng province, South Africa	Provides data to assist with estimating '3.1 <i>Alien species richness</i> ', and baselines with which to monitor spread.
Nxele (in press)	Bridging Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Western ecological science approaches through language: the role of language in ecosystem restoration and invasive alien species management	Provides an example of methods to encourage community-based management of invasions (cf. Chapter 5).
Potgieter et al. (2025)	An evidence-based protocol for developing lists for tree planting	An example of a tool to produce a 'safe' list (i.e., what can be planted rather than what is prohibited from being planted) (cf. Section 6.7 for a discussion on potential to address invasions through non-regulatory means).
van Wilgen et al. (2026)	Streamlining alien species listing processes to enable prioritisation and reporting in protected areas: The case of alien plants in South African National Parks	Outlines the processes used by South African National Parks to compile lists of alien taxa, with recommendations for future lists. The data assist with estimating '3.1 <i>Alien species richness</i> ', and other species and site indicators.
Zengeya et al. (2025)	Lessons and challenges in creating alien species lists: insights from South Africa's national reports on the status and management of biological invasions	Outlines how South Africa's lists of alien taxa were developed and have changed over time (cf. Sections 2.1, Table S2.3)
Zengeya et al. (in press)	A list of alien taxa for South Africa	A summary of the list and metadata for South Africa's list of alien taxa (cf. Appendices 6–8).

1605

1606

1607 **Box 2.2 The B-Cubed Project**

1608 The Biodiversity Building Blocks for Policy project (B-Cubed) (Groom et al. 2025; <https://b-cubed.eu/>)
1609 is a multi-partner, collaborative project funded through the European Research Executive Agency and
1610 coordinated by the Meise Botanic Garden, Belgium. The overarching objective of the B-Cubed project
1611 is to develop pipelines to improve the integration of biodiversity data into data cubes that are then
1612 used as the basis for models and indicators to monitor biodiversity status and change. The simplest
1613 data cube is species occurrence data over time (species × site × time) with uncertainty estimates for
1614 each dimension (Groom et al. 2025). However, the data cube approach can be extended to use
1615 different types of data (e.g., on impacts of alien species). By automating analyses, the approach
1616 provides a mechanism for turning information into a regularly updated dashboard.

1617 SANBI and Stellenbosch University (through the Centre for Invasion Biology) are two of the 12 partner
1618 organisations in the project. This report, i.e., ‘The Status of Biological Invasions and their Management
1619 in South Africa’, is a ‘use case’ for B-Cubed products. The data cubes, models, and indicators developed
1620 under the B-Cubed project provide information on five indicators used in the status report: changes
1621 in the ‘2.1 number and status of alien species’, ‘2.2 extent of alien species’ and ‘3.1 alien species
1622 richness’ were tracked over time at various scales (e.g., Figures 2.1–2.3 and 3.1); and the potential for
1623 mapping ‘2.4 impact of alien species’ and ‘3.3 impact of invasions’ has been assessed [cf. Boulesnane-
1624 Guengant et al. (2025) for an example of the approach for alien *Acacia* species in South Africa]. This
1625 information thus helps address three of the six identified key gaps in previous reports (alignment of
1626 indicators, mobilisation of spatial data, and mobilisation of impact data) (Zengeya and Wilson 2023).

1627 *Alignment of indicators* Standards for developing national level indicators to monitor biological
1628 invasions and their application are often lacking, and this impedes our ability to estimate progress
1629 made towards meeting global biodiversity targets (Section 0.2.2; McGeoch et al. 2023). B-Cubed has
1630 developed workflows to calculate indicators used to monitor biological invasions in a standardised
1631 way. Moreover, the B-Cubed project is assessing the types and quality of data required to inform the
1632 indicators; the processes used to collect, aggregate, and harmonise data; and workflows and
1633 processes used to calculate indicators and to report on trends. This work has facilitated the exchange
1634 of practical experiences on the processes used to inform the indicators and reporting, including
1635 indicator alignment, data availability, and gaps.

1636 *Mobilisation of spatial and impact data* B-Cubed has used the species occurrence cube format for a
1637 range of analyses to monitor biodiversity status and change. It is documenting the workflows and
1638 scripts that are used to generate the cubes, ensuring that they are interoperable with other data

1639 cubes, particularly those that include environmental variables. The B-Cubed process to create the
1640 species occurrence cubes has been integrated with processes of the Global Biodiversity Information
1641 Facility (GBIF) and the species occurrence cubes can be downloaded based on GBIF-mediated data.
1642 Moreover, the process is designed to follow the FAIR data principles. For instance, downloaded data
1643 are assigned metadata and a unique digital object identifier to enable FAIR citation; adaptable
1644 workflows are easy to use and fully annotated; standardised biodiversity indicators are presented to
1645 track and understand biodiversity status and trends; and all products are freely accessible through
1646 project's website.

1647

1648 **Box Figure 2.2.** The Biodiversity Building Blocks for Policy project (B-Cubed) kick-off meeting in Brussels,
1649 Belgium, March 2023 (<https://b-cubed.eu>)

1650 3. Sites

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1656 **Findings for sites**

1657 • Alien species are distributed across the country, with most broad-scale administrative units
1658 and biogeographical regions being invaded by a variety of taxa. Most alien species are found
1659 in the Western Cape, Eastern Cape, and KwaZulu-Natal.

1660 • Recorded alien species richness is highest around major urban centres. A recent increase in
1661 recorded alien species richness around urban areas is due to an increase in records from
1662 citizen science platforms such as iNaturalist.

1663 • The National Invasive Alien Plant Survey (2008–2023) estimated changes in the levels of plant
1664 invasions in terrestrial biomes and water catchment areas. The biomes with the largest
1665 proportion of invaded land are the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt (11%), Fynbos (5%), Albany
1666 Thicket (3%), and Grassland (3%). Six of the primary catchment areas (those that were also
1667 Strategic Water Sources Areas) had a relatively high cover of invasive plants (4–10%). Most of
1668 the plant taxa have increased in cover despite mechanical and chemical control efforts, but
1669 there were decreases in cover for taxa under biological control.

1670 • Biological invasions continue to cause major impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and
1671 human livelihoods by reducing South Africa’s water resources, degrading pasturelands, and
1672 exacerbating fires. These estimates need to be regularly reassessed.

1673 **Gaps for sites**

1674 • Data on the distribution and abundance of alien species need to be collected, collated and
1675 integrated into national and global databases to facilitate the planning of interventions. For
1676 example, due to the absence of monitoring programs, there are no reliable estimates for the
1677 relative abundance of invasive species at sub-national levels (for example protected areas).

1678 • The systematic quantification of the impacts of biological invasions would: facilitate the
1679 prioritisation of interventions targeting particular species and particular sites; provide the
1680 justification for government investment to control biological invasions; and provide important
1681 background to communicate the issue to society.

Invasion-specific outcomes

3. *Extent of area that suffers 'Major' impacts from invasions*

3.1. *Alien species richness*

3.2. *Relative invasive abundance*

3.3. *Impact of invasions*

1683

3.1. Alien species richness

1685 Alien species are distributed across the country, with differences in alien species richness recorded
 1686 across provinces, biomes, primary catchments, and marine ecoregions (Table 3.1; Table S3.1–S3.2). At
 1687 the provincial scale, there has been substantial changes in alien species richness since the last
 1688 reporting period (Table 3.1). Most alien plant species are found in the Western Cape, KwaZulu-Natal,
 1689 Eastern Cape, with Northern Cape having the least number of alien plant species (Table 3.1a). The
 1690 greatest increase in alien plant taxa per province was in Limpopo, Northwest, and KwaZulu-Natal, and
 1691 low increases were found in the other provinces (Table 3.1a). Savanna, Fynbos, and Grassland biomes
 1692 have the highest number of alien plant species, and the Desert and Forest biomes have the least
 1693 number of alien plant species and the lowest increase in alien plant species richness (Table 3.1b). Alien
 1694 freshwater fish species are distributed across most primary catchments, except Buffels River
 1695 catchment that is alien-free (Table 3.1c). A total of 13 primary catchments (59%) have at least 10 alien
 1696 freshwater fish species, e.g., Mfolozi, Berg, and Komati rivers (Table 3.1c). There have been recent
 1697 changes in alien freshwater fish species in five primary catchments (Table 3.1c). The estimates of alien
 1698 species richness for marine ecoregions presented in the last report (cf. Robinson et al. 2020) have not
 1699 been updated due to the lack of comprehensive data for marine taxa in South Africa from the Global
 1700 Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF).

1701 Information on *alien species richness* was also available for SANParks and Cape Nature protected areas
 1702 (Table 3.1e). A total of 1 469 alien and invasive species (excluding biocontrol agents and marine
 1703 species) are now recorded across the SANParks estate – a 48% increase from 2022. The increase in the
 1704 recorded species richness across the SANParks estate between 2022 and 2025 is primarily due to
 1705 recent efforts to revise and update previous lists of alien and invasive plants found within the estate
 1706 (van Wilgen et al., 2026). This revision consolidated various data sources, including historical
 1707 management and research reports, ornamental plant records from Kruger National Park rest camps
 1708 and staff facilities that had been previously excluded, citizen science observations (e.g., iNaturalist),
 1709 and peer-reviewed publications (e.g., Foxcroft et al. 2017). Several challenges were encountered when

1710 merging information from different data sources, including outdated taxonomy, spelling
1711 inconsistencies, and duplicate records, all of which required extensive data cleaning and verification.
1712 The review subsequently produced data pipelines, workflows, and recommendations that can be used
1713 to guide and inform conservation practitioners that aim to develop similar processes to develop a
1714 consolidated list of alien species in protected areas under their management. Of the 1 469 alien
1715 species recorded within the SANParks estate, 276 plants and 74 animal species are currently listed
1716 under the A&IS Regulations (Table S3.4).

1717 The distribution of alien species across protected areas within the SANParks estate is highly skewed.
1718 Three protected areas (Garden Route National Park, Kruger National Park, and Table Mountain
1719 National Park) have recorded more than 300 alien species each (including species that have formed
1720 native-alien populations) (Table S3.3). This is largely due to survey effort, the size of the parks, the
1721 biome(s) that they cover, and the alien taxa listed for each park (i.e., ornamentals are included in the
1722 list for Kruger National Park but not for other parks). The Groenkloof National Park is the only protected
1723 area within the SANParks estate that is listed as alien-free, and the Meerkat and Grasslands national
1724 parks had the lowest species richness likely because of low survey effort.

1725 As noted in previous reports, the alien species richness for birds and plants appears to be highest
1726 around major urban centres in Gauteng, KwaZulu-Natal, and Western Cape, likely due to greater
1727 survey efforts in those areas and because some species are commensal with humans and most species
1728 were first introduced in urban centres (Figure 3.1a, c; Figure S3.1). Information on *alien species*
1729 *richness* from municipalities was only supplied by the City of Cape Town and City of Ekurhuleni (Table
1730 3.1f). In 2022, there were 104 taxa that are reported to occur across the areas managed by the City of
1731 Cape Town (Table 3.1f). The majority of these were plants (98 taxa) and the remainder are three
1732 terrestrial invertebrates (*Euwallacea fornicatus*, *Polistes dominula*, *Vespula germanica*), two birds
1733 (*Anas platyrhynchos*, *Corvus splendens*), and an amphibian (*Amietophrynus gutturalis*). Of these taxa
1734 79 are listed under the A&IS Regulations, and the remaining 27 taxa are unlisted. In 2025, the total
1735 number of alien taxa in areas managed by the City of Cape Town has increased to 284 taxa (Table S3.3),
1736 mainly due to new records of plants (272 taxa) and a few species of legally released biological control
1737 agents for alien plants (*Cyrtobagous salviniae*, *Dactylopius* spp., *Lysanthia* spp., *Megamelus scutellaris*,
1738 *Neohydronomus affinis*), and a bird (*Acridotheres tristis*). The number of taxa listed under the A&IS
1739 Regulations has also increased to 123 and 161 taxa are unlisted.

1740 There are 34 alien taxa that are reported to occur across the areas managed by the City of Ekurhuleni
1741 (Table 3.1f). The majority of these are plants (28 taxa) and the remainder are two terrestrial

1742 invertebrates (*Harmonia axyridis*, *Euwallacea fornicatus*), three birds (*Acridotheres tristis*, *Anas*
 1743 *platyrhynchos*, *Columbia livia*), two fishes (*Cyprinus capio*, *Micropterus salmoides*) and two mammals
 1744 (*Rattus rattus*, *Rattus norvegicus*) (Table S3.3). All of these taxa are listed under the A&IS Regulations,
 1745 except *Euwallacea fornicatus*. These estimates have not been updated in 2025.

1746 **Table 3.1.** Alien species richness in South Africa for different broad-scale administrative units and
 1747 biogeographical regions. The estimates of change are made with low confidence because most reported
 1748 increases arise from the formal recording of species that have probably been present for some time. The values
 1749 are based on records from the Global Biodiversity Information facility (GBIF) (<https://www.gbif.org>) and the
 1750 Southern African Plant Invaders Atlas (SAPIA) for continental South Africa; and Robinson et al. (2020) for marine
 1751 ecoregions. Further details are provided in the Supplementary Material; see Appendix 6] for the full list of alien
 1752 taxa.

1753 a) Alien terrestrial and freshwater plant species richness per province.

Province	End of 2022	End of 2025	Change
Eastern Cape	881	915	34
Free State	482	514	32
Gauteng	782	826	44
KwaZulu-Natal	1 046	1 092	46
Limpopo	663	774	111
Mpumalanga	775	792	17
Northern Cape	366	400	34
North West	440	502	62
Western Cape	1 027	1 063	36

1754 b) Alien plant richness per biome.

Biome	End of 2022	End of 2025	Change
Albany Thicket	583	613	30
Desert	41	46	5
Fynbos	1 031	1 065	34
Forest	166	189	23
Grassland	1 021	1 076	55
Indian Ocean Coastal Belt	784	822	38
Nama-Karoo	337	349	12
Savanna	1 157	1 209	52
Succulent Karoo	297	349	52

1755

1756 c) Alien freshwater fish species richness per primary river catchment.

Primary catchment	End of 2022	End of 2025	Change
A–Limpopo	10	10	0
B–Olifants North	10	10	0
C–Vaal	10	10	0
D–Orange	8	9	1
E–Olifants West	8	8	0
F–Buffels	0	0	0
G–Berg	18	18	0
H–Breede	10	10	0
J–Gouritz	8	8	0
K–Krom	11	11	0
L–Gamtoos	7	7	0
M–Swartkops	8	8	0
N–Sundays	5	5	0
P–Bushmans	7	7	0
Q–Great Fish	7	7	0
R–Keiskamma	13	13	0
S–Kei	9	10	1
T–Mzimvubu	15	15	0
U–Mkomazi	19	19	0
V–Tugela	12	13	1
W–Mfolozi	13	14	1
X–Komati	12	13	1

1757 d) Marine invasive species richness per marine ecoregion (not updated for 2025).

Marine ecoregion	End of 2022
Agulhas	41
Natal	25
Delagoa	8
Southern Benguela	39
Southeast Atlantic (offshore)	0
Southwest Indian (offshore)	0

1758 e) Alien species richness in areas managed by the City of Cape Town and City of Ekurhuleni. [Note: information
 1759 from the City of Cape Town and City of Ekurhuleni have been requested to update the status of alien species
 1760 richness in areas under their respective management. This section will be updated when this information is
 1761 received]

Metro	Group	End of 2022	September 2025	Change
City of Cape Town	Grasses, annuals, vines	45	87	42
	Trees and shrubs	53	185	132
	Terrestrial invertebrates	3	8	5
	Fishes	NA	NA	NA
	Amphibians	1	1	0
	Birds	2	3	1
	Mammals	NA	NA	NA
	Total		104	284
City of Ekurhuleni	Grasses, annuals, vines	11	NA	NA
	Trees and shrubs	17	NA	NA
	Terrestrial invertebrates	2	NA	NA
	Fishes	2	NA	NA
	Amphibians	NA	NA	NA
	Birds	3	NA	NA
	Mammals	2	NA	NA
	Total		37	NA

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1765 **Figure 3.1.** Alien species richness of birds and plants in South Africa per quarter degree grid cell (QDGC) as of
 1766 December 2025 and the change in these values since December 2022. A) alien bird species richness; B) increases
 1767 in alien bird richness; C) alien plant richness; D) increases in alien plant richness. Maps are based on occurrence
 records from GBIF and SAPIA.

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3.2. Relative invasive abundance

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The national-scale survey of invasive plants provided estimates for changes in the *relative invasive abundance* of selected species between 2008 and 2023 in terrestrial biomes and water catchment areas in South Africa (Kotzé et al. 2025). The Indian Ocean Coastal Belt was the most invaded terrestrial biome, with 11% of the remaining natural vegetation invaded, followed by the Fynbos (5%), Albany Thicket (3%) and Grassland (3%) biome (Table 3.2). There was a significant increase in cover between two surveys for the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt (79%), Forest (36%), Nama Karoo (23%) and the Fynbos (20%). Wattles (*Acacia dealbata*, *A. decurrens* and *A. mearnsii*) and *Eucalyptus* species occupied the largest area and spread more rapidly than other taxa, but the relative contribution of taxa differed between biomes (Table S3.5). In contrast the proportion of invaded area decreased for the Desert (34%), Albany Thicket (12%), and Succulent Karoo (18%). These decreases in the proportion of invaded area are likely due to a decrease in cover of *Acacia* trees and succulent cactus shrubs for the Albany Thicket, as well as a decrease in *Neltuma* species in the drier Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes. This

1781 decrease in cover is likely because of successful biocontrol programmes, especially against the cactus
 1782 shrubs (e.g., Paterson et al. 2021).

1783 **Table 3.2.** Changes in the extent of invasion by 14 alien plant taxa in nine terrestrial biomes in South Africa from
 1784 two successive surveys. Based on data from Kotzé et al. (2025)

Biome	Biome area (km ²)	Area of remaining natural vegetation (km ²)	Invaded area in 2008 (km ²)	Invaded area in 2023 (km ²)	% change	% of remaining natural vegetation invaded
Indian Ocean Coastal Belt	1542	850	525	939	79	11
Fynbos	8489	6288	2701	3241	20	5
Albany Thicket	3115	2792	875	773	-12	3
Grassland	32541	21984	5127	5411	6	3
Savanna	40457	34896	3534	3723	5	1
Forest	444	413	20	27	36	<1
Nama Karoo	25913	25473	781.5	962	23	<1
Succulent Karoo	8728	8469	178.1	147	-18	<1
Desert	734	721	18.4	12	-34	<1

1785

1786 Strategic Water Source Areas (SWSAs) are areas of land that either supply a disproportionate (i.e.,
 1787 relatively large) quantity of mean annual surface water runoff in relation to their size or are areas that
 1788 have high groundwater recharge and where the groundwater forms a nationally important resource
 1789 (Le Maitre et al. 2018). In South Africa, SWSAs generate more than half of the country's surface water
 1790 runoff from only 10% of the land, with key groundwater recharge areas contributing up to 42% of river
 1791 baseflow and maintaining flows during dry periods. Kotzé et al. (2025) assessed the impact of plant
 1792 invasions in six primary catchments that have more than 50% of their area classified as SWSAs (Table
 1793 3.3). The six primary catchment areas had a relatively high cover of invasive plants (4–10%) (Table 3.4),
 1794 compared to the national average of 1.5%. There was significant increase in cover (22–32%) for five
 1795 of the six primary catchments that was mainly driven by increases in the estimated cover of *Acacia*,
 1796 *Eucalyptus* and *Pinus* species (Table S3.6). The exception was the Swartkops catchment, where cover
 1797 decreased by 19%. The Swartkops catchment is situated predominantly in the Albany Thicket biome,
 1798 where similar decreases in cover were noted due to a decrease in cover of *Acacia* trees.

1799 **Table 3.3.** Changes in the extent of invasion by 14 alien plant taxa in six primary catchments in South Africa from
 1800 two successive surveys done in 2008 and 2023 respectively. SWSA is Strategic Water Source Area. Only six
 1801 primary catchments are shown (those with >50% of their area classified as SWSAs). Data are from Kotzé et al.
 1802 (2025), see Table S3.6 for information on the other 16 primary catchment areas.

Primary catchment	Catchment area (km ²)	Proportion (%) of catchment in SWSA	Proportion (%) of catchment invaded (2023)	% Change from 2008
Berg	25 322	59	5	28
Breede	15 353	50	4	22
Kromme	7222	67	10	23
Swartkops	2628	79	7	-19
Mzimvubu	46 679	69	5	32
Nkomazi	18 343	72	6	32

1803 3.3. Impact of invasions

1804 van Wilgen et al. (2008) performed a biome-scale assessment of the impact of invasive plants on
 1805 ecosystem services in South Africa. This study has been pivotal in our understanding of the impacts of
 1806 invasive plants (invasive trees in particular) in South Africa, but the study has not been updated or
 1807 revised. There was a recent unsuccessful attempt to replicate these estimates and develop
 1808 transparent and repeatable workflows that could be used to update the figures and track changes
 1809 over time, therefore no updated estimates are possible (see Supplementary S3.3 for more details).

1810 Recent studies have proposed alternative methods for estimating the impacts of plant invasions on
 1811 surface water runoff (e.g., Le Maitre et al. 2016; Moncrieff et al. 2021). However, the key challenge is
 1812 to develop a method that is scalable to the national level while still capturing local-scale variation.

1813 Recent studies have incorporated remote sensing with evapotranspiration models to monitor and
 1814 assess impacts of plant invasions (e.g., Rebelo et al. 2025, Cogill et al. 2025, and Box 3.2). For example,
 1815 a study in selected river catchments (Luvuhu, Sabie-Crocodile, Tugela and uMzimvubu) found that
 1816 invasive trees cover about 10% of the catchment areas, mostly in SWSAs where water resources could
 1817 be increased by between 6 to 176 million m³ across catchments by clearing invasive trees (Rebelo et
 1818 al. 2025).

1819 3.4. High level indicator 3: *Extent of area that suffers 'Major' impacts from invasions*

1820 Biological invasions continue to cause 'Major' impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem services and human
 1821 livelihoods by reducing South Africa's water resources, degrading pasturelands and exacerbating fires.
 1822 These estimates, however, have not been recently revised.

1823 Impacts are likely to increase as invasive species continue to spread and as control efforts are scaled
 1824 back in response to fiscal constraints. This underscores the importance of refocussing control efforts
 1825 on agreed priority sites and taking steps to improve control effectiveness. If control efforts focus on
 1826 priority sites (e.g., sites that provide water to South Africa's towns and cities – SWSAs) then significant

1827 returns on investment could be realised. However, without agreement on priorities, there is a
1828 substantial risk that control could remain ineffective, and the area that suffers from 'Major' impacts
1829 will continue to grow. Estimates of the full magnitude of impacts require more accurate assessments
1830 of the extent of invasions. This, in turn, requires effective mapping of the areas invaded and
1831 monitoring of spread. Such monitoring is currently lacking, and without which effective prioritisation
1832 is not possible.

1833 **Box 3.1** A study to track the extent and abundance of invasive species

1834 The Working for Water Programme commissioned a national-scale survey of selected high-priority
1835 invasive plants in 2007. The survey was completed in 2008 and repeated between 2016 and 2023. The
1836 survey was intended to track trends in cover of 14 plant taxa (at species, genus or family level) on
1837 47830 plots of 100 × 100 m, using observers in low-flying aircraft. The taxa included *Acacia cyclops*, *A.*
1838 *saligna*, *Arundo donax*, *Chromolaena odorata*, *Lantana camara*, *Melia azedarach*, and *Solanum*
1839 *mauritianum*, the genera *Acacia* (other than *A. cyclops* and *A. saligna*), *Eucalyptus*, *Hakea*, *Neltuma*,
1840 *Pinus* and *Populus*, as well as succulents in the family Cactaceae.

1841 The findings of this study were reported for the first time in 2025 (Kotzé et al. 2025). Although the
1842 study only covered a relatively small number of species (31), it provided data to inform the indicator
1843 for trends in the extent of alien species. It was possible to report, for these species at least, trends in
1844 the extent of occupation at a national level, as well as at the level of invasions in terrestrial biomes
1845 and primary water catchment areas. The study found both increases and decreases in extent, with
1846 decreases being attributed to biological control (see section 4.8).

1847 The study was similarly useful for estimating the abundance of the selected species. In the previous
1848 three reports, it was noted that this indicator could not be assessed due to a lack of information. An
1849 estimate can now be provided for 14 taxa, including 31 species. Although there are many more species
1850 for which abundance cannot be estimated, the sample reported by Kotzé et al. (2025) covered species
1851 of a high priority on which > 60% of the money has been spent on control over the past two decades
1852 (van Wilgen et al. 2022b).

1853 This study was intended to provide a reliable monitoring system to inform management on trends in
1854 the extent and abundance of the priority species that were being managed in the country. Recent
1855 substantial cuts in funding (see Section 4.2) have meant that this monitoring programme has been
1856 discontinued. Earth observation through satellite remote sensing can potentially fill the gap, but
1857 several challenges need to be overcome (Box 3.2).

1858

1859 **Box 3.2** The use of remote sensing to monitor plant invasions

1860 Remote sensing is the use of satellites, drones, or aircraft to collect information about the Earth's
1861 surface without physical contact. Recent technological advancements in satellite sensors, cloud
1862 computing, and machine learning have expanded the potential for using remote sensing to map
1863 invasive plants and to monitor the extent of invasions and their impacts (Box Figure 3.1). The open
1864 data movement has created additional opportunities, for example freely available satellite imagery
1865 from Europe's Copernicus programme (Sentinel-2), free cloud computing via the Google Earth Engine
1866 platform, and the researchers who make their code and packages available to others. This has
1867 improved accessibility of remote sensing for ecological applications, particularly in resource
1868 constrained regions.

1869 South Africa has a reasonably long history of using remote sensing to map invasive plants, particularly
1870 trees. Most research has been exploratory, and therefore patchy (e.g., van den Berg et al. 2013,
1871 Meijninger and Jarman 2014, Holden et al. 2021). Recently the National Invasive Alien Plant Survey
1872 combined modelling with remote sensing imagery to produce a national-scale alien plant map (Kotzé
1873 et al. 2025), with detailed distribution data for 14 invasive tree taxa (Box 3.1). However, the map is for
1874 a single point in time and there are no plans to repeat the survey on which it was based, and as such
1875 it will rapidly become out of date. A new project, named 'Mapping Woody invasive Alien Plant Species'
1876 (MAPWAPS) has been piloted in six regions of the country with the goal of producing an easily
1877 updatable national map (Rebello et al. 2025). This project focuses on woody plants at the genus level
1878 (e.g., *Acacia*, *Eucalyptus*, and *Pinus*) although some herbaceous taxa are included and there has been
1879 some success in distinguishing species (e.g., 99% accuracy in distinguishing between different
1880 Australian *Acacia* species in the Eastern Cape; Skosana et al. 2025).

1881 While remote sensing holds promise, several challenges remain. It is not always possible to distinguish
1882 invasive species from native vegetation, particularly when invasions are sparse (scattered or young
1883 individuals) or are herbaceous and grow under or among other species. The acquisition, storage, and
1884 processing costs needed for high resolution imagery can be prohibitive or rely on companies providing
1885 free access (that might be subsequently withdrawn). Finally, maps are often not accurately or
1886 appropriately interpreted, especially when local ecologists are not included in the interpretation. The
1887 inclusion of ecological expertise and in-field validation will continue to be vital if the benefits of
1888 technological advances in remote sensing are to be realised; supplemented by citizen science data if
1889 processing and curation standards are adequate.

1891 **Box Figure 3.2.** A comparison of classifications done with two different types of remote sensing imagery
1892 (hyperspectral vs multispectral) in the Swartberg, South Africa (Source: Rebelo et al. 2025).

1893 4. Interventions

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1898 **Findings and gaps for interventions**

1899 ● There have been no significant legislative changes (2023–2025). However, draft amendments
1900 to the NEM:BA were published, a national strategy has been drafted, the evidence base in
1901 support of listing taxa is growing, and procedures regarding compliance and enforcement are
1902 being implemented.

1903 ● Government investment to manage biological invasions has declined by over 50% (2023–
1904 2025).

1905 ● Even at the previous levels of investment, it was estimated that spending was 4% of that
1906 needed to bring invasions under complete control.

1907 ● No pathway-management plans have been prepared. No species-management plans have
1908 been approved. 48 site-management plans for organs of state have been approved by the
1909 DFFE—fewer than 7% of organs of state have an approved site-management plan.

1910 ● There is partial management in place for many pathways, management focuses on specific
1911 species that pose a threat to agriculture or human health or is not national in scope.

1912 ● The effectiveness of interventions for pathways is not monitored by the management
1913 agencies that implement them. Available estimates for the effectiveness of pathway
1914 management indicate management is ineffective, with illegal and accidental introductions
1915 continuing.

1916 ● The Border Management Authority (BMA) became fully operational in 2023. >39 000
1917 inspections for environmental threats at ports of entry were conducted in 2024, an overall
1918 decline since 2022.

1919 ● The BMA intercepted an illegal import of the red claw crayfish (*Cherax quadricarinatus*) at OR
1920 Tambo, with the offender arrested and convicted.

1921 ● Monitoring of the effectiveness of control interventions that targeted invasive species
1922 remains largely absent, and available information is patchy.

- 1923 ● Recent studies of interventions aimed at the control of invasive species found eight
- 1924 management interventions to be partially effective, three ineffective, and one counter-
- 1925 productive.

- 1926 ● A remote sensing survey found *Acacia cyclops*, *A. saligna*, cacti (family Cactaceae), and *Hakea*
- 1927 *sericea*, all of which are under biological control, decreased in cover at a national level, while
- 1928 all other surveyed species not subjected to biological control had increased in cover.

- 1929 ● WfW ceased funding the research and implementation of biological control at the end of 2022.

- 1930 ● The invaded area increased by 78.8% between 2008 and 2023 in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt
- 1931 biome, and there were also substantial increases in the Forest, Nama Karoo, and Fynbos
- 1932 biomes (36, 23, and 20% respectively), the cover decreased in the Desert, Succulent Karoo,
- 1933 and Albany Thicket biomes by 34, 18 and 12 % respectively.

- 1934 ● The Working for Water programme has discontinued the recording of sites treated. The total
- 1935 area over which alien plant control interventions were conducted is thus not known.

- 1936 ● Formal systems to monitor the outcomes of site treatments are not in place. Research studies
- 1937 that have assessed the effectiveness of control interventions report partial effectiveness—the
- 1938 native vegetation that established after control was typically reduced in species richness.
- 1939 Further interventions are needed if full restoration is to be achieved.

1940

1941

1942 **4.1. Quality of regulatory framework**

1943 Between January 2023 and December 2025, the primary legislation governing biological invasions in
1944 South Africa (the NEM:BA of 2004) did not change nor were the A&IS Lists or Regulations promulgated
1945 under the Act revised (Figure 4.1). No new significant relevant international commitments were
1946 agreed to (the GBF was agreed in December 2022). However there have been some significant
1947 developments. Draft amendments to the NEM:BA were published in May 2024, a national strategy
1948 has been drafted, the evidence base in support of the regulatory listing of taxa has been developed,
1949 and procedures regarding compliance and enforcement are being implemented. These are discussed
1950 in turn below. This section concludes with a discussion of how the regulatory framework is being
1951 implemented.

1952 **4.1.1 Legislative revisions**

1953 The National Environmental Laws Amendment Act, 2022 (NEMLAA) was passed by the President in
1954 June 2022, and came into effect 30 June 2023. The Amendment Act amended, among other Acts,
1955 NEM:BA. Once NEMLAA commences, NEM:BA will have clearer definitions of the terms ‘eradicate’
1956 and ‘control’. It is also clearer from the text that invasive species must be either eradicated or
1957 controlled depending on what is possible under the circumstances (presently landowners and other
1958 role-players are required to both eradicate and control invasive species). Furthermore, NEM:BA will
1959 no longer require landowners to notify competent authorities of the presence of invasive species on
1960 their land. The Minister will have the power to specify the circumstances under which such notification
1961 must be given.

1962 A White Paper on the ‘Conservation and Sustainable Use of South Africa’s Biodiversity’ was published
1963 on 14 June 2023. Biological invasions were referred to in one policy objective: “1.4. *Identify and*
1964 *manage harmful, and potentially harmful, invasive species, their potential and existing introduction*
1965 *pathways and biological invasions.*” The White Paper represents an important step, but as the White
1966 Paper does not cover all aspects of biological invasions (e.g., the focus is on biodiversity rather than
1967 the impacts invasive species have on built-infrastructure and food security) it is unclear if it would
1968 negate the need for a policy specifically on biological invasions. Lukey and Hall (2020) make it clear
1969 that law can be used to implement policy. If a law does not make provision for a means to implement
1970 policy, it may be necessary to introduce new laws or regulations. A White Paper is a precursor to law,
1971 but there is still no policy on biological invasions, so it is not immediately clear what has informed the
1972 drafting of references to invasions in the White Paper.

1973 A ‘Draft National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Bill’ was published for public comment in
1974 the government gazette on 24 May 2024, i.e., immediately before the 2024 general election. A primary
1975 aim of the bill is to “...provide for the management of the impacts of invasive species”, and in general
1976 terms the intention seems to be to simplify what is in the NEM:BA with details to be published in
1977 future regulations. It is not clear at what stage the revisions have reached. Until the Bill is promulgated
1978 (and NEM:BA 2004 is repealed), revised regulations cannot be published.

1979 **4.1.2 A national strategy on biological invasions**

1980 A national strategy on biological invasions (formally the National Invasive Species Strategy and Action
1981 Plan, NISSAP²¹) has been under development for several years, led by the DFFE with input from other
1982 departmental officials and scientists from the SANBI. Various consultations have happened, including
1983 a national stakeholder meeting (21–22 November 2024), but the full draft is yet to be made available
1984 for public comment. In August 2025, the draft was shared with the members of Working Group 1²²,
1985 and the intention is for the strategy to go for public comment in the 2026/27 financial year.

1986 **4.1.3 Processes to provide evidence to inform the listing of alien taxa**

1987 The rationale for including taxa on the A&IS Lists²³ is not clearly set out anywhere. To ensure that
1988 structured evidence informs revisions to the lists, a process has been set up to produce and review
1989 risk analyses (see Figure 5.2D, with details in Wilson and Kumschick 2024). Risk analyses are produced
1990 using the Risk Analysis of Alien Taxa Framework (RAAT). The RAAT framework was recently updated
1991 to v2.0 to i) clarify descriptions; ii) remove superfluous questions; and iii) add questions to fully justify
1992 recommendations (Kumschick et al. 2025). There is still a need, however, to integrate all the
1993 information in the risk analyses with the information presented in the list of alien taxa (Appendix 6)
1994 and ensure that information collated can easily feed to and from international databases.

1995 Risk analyses are produced by whomever is interested in influencing the listings, these are evaluated
1996 by the DFFE and/or SANBI as appropriate and sent by SANBI to an independent scientific body for

²¹The NISSAP is intended to cover all aspects of biological invasions, not just invasive species. The phrasing is to align with the CBD.

²² Working Group 1 is formed under Chapter 3, section 41(1) of the Constitution and fosters the principles of cooperative government and intergovernmental relations. Working Group 1 is made up of national, provincial, and local government officials, and they meet quarterly to discuss and address challenges related to biodiversity and conservation—be it policy, frameworks, action plans etc. These groups are responsible for providing guidance and recommendations to Ministerial sectoral and technical meetings (MINMEC and MINTECH). From there, as appropriate, the strategy would go to the relevant Cabinet and/or Portfolio committees in Parliament.

²³ For full details of the current (and past) NEM:BA A&IS Lists see Wilson (2025).

1997 review (the Alien Species Risk Analysis Review Panel, ASRARP). The risk analysis once approved by
 1998 ASRARP is submitted by SANBI to the DFFE for consideration. The DFFE, as appropriate, tables it at a
 1999 cross-governmental decision-making body (the Risk Analysis Review Committee, RARC) and
 2000 recommendations to revise the regulatory listings are made. The intention is that such
 2001 recommendations will be published along with the risk analyses to justify future revisions to the A&S
 2002 Lists (though as discussed above, this will only happen after the revised Bill is promulgated).

2003
 2004 **Figure 4.1** Timeline of the development of the Alien and Invasive Species Regulations under the National
 2005 National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act (NEM:BA A&S Regulations). Adapted and updated from Wilson
 2006 and Kumschick (2024). ASRARP is the Alien Species Risk Analysis Review Panel (an independent body) and the
 2007 RARC is the Risk Analysis Review Committee (a governmental decision-making body). See Wilson (2025) for full
 2008 details of the A&S Regulations and Lists to date. In 2020 the regulations did not come into effect when they
 2009 were supposed to as there was an ‘extension to the commencement date’. The regulations came into effect in
 2010 March 2021 with the removal of trout species from the lists. This figure was produced using a template from the
 2011 programme Vertex42.

2012 By the end of December 2025, risk analyses for 170 taxa have been evaluated by ASRARP and
 2013 submitted by SANBI to the DFFE, including 148 of the 560 listed taxa (Table S4.1), i.e., over a quarter
 2014 of all listed taxa. Between January 2023 and December 2025, risk analyses on 77 taxa were submitted
 2015 by SANBI to DFFE, slightly more than the period 2020–2022 (68 taxa). Of the risk analyses completed
 2016 on 77 taxa (2023–2025), 68 were regarding currently regulated taxa (of those not regulated, five
 2017 recommended regulating as present in the country and two to be added to a prohibited list), only for

2018 36 of these was there no change recommended to the nomenclature (though as previously this was
2019 mostly about dropping synonyms). In 26 out of the 68 regulated taxa there was a recommended
2020 change to the listing (~38%, slightly less than in previous period 25/58). This is not, however, of
2021 immediate concern as many of the changes are due to the intention to simplify listings and as those
2022 taxa with controversial listings have been prioritised for evaluation.

2023 The Risk Analysis Review Committee (RARC) had its inaugural meeting on 2 February 2023, is meeting
2024 quarterly, and addressing four to five risk analyses at each meeting (thus keeping pace with the rate
2025 at which risk analyses are being produced, though not as yet clearing the backlog). The RARC have
2026 considered ~40 risk analyses as of end December 2025. The intention is that decisions of the RARC
2027 (and supporting risk analyses reviewed by ASRARP) will be made public when revisions to the A&IS
2028 Lists are published for public comment (this will only happen after the new Act has been promulgated).

2029 **4.1.4 Implementation of the regulatory framework**

2030 Technically the quality of the regulatory framework is an input (cf. Figure 0.2). Discussion on the
2031 implementation of the regulatory framework addresses activities (pathways, species, and sites
2032 treated; e.g., the number of inspections carried out and prosecutions) and outputs (levels of
2033 compliance or remedial actions taken). However, as these activities are consolidated in terms of those
2034 responsible (i.e., largely DFFE officials in terms of the A&IS Regulations), the implementation of the
2035 regulatory framework is discussed here.

2036 [Note: the permit database is still to be updated, the following two paragraphs will be updated
2037 accordingly when that update is made]

2038 The process for issuing import permits is described in Figure 5.2E with variation for biological control
2039 agents in Figure 5.2F. XX import permits were issued by DFFE in 2023–2025 for XX taxa with some of
2040 these for research and display purposes; by comparison XXX import permits were issued on XX taxa in
2041 the period 2015–2022 (no permits were issued in 2014). Discuss trend. Notably during 2023–2025 no
2042 permits were issued to import species not already legally in the country, except to import classical
2043 biological control agents (X-ref).

2044 The process for issuing permits to conduct activities on taxa listed under the A&IS Regulations is
2045 described in Figure 5.2G. During 2023–2025, XXX permits were issued (excluding import permits and
2046 permits for research, biological control, or display purposes that can be issued for any listed taxon).
2047 At ~XXX permits per year comparison with an average of ~XXX per year for 2015–2022) (Figure XXX).

2048 Notably, of the 117 listed taxa for which there is provision for permits to be issued for their usage in
2049 the 2020 lists (i.e., category 2) XX taxa have never had a permit issued, a further XX taxa have had five

2050 or fewer permits issued, but the XX most frequently permitted taxa have had over XXX permits each
2051 [in order XXX] (see Table XXX; for the full list of permits see Appendix 6).

2052 DFFE conducts various inspection activities regarding compliance (Fig. 5.2J), as well as enforcement
2053 that can lead to criminal prosecutions (Fig. 5.2K). As part of this report, various types of information
2054 that are needed to facilitate these processes are outlined Table 5.3. However, it is not clear if these
2055 data have been collated yet and are not reported here. [Note: awaiting information on the numbers
2056 of successful prosecutions under the A&IS Regulations in the period covered by this report]. There are,
2057 however, some noteworthy examples of the process being applied, for example, see Section 4.7 for a
2058 discussion of a successful prosecution related to pathways.

2059 Chapter 5 discusses several issues and sources of information that will need to be addressed if the
2060 regulatory framework is to be implemented effectively. For example, import permits are only required
2061 for alien taxa that are not legally in the country (Figure 5.2E), however, such a list does not exist.
2062 Without access to the information outlined in Table 5.3, and more broadly indications of cases of
2063 missing data or reports (e.g., how many permits should have been issued for a given taxon if everyone
2064 were compliant) it is not possible to fully evaluate the extent to which the regulations are being
2065 effectively implemented.

2066 **4.2. Money spent**

2067 McCulloch-Jones et al. (2024) quantified costs from available information and estimated that ZAR 9.6
2068 billion (expressed in 2022 values of ZAR) had been spent managing biological invasions in South Africa
2069 between 1960 and 2023, noting that this was just 4% of the money predicted as being necessary for
2070 management (ZAR231.8 billion in 2022 values, based on models that used estimates from studies of
2071 the potential costs to manage biological invasions). This study also noted that the cost of damage
2072 caused by invasions far exceeded expenditure on control, that almost all management had focussed
2073 on a few invasive plant species, and that there were large gaps in information that reduced the level
2074 of confidence in the estimates. Notably, however, there is very little reliable information on the money
2075 spent on managing biological invasions. Data are not routinely recorded, curated or reported in
2076 consistent ways, and so there is significant uncertainty associated with the findings.

2077 What seems clear is that the money spent has been declining. DFFE budgeted ZAR 0.92 billion to
2078 manage biological invasions 2023–2025, a decrease of ~54% from the ZAR 2.02 billion expended 2020–
2079 2022 (values are adjusted to 2025 values of ZAR).

2080 There have also been notable shifts in spending (Table S4.2). Most notably, the amount spent on
2081 biological control research and implementation 2023–2025 was 17% that of 2020–2022 (Figure 4.2).

2082 This decline was mainly due to the termination of funding from the DFFE’s Working for Water
 2083 programme to the Centre for Biological Control (CBC) at Rhodes University and to the Agricultural
 2084 Research Council’s Plant Health and Protection unit (ARC-PHP) at the end of 2022. While the CBC has
 2085 not been able to conduct research in this field over the past three years, the ARC-PHP has received
 2086 some funding from the Department of Agriculture (DoA) and the Global Environmental Facility. The
 2087 DoA funding has supported research into biological control of *Acacia dealbata* (silver wattle), *Cestrum*
 2088 species, *Parthenium hysterophorus* (parthenium), *Solanum elaeagnifolium* (silver-leaf bitter apple),
 2089 and the operation of facilities for the mass-rearing and release of biological control agents.

2090

2091 **Figure 4.2** The amount of money spent annually on the biological control of invasive plants in South Africa.
 2092 Figures are adjusted for inflation to 2025 values of ZAR. DFFE stopped funding biological control at the end of
 2093 2022 with funds coming from other sources (e.g., the DoA). For the actual values see Table S4.2.

2094 National conservation agencies (South African National Parks and the Isimangaliso Agency) received a
 2095 greater proportion of the budget. For example, all funding in the Western and Northern Cape
 2096 provinces went to South African National Parks, i.e., the provincial authorities in those provinces
 2097 receiving no funding 2023–2025.

2098 An additional amount was budgeted to be spent on value-added products, i.e., the conversion of
 2099 biomass from alien plants into furniture and other products (see Section 4.9 on outcomes below). The
 2100 annual totals for value-added products (adjusted to 2025 values of ZAR) indicate that ZAR 73.8 million
 2101 was budgeted for 2023–2025, a decrease of 60.9% from that spent 2020–2022. Biomass to produce
 2102 value-added products is obtained from a range of sources and not necessarily from alien plant control
 2103 projects alone, nor is it clear whether the income from these products is invested back into control
 2104 interventions (van Wilgen et al. 2022b).

2105 The quality of the record keeping also seems to be declining. Since 2022, information on spending has
2106 not been recorded in DFFE’s Water Information Management System (WIMS), and the DFFE only
2107 supplied the amounts budgeted for individual projects for each year. These budgets are less detailed
2108 than the WIMS data (for example the area cleared and the species treated are not reflected).
2109 Estimates of money spent on the management of biological invasions in South Africa are thus
2110 unreliable. Moreover, the money spent by various entities was largely sourced from the Working for
2111 Water program, and thus summing these amounts would lead to double counting (cf. Table S4.2).
2112 Information on money spent was also only received from a few organisations (no estimates of
2113 spending were received from provincial environmental departments and the only municipalities who
2114 provided estimates were Cape Town and Ekurhuleni).

2115 The Border Management Authority (BMA) has spent on managing pathways and border posts. The
2116 amounts spent have been requested from the BMA, but that data have not yet been received.

2117 The Greater Cape Town Water Fund (GCTWF, Stafford et al. 2018) spent ZAR 184.4 million (adjusted
2118 to 2025 values of ZAR) on the control of invasive trees in the catchments of the Theewaterskloof, Berg
2119 River and Wemmershoek Dams, the Voelvllei Dam, the Steenbras Dam, and the Atlantis Aquifer (2023–
2120 2025; Table S4.2). Spending (2023–2025) was mainly directed towards follow-up work. Due to
2121 declining funding from government sources, the proportion of work funded by the GCTWF at these
2122 sites increased from 47.6% in 2020 to 77.9% in 2025.

2123 The City of Cape Town reported having spent ZAR 140.3 million (2023–2025). Of this 125.5M was on
2124 alien plants, 5.6M on alien animals, and 9.2M on the polyphagous shot hole borer. The City of
2125 Ekurhuleni (Gauteng) spent ZAR 37.7 million 2023–2025 on the control of invasive species in 384 ha.
2126 The eThekweni (Durban) and Cape Town metros have spent ZAR 3.27 million (adjusted for inflation to
2127 2025 values of ZAR) on attempts to eradicate House Crows 2023–2025.

2128 **4.3. Planning coverage**

2129 **4.3.1 Pathway management plans**

2130 To address Target 6 of the GBF, pathway management plans (also termed ‘pathway action plans’)
2131 should be developed for pathways that have been prioritised for management and for which
2132 management is feasible (CBD and IUCN 2024; see Section 5.7). In South Africa, there is no legal
2133 requirement for pathway management plans under the A&IS Regulations nor under any other relevant
2134 regulations, and there has been no national exercise to prioritise pathways for management or to
2135 determine the feasibility of such management. Ballast water management plans have reportedly been
2136 developed for eight ports, but a 2012 study found that only three such plans (Port of Saldanha Bay,

2137 Port of Ngqura, and the Port of Durban) could be produced (Calitz 2012). The ballast water
2138 management plan for one of these ports (Saldanha Bay) is still well-recognised and details several
2139 mechanisms to track and control ballast water release (Anchor Environmental Consultants 2024).
2140 Nonetheless, the requirements set out in these plans differ (Calitz 2012) (see Section S4.3 for further
2141 details).

2142 Recent guidance has been provided at an international level as to what pathway action plans should
2143 contain (CBD and IUCN 2024)—pathway action plans should set out strategic actions (e.g., at-border
2144 checks, methods to minimise contamination, codes of practice, awareness raising) that need to be
2145 taken for each pathway. While the actions outlined in these plans should be informed by international
2146 agreements, and the guidelines and standards linked to these agreements, additional, national actions
2147 are still required (see Section S4.3 for further details of what pathway action plans should contain).
2148 The pathway management plans that have been developed for South Africa do not follow these
2149 pathway action plan guidelines.

2150 **4.3.2 Species-specific management plans**

2151 For species, the NEM:BA [Section 75(4)] requires the Minister to ensure the coordination and
2152 implementation of ‘Prevention, Control or Eradication of Invasive Species Programmes’ (hereafter
2153 species-specific management plans). To this end, the Minister may also establish an entity consisting
2154 of public servants to coordinate and implement these programmes.

2155 No species-specific management plans have been formally adopted, although, as discussed in previous
2156 reports, plans have been prepared for two species [*Parthenium hysterophorus* (parthenium) and
2157 *Campuloclinium macrocephalum* (pompom weed)], two genera [*Acacia* (wattles) and *Neltuma*
2158 (formerly *Prosopis*, mesquite)], and one family [Cactaceae (cacti)] of invasive plants. [We are awaiting
2159 information on species plans for alien plants that are targets for national eradication.]

2160 Although biological control agents are identified, screened and released for the control of specific
2161 invasive plant species, there are no formal species-specific management plans to guide these
2162 interventions, or to integrate them with other control methods.

2163 A detailed strategy and control plan for the house crow (*Corvus splendens*) was compiled by a multi-
2164 stakeholder group consisting of national government, provincial government, municipalities, SANBI,
2165 the Centre for Invasion Biology, and other invasion biologists (DFFE 2023). The overall objective of the
2166 strategy is to prevent the establishment of a permanent house crow population in South Africa by
2167 eradicating all existing populations and any subsequent arrivals. This Strategy provides a framework
2168 for achieving this objective, including by setting six goals with timelines and responsibilities. It also

2169 seeks to coordinate actions between various role players and to facilitate the release of resources.
2170 The strategy is designed to give effect to the requirements of NEM:BA for organs of state to prepare
2171 invasive species monitoring, control and eradication plans for land under their control. The strategy
2172 estimates that South Africa will have to commit ZAR 8 million per year for at least the next three to
2173 five years to achieve the objectives and goals, with costs reducing thereafter, but there will be a
2174 surveillance and rapid response requirement in perpetuity. The strategy stresses that failure to
2175 commit these resources and fully implement the strategy will result in the certainty of establishing a
2176 permanent and abundant population of house crows and transferring costs and impacts to future
2177 generations. The strategy was submitted to the DFFE in March 2023 but has not yet been approved.

2178 The Department of Agriculture has developed an emergency plant pest response plan (Department of
2179 Agriculture, no date). The aim of the plan is to outline an effective rapid response for the detection,
2180 identification, and mitigation of an emergency plant pest incursion in South Africa. The plan covers
2181 methods and actions to control of the spread of a pest during the early stages of incursion; to
2182 determine if eradication is possible; to provide effective and timely communication between
2183 stakeholders at all levels about when responses are needed; to protect unaffected areas and to
2184 maintain production and business continuity in affected areas during a plant pest emergency. Funds
2185 will need to be used for the coordinated management of resources within government, research and
2186 industry institutions.

2187 **4.3.3 Site-specific management plans**

2188 The NEM:BA section 76 (2) (a) requires all organs of state in all spheres of government to prepare an
2189 'Invasive Species Monitoring, Control and Eradication Plan' (hereafter a site-specific management
2190 plan) for land under their control. Section 10 (2) of the A&IS Regulations state that organs of state in
2191 all spheres of government must prepare their site-specific management plan based on prescribed
2192 guidelines, and submit those plans to the Minister and to SANBI. The guidelines are based on criteria
2193 listed in NEM:BA section 76 (4), and include a list of all invasive species; description of the parts of that
2194 land that are infested with such listed invasive species; the extent of such infestation; the efficacy of
2195 previous control measures; the current measures to monitor and control invasive species; and
2196 measurable indicators of progress.

2197 In addition to the requirements under NEM:BA, management authorities of protected areas are
2198 required to submit a protected area management plan to the Minister or the MEC for approval in
2199 terms of the National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act (NEM:PAA, Act 57 of 2003).
2200 These plans include the need to manage biological invasions but were not assessed for this report.

2201 Details of the site-specific management plans are captured by the DFFE in a database. The database
 2202 includes the name and location of the site, the date of submission of the plan, the period for which
 2203 the plan is valid and whether the plan has been approved. The plan is evaluated by the DFFE in terms
 2204 of whether it meets the required criteria and is either approved or returned for revision if necessary
 2205 (Figure 5.2I). Importantly, as discussed above, the database does not include the management plans
 2206 prepared in terms of the NEM:PAA.

2207 The DFFE has received 216 site-specific management plans since 2016 (Table S4.3). Plans were
 2208 submitted by conservation agencies, municipalities, metros, and a variety of organs of state (e.g.,
 2209 Eskom, SANRAL, the Ports Authority, and the Airports Authority), as well as for privately-owned areas.
 2210 Of the 128 plans prepared by state-owned landowners, 48 (37.5%) have been approved and signed
 2211 off, while 56 of the 88 plans submitted by private landowners (63.6%) have been approved and signed
 2212 off. The area covered by the plans (in hectares) is not recorded on the DFFE’s database. In addition,
 2213 the period for which the plan is valid has not been captured, and it is thus not possible to estimate the
 2214 value for the indicator for planning coverage (the proportion of the relevant area covered by plans).
 2215 The largest number of plans submitted came from the Western Cape (63% of the plans from state-
 2216 owned land and 92% from private landowners, Table S4.3).

2217 SANBI has developed a strategy for the management of biological invasions within National Botanical
 2218 Gardens (SANBI 2025). The main aim of the strategy is *“To anticipate, prevent entry, and where
 2219 feasible and/or necessary, control biological invasions [in National Botanical Gardens and the National
 2220 Zoological Garden], in an effort to minimise their negative impacts on the ecological integrity of
 2221 protected indigenous biodiversity”* (SANBI 2025, adapted from Freitag-Ronaldson 2005). The strategy
 2222 notes that plans have been developed for the Free State, KwaZulu-Natal, Kwelera, and Kirstenbosch
 2223 National Botanical Gardens, and others are being developed. These have not yet been included in the
 2224 DFFE’s database or assessed.

2225 **Table 4.2** The number of site-specific management plans submitted to the DFFE since 2016 by state-owned and
 2226 private landowners. Since all organs of state are required to have plans in place, the number of plans approved
 2227 shown be equal to the number of entities. A list of all organs of state that require a site is not available (Table
 2228 5.3), noting that many organs of state do not manage land. The process for the evaluation of such plans is
 2229 outlined in Figure 5I.

Entity	Number of entities	Number of plans	Number of plans approved
Private	> 7 000 000	88	56
Municipalities	249	45	No data
Provincial protected areas	427	34	No data
Other organs of state	No data	25	No data
National Parks	21	17	No data
Metros	8	14	No data

2230 4.4. Pathways treated

2231 Forty (40) of 44 pathways are managed to some extent and this has not changed since December
2232 2022. However, for half of these pathways (20), management is partial (e.g., focusing only on specific
2233 species that pose a threat to agriculture or human health or not being national in scope, see Section
2234 S4.5). For example, South Africa is a signatory to the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) and
2235 must give effect to the International Convention for the Control and Management of Ships' Ballast
2236 Water and Sediments (BWM) through national legislation. The Ballast Water Management Bill was
2237 drafted in 2013 and went out for public comment in 2017, but as of February 2025, it had not been
2238 enacted (Parliamentary Monitoring Group 2025). Ballast water management is currently only
2239 implemented at a few ports [e.g., Saldanha Bay (Anchor Environmental Consultants 2024)]. An
2240 important pathway that is still not managed is biofouling on aquatic vessels. The guidelines for
2241 managing biofouling developed by the IMO were recently updated, and the updated version adopted
2242 in 2023 (IMO 2023). The development of a legally binding framework for the control and management
2243 of ships' biofouling has been approved
2244 (<https://www.imo.org/en/ourwork/environment/pages/biofouling.aspx>).

2245 The Border Management Authority (BMA), which was established through the Border Management
2246 Authority Act of 2020, became fully operational in 2023. This represents a major change in the way
2247 many pathways are managed (Box 4.1), integrating functions previously performed by various
2248 government departments at ports of entry (see Figure 4.3 for ports of entry through which alien
2249 species can be legally imported).

2250 There have been changes since 2022 to the operations carried out by DFFE at OR Tambo International
2251 Airport. Between January 2023 and August 2025 ~81 200 inspections at OR Tambo International
2252 Airport were performed for environmental threats, with most of these being performed at the arrivals
2253 (~56 700) and departures (~23 000) terminals (Figure S4.4). Notably this represents a decline in the
2254 number of inspections – in 2022 ~46 500 inspections were undertaken, but in 2023 there were ~27
2255 700 inspections and in 2024 there were ~ 39 100 inspections (Figure S4.4). As of December 2022,
2256 officials performed inspections at the mail centre; at the arrivals, departures and cargo terminals; and
2257 at the private terminal, Fireblade (Figure 5.2A). Inspections continue to be performed at most of these
2258 locations, but in 2023 the Mail Centre relocated from the OR Tambo International Airport precinct to
2259 the new Germiston Mail Centre, and consequently inspections of the mail were halted until September
2260 2025. Since 2023 inspections of cargo and at Fireblade have been hindered by transport challenges.
2261 These changes, delays in the deployment of x-ray scanners, and capacity constraints have contributed
2262 to the reduced number of inspections. Financial constraints have meant that there has been a

2263 reduction in the number of inspectors employed. An arrangement was initiated to assist with
2264 inspections for CITES listed species - this has exacerbated capacity constraints.

2265 Details on the cargo inspections were recorded for 2023, and as for 2020-2022, almost all the imported
2266 cargo consignments inspected (99% of ~73 consignments) were of *Psittacula krameri* (rose-ringed
2267 parakeet), with one consignment inspected for *Centrochelys sulcata* (spur-thighed tortoise). These
2268 taxa are listed under the A&IS Regulations [see Appendix 6 and Wilson (2025) for details]. Such
2269 information on cargo inspections is no longer recorded, and so cannot be reported on for 2024 and
2270 2025.

2271 Inspections for agricultural threats (of imported plants, animals and their products) are performed at
2272 various ports of entry and other sites (e.g., National Plant and Plant Product Inspection Services
2273 regional offices). If a suspected plant pathogen or pest is found during an inspection, tests are
2274 performed for 'quarantine pests' by Plant Diagnostic Services. Plant Diagnostic Services also performs
2275 these tests on 'audit samples', and some imported animals and plants are also kept under quarantine
2276 while further tests are done. 'Quarantine pests' are those that have been assessed through a pest risk
2277 analysis, have been deemed to pose an unacceptable risk to agriculture, and are prohibited from
2278 entering the country (in terms of agricultural regulations rather than the A&IS Regulations). There are
2279 also several other biosecurity initiatives that focus on agricultural pests, including public-private
2280 partnerships (see Box 4.1).

2281 [Inspection data for agricultural threats has been requested from the BMA, but has not yet been
2282 received]

2283

2284

2285 **Figure 4.3.** Alien species can be legally imported through 11 of South Africa's 71 official ports of entry. Ports of
 2286 entry through which alien species can be imported are shown in black, other ports of entry are shown in red.
 2287 The red cross on the map represents Zanzibar, a port of entry between South Africa and Botswana that was
 2288 withdrawn in November 2023.

2289 **4.5. Species treated**

2290 A national list of alien taxa in South Africa has been developed, in which it is recorded whether the
 2291 species has received treatment, and what the effectiveness of that treatment has been (Zengeya et
 2292 al. in press). Control interventions have been directed at 183 taxa (out of 560) listed under the A&IS
 2293 Regulations, and a further 136 taxa that are not listed. Information on species treated has been
 2294 derived from several sources, including published accounts and submissions from a range of
 2295 government agencies, NGOs and private individuals in response to requests for such information.
 2296 Most information on government-funded interventions was historically sourced from the WfW Water
 2297 Information Management System (WIMS). The WIMS system is no longer consistently used, and
 2298 Working for Water was unable to provide a list of species that had been treated over the past three
 2299 years. Requests were made to organs of state, provincial conservation agencies and municipalities and
 2300 metros to provide this information, but only two submissions were received. The City of Cape Town
 2301 carried out control interventions aimed at 210 alien taxa (of which 118 were listed under the A&IS
 2302 Regulations), and the City of Ekurhuleni carried out interventions aimed at the control of 11 listed
 2303 alien species (10 plants and one freshwater fish). Studies published over the past three years have
 2304 assessed the outputs and outcomes of interventions to control 11 species (5 terrestrial plant species,
 2305 two aquatic plant species, two insect species and one pathogenic fungus, see supplementary Table
 2306 S4.4 for details).

2307 Several alien species have been identified as potential targets for national eradication. Information on
2308 these has been requested and will be included in this report when received.

2309 Biological control of invasive plants has targeted 66 species (Zachariades 2021). In many cases, this
2310 control continues without the need for further management interventions, but in some cases (for
2311 example for aquatic plants) continued management in the form of mass rearing and release of agents
2312 is required. Four new biological control agents were released against four target invasive plant species
2313 between 2023 and 2025 (Table 4.3).

2314 **Table 4.3** Biological control agents released in South Africa between 2023 and 2025. Information supplied by
2315 the Plant Health and Protection unit of the Agricultural Research Council.

Target invasive plant species	Biological control agent	Year first released
<i>Acacia dealbata</i>	<i>Perilampella hecateus</i>	2023
<i>Sagittaria platyphylla</i>	<i>Listronotus appendiculatus</i>	2023
<i>Salvinia minima</i>	<i>Cyrtobagous salviniae</i> (Florida)	2025
<i>Tecoma stans</i>	<i>Heikertingerella</i> sp.	2023

2316

2317 A total of ZAR413 768 was spent eThekweni (Durban) metro to manage house crows 2023–2025.
2318 Another project has been ongoing in the Cape Town metro during the period covered by this status
2319 report (DFFE 2023), but recent details were not available.

2320 Control interventions are ongoing for many other species that have been subjected to control in the
2321 past, even though funding has declined over the past three years. However, compiling a list of all
2322 species subjected to control interventions every three years cannot be made with confidence at this
2323 stage.

2324 **4.6. Sites treated**

2325 The area over which alien plant control interventions were conducted 2023–2025 is not known. Most
2326 of the information was historically sourced from WIMS, but this system is no longer consistently used,
2327 and WfW was unable to provide the details of areas that had been treated over the past three years.
2328 In addition, no information was obtained from organs of state, provincial conservation agencies, and
2329 municipalities and metros, with three exceptions. South African National Parks indicated that alien
2330 plant control interventions were implemented in 18 of the 22 national parks under their management,
2331 and the City of Cape Town submitted management plans indicating that alien plant control
2332 interventions were implemented in 11 nature reserves. The City of Ekurhuleni reported that invasions
2333 were managed over an area of 384.4 ha. Private landowners and volunteer groups (cf. Box 4.2) also
2334 manage invasions at particular sites, incorporating such contributions into the report remains a
2335 significant gap (Chapter 6).

2336 **4.7. Effectiveness of pathway treatments**

2337 There is no systematic monitoring of pathway treatments, and their effectiveness is not assessed by
2338 the management agencies that implement them. Therefore, the effectiveness of pathway treatments
2339 was determined based on recently published data and data obtained from management agencies. For
2340 24 of the 44 pathways (55%) there is either no management or management was ineffective [for 13
2341 pathways (30%) the effectiveness of management could not be estimated]. There has been little
2342 change since December 2022 to the estimated effectiveness of pathway management, with the
2343 estimates remaining the same for 93% of pathways. In many cases, recently published research or
2344 data obtained from management agencies confirmed the assessment made in the previous report
2345 (Section S4.6).

2346 There was one instance of a prosecution arising from inspections carried out by DFFE at OR Tambo
2347 International Airport between January 2023 and August 2025. In January 2024, 158 live freshwater
2348 crayfish weighing 30kg were found in the luggage of a traveller at the international passengers arrival
2349 terminal. The individual, a repeat offender who was previously found with *Eriocheir sinensis* (Chinese
2350 mitten crab), was arrested and charged in accordance with the NEM:BA. The crayfish were identified
2351 by experts at the Pretoria Zoo as *Cherax quadricarinatus* (red claw crayfish), currently listed as 1b.
2352 The case resulted in a conviction, and the offender was fined R 50 000. Such interceptions, as well as
2353 various studies (see below for discussion on these studies), indicate that intentional introductions (the
2354 focus of these inspections) are not being effectively managed.

2355 Studies on the pet trade have confirmed that the management of this pathway is ineffective, with
2356 poor co-operation and ambiguous lines of responsibility posing a challenge to the effective regulation
2357 of parts of this trade (Shivambu et al. 2024a; Vezi et al. 2024). Up until 2014 a ‘safe’ list approach
2358 (Kumschick et al. 2024) was followed for imports of ornamental fish (DEA 2015). Yet of the 312 species
2359 included in an inventory of the trade only 77 are on that list (Vezi et al. 2024). The current process is
2360 unclear, but it does not appear to be in line with other import processes (cf. Figure 5.2E) and such
2361 imports have not been recorded in the DFFE’s permit database. There is therefore significant concern
2362 around the legality of alien ornamental fish imports. The traded species included 13 that are invasive
2363 in their global introduced range, four recorded as invasive in the country, and one which has had
2364 ‘Major’ impacts (*Micropterus salmoides*) on South Africa’s freshwater systems (Vezi et al. 2024). It is
2365 currently unclear whether DFFE or DoA is responsible for the management of ornamental fish
2366 importation records, and freshwater and marine fish permit records are not available. The records
2367 that do exist have not been digitised (Vezi et al. 2024). Alien pet birds are escaping from captivity,
2368 although some of the escaping species are already found outside of captivity and are listed in the A&IS

2369 regulations, including *Acridotheres tristis* (category 3, common myna), *Anas platyrhynchos* (category
2370 3, mallard), *Columba livia* (category 2 and 3, rock dove), *Psittacula krameri* (category 2, rose-ringed
2371 parakeet), and *Sturnus vulgaris* (category 3, common starling) (Shivambu et al. 2024a). *Psittacula*
2372 *krameri* was the third most reported pet bird species escaping from captivity (149 reports of lost birds,
2373 82 of found birds, and 12 sighted), with only *Psittacus erithacus* (grey parrot) and *Nymphicus*
2374 *hollandicus* (cockatiel) having more reports (Shivambu et al. 2024a). These findings suggest that
2375 permitting is ineffective in stopping escapes, and therefore that relisting might need to be considered.

2376 The management of the horticulture/ornamental plant pathways also appears to be ineffective.
2377 Almost half of the alien tree species planted in the town of Prince Albert (28 of 62 species) are listed
2378 under the A&IS Regulations. Importantly, most of these regulated tree species were also self-seeding
2379 (Milton and Dean 2025), representing spread from ornamental plantings. Similarly, of the 94 alien
2380 plant species planted within the Tshwane University of Technology grounds, almost a half (43 species)
2381 are listed in the regulations (Nelufule et al. 2024). While some of these plantings may have been
2382 before the regulations were first promulgated in 2014; these is evidence that alien taxa listed in the
2383 regulations are still being sold at nurseries (Rodríguez-Cala et al. 2025b).

2384 A comprehensive dataset of agricultural inspections performed by DoA (Saccaggi et al. 2021) has been
2385 used in several national and international studies, which have indicated that harmful species are likely
2386 slipping through the borders with imports of plants and their products. One of these studies
2387 attempted to estimate the effectiveness of South Africa’s interventions to prevent insect introductions
2388 with fruit imports (Shabangu 2023). The study implemented a method developed by Bacon et al.
2389 (2012), which is applicable for situations like that in South Africa, where the data available are not
2390 ideal for estimating effectiveness. The study concluded that there appear to be biases in inspections;
2391 and that there are pathways that should receive more attention based on the risks posed. The study
2392 also highlighted potentially harmful species that have not yet been recorded the country but are likely
2393 to slip through border control because of these biases. Many of these were thrips (*Frankliniella*
2394 *intonsa*, *Frankliniella schultzei*, *Thrips fuscipennis*, and *Thrips major*), but the mealybug,
2395 *Maconellicoccus hirsutus*, whose introduction was prohibited under the A&IS Regulations of 2016, was
2396 also shown to have a high risk of being introduced. There were far more interceptions of non-
2397 quarantine species than quarantine species, which could be due to the efforts of exporters to ensure
2398 consignments are free of quarantine pests. However, non-quarantine pests could also pose a threat
2399 and should not be ignored. There were a few challenges to the implementation of the method, such
2400 as lack of transparent, comprehensive watch lists (or quarantine lists), and a large proportion of the
2401 records not being identified to species level (~50%). There are several reasons why there is taxonomic

2402 uncertainty in inspection data (see Saccaggi and Ueckermann 2024), and while this issue poses a
2403 challenge to estimates of intervention efficacy, it also importantly poses a threat to the country's
2404 biosecurity (Saccaggi and Ueckermann 2024). An international study that used the data from South
2405 Africa highlighted that certain groups of insects are slipping through border controls and are
2406 establishing without being intercepted (Turner et al. 2025). For example, higher interceptions were
2407 recorded for plant feeding insects than other groups, which could reflect the emphasis on
2408 phytosanitary inspections at borders, but could also be due to differences across taxa in ease of
2409 detection (and identification), or variation in establishment probabilities (Turner et al. 2025). There
2410 have also been several recently recorded new alien species have that were likely introduced as
2411 contaminants of imported products (Section 1.2).

2412 [Note: Inspection data for agricultural threats has been requested from the BMA, information will be
2413 added once received]

2414 **4.8. Effectiveness of species treatments**

2415 The absence of formal monitoring programmes remains a significant barrier to estimating the
2416 effectiveness of species treatments. Some information has been gleaned from a range of sources and
2417 is summarised below. However, the coverage is patchy, as reported in the previous report.

2418 [Note: The list of alien taxa needs to be updated with new information to derive numbers].

2419 In South Africa, 90 invasive plant species have been targeted for biological control using 136 agents,
2420 of which 92 are established on 66 target species (Zachariades 2021). Zachariades (2021) reported that
2421 72% of the agents inflict some level of damage to the host plant, and 35% inflict extensive damage
2422 (Zachariades 2021). Moran et al. (2021) also evaluated the success of biological control on alien plant
2423 species in the country that have had agents released on them for long enough for biological control
2424 to have reached its full potential. Of the 54 targeted species considered, 39 have been reduced below
2425 pre-biological control levels for at least one of the metrics evaluated (density, biomass, area, rate of
2426 spread), and 15 have been reduced permanently to levels where they no longer have any negative
2427 impacts (Moran et al. 2021). Although this assessment was conducted in 2021, the benefits are
2428 permanent and have continued to contribute to a reduction in the negative impacts from invasive
2429 plants in South Africa in recent years. For the biological control agents released more recently (Table
2430 4.3) it is too early to be able to assess their effectiveness.

2431 Paterson et al. (2024) provides a review of post-release evaluations of biological control programs
2432 against invasive plants in South Africa. These assessments have been done at levels ranging from
2433 physiological changes within individual plants, plant growth parameters, plant population dynamics

2434 and landscape level changes. Twenty-three post-release evaluations were included in the Paterson et
2435 al. (2024) review, the majority of which provided evidence of a reduction in negative impacts at the
2436 level of the study (i.e., individual plant, population, or landscape level). In most cases, studies showed
2437 a reduction in the plant invasion but have not investigated the actual benefits accrued to ecosystems
2438 and society, except in a few cases (e.g., Coetzee et al. 2020; Motitsoe et al. 2020, 2022).

2439 Post-release evaluations have provided direct evidence for the complete and permanent control of
2440 several cactus weeds such as *Opuntia stricta* (Hoffmann et al. 2020, Australian pest pear),
2441 *Cylindropuntia fulgida* (Klein et al. 2020, boxing-glove cactus), and *Cereus jamacaru* (Muskett et al.
2442 2024, queen of the night cactus). The biological control of *Opuntia aurantiaca* (jointed cactus),
2443 although not considered under complete control (Moran et al. 2021), has had considerable benefits
2444 to society (Mnqeta and Paterson 2024). Invasive aquatic plants have also been assessed providing
2445 evidence that biological control has been effective against several important species including
2446 *Pontederia crassipes* (water hyacinth), *Salvinia molesta* (Kariba weed), *Azolla filiculoides* (Azolla), *Pistia*
2447 *stratiotes* (water lettuce) and *Myriophyllum aquaticum* (parrot's feather) with significant benefits
2448 (Coetzee et al. 2021; Coetzee et al. 2022). Both invasive cacti and aquatic plant species require mass-
2449 rearing and releases, with 81 releases totalling over 270 000 agents released on six invasive water
2450 weed species and 56 releases of over 10 000 agents for cactus weeds in 2024 alone (CBC Annual Report
2451 2024). Augmentative releases of these agents have yielded positive results, improving levels of control
2452 (Coetzee et al. 2022; Moffett et al. 2024). Post-release evaluations also provide evidence for the
2453 substantial control of *Acacia saligna* (Port Jackson) (Wood and Den Breeyen 2021), as well as changes
2454 in trajectory of the invasion towards long-term reductions in populations of several Australian *Acacia*
2455 species that are targeted with seed-attacking biological control agents (Impson et al. 2021a,b).

2456 The findings from two successive surveys of the extent of invasion by 32 invasive species (grouped
2457 into 14 taxa) at a national level was reported for the first time by Kotzé et al. (2025). The survey was
2458 completed in 2008 and repeated between 2016 and 2023. The cover of most taxa increased between
2459 the two surveys, but *Acacia cyclops* (rooikrans), *A. saligna*, cacti (family Cactaceae), and *Hakea sericea*
2460 (silky hakea), all of which are under biological control, decreased in cover. While other species
2461 increased despite biological control [e.g., *Acacia mearnsii* (black wattle)], all the surveyed species that
2462 were not subjected to biological control increased in cover. For many species, such as *A. mearnsii*,
2463 changes in cover such as those measured in Kotzé et al. (2025) would not have expected to have
2464 changes, as the agents have not been present in the system for long enough to have resulted in
2465 measurable impacts in plant density.

2466 The biological control agent *Uromycladium woodii* (a pathogenic fungus) against the invasive tree
2467 species *Paraserianthes lophantha* (Australian albizia) is very effective with 100% mortality of trees.
2468 However, field observations now suggest that seedlings of *P. lophantha* are emerging from the soil
2469 seed bank, and they show no signs of infection with *U. woodii*. This is because the fungus has died off
2470 in localities where all its host plants have been eliminated. It has proved difficult to maintain a culture
2471 for the re- release of the fungus now that funding for this work has ceased. The intervention might
2472 therefore prove ineffective in the long term (A. Wood, Agricultural Research Council, personal
2473 communication).

2474 There are few examples of attempts to control invasive pathogens, and it is an important aspect that
2475 requires attention. An example of such a species is *Phytophthora cinnamomi*, a globally recognised
2476 invasive plant pathogen. In South Africa, *P. cinnamomi* is known to cause root rot in endemic
2477 Proteaceae. Msweli et al. (2025) reported on a trial that used phosphite and assessed its effectiveness
2478 against *P. cinnamomi* infection in the indigenous tree *Leucadendron argenteum*. Phosphite was
2479 effective on seedlings in the glasshouse but proved to be ineffective in field trials.

2480 An attempt to eradicate *Corvus splendens* (house crow) from South Africa has been ongoing, but
2481 control to date seems to be ineffective. During 2023–2025, 1882 birds were euthanised in eThekweni
2482 (Durban) metro, but the estimated population grew from 1000 birds in 2023 to 1200 birds in 2025.
2483 Another project has been ongoing in the Cape Town metro during the period covered by this status
2484 report (DFFE 2023), but recent details were not available. In addition, new populations have
2485 established in Pietermaritzburg and Richard’s Bay in KwaZulu/Natal province, and in East London,
2486 Gqeberha, and the general areas of Makhanda and Port Alfred in the Eastern Cape province, and
2487 populations are spreading and growing—the species has now established populations in seven coastal
2488 metros and municipalities (DFFE 2023). There are several major issues to address if eradication is to
2489 be achieved: sustained funding and sustained control will be essential if gains from control operations
2490 are not lost; given their high levels of intelligence, crows are very difficult to control at low density
2491 (and therefore to extirpate from a site); and there is no evidence to suggest existing introduction
2492 pathways have been effectively closed (and so, even if nation-wide extirpation was achieved, the
2493 expectation is that reinvasion would be swift).

2494 Eight working groups have been established to improve the effectiveness of management of biological
2495 invasions (Table 4.4) by exchanging ideas and information and developing practical approaches to
2496 implementing potential solutions. These working groups have no legal standing or statutory role, but
2497 rather they constitute a community of practice that enables decision makers and researchers to work
2498 collaboratively while advancing projects through integrated decision-making. The effectiveness of

2499 these groups has only been assessed in the case of the Cape Invasive Animal Working Group, where
 2500 Davies et al. (2020) concluded that their deliberations improved management effectiveness and
 2501 helped to make decisions on interventions.

2502 **Table 4.4.** Working groups established to share information and co-ordinate management interventions relating
 2503 to biological invasions in South Africa.

Working group	Focus of activities	Geographical scope	Notes / Reference
Marine Alien and Invasive Species Working Group	Marine and estuarine organisms	Coastal provinces	Group was initiated but is currently inactive
Cactus Working Group	Plants in the family Cactaceae	National	Kaplan et al. (2017)
Alien Grass Working Group	Plants in the family Poaceae	National	Visser et al. (2017)
Australian Woody Plants Working Group	Tree and shrub species native to Australia	National	None
Cape Floristic Region Partnership Invasive Alien Animal Working Group	Vertebrate and invertebrate fauna	Fynbos Biome (Western and Eastern Cape provinces)	Deliberations by the group improved management effectiveness and helped make decisions on interventions (Davies et al. 2020)
KwaZulu/Natal Invasive Species Forum	All taxa	KwaZulu/Natal province	None
Eastern Cape Invasive Alien Species Forum	All taxa	Eastern Cape province	Currently in an inception phase.
KwaZulu/Natal Aquatic invasive working group	Aquatic plants	KwaZulu/Natal province	None

2504

2505 **4.9. Effectiveness of site treatments**

2506 As reported previously, the scarcity of formal systems to monitor the outcomes of site treatments
 2507 (i.e., changes in the populations of invasive species or ecosystem recovery after their removal) remains
 2508 an obstacle to assessing the effectiveness of site treatments. Such assessments therefore must be
 2509 based on a few studies. All these studies reported partial effectiveness of interventions as the native
 2510 vegetation that established after control was typically reduced in species richness, and it was generally
 2511 concluded that further interventions would be needed if full restoration was to be achieved (see Table
 2512 S4.4 for details). Some notable findings are summarised briefly below.

2513 Kotzé et al. (2025) reported that six primary catchment areas with > 50% of their area classified as
 2514 strategic water source areas had between 4.4–10.1% cover of invasive plants, compared to the
 2515 national average of 1.5%. This cover increased by between 21.9 and 32.3% in five of the six catchments
 2516 between 2008 and 2023 despite ongoing control efforts. The exception was the relatively small
 2517 Swartkops catchment, where the estimated invaded area decreased by 18.9%. Kotzé et al. (2025) also
 2518 reported changes in invasive plant cover between 2008 and 2023 at the level of terrestrial biomes.

2519 The most heavily invaded biome was the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, where 11% of the remaining
2520 natural vegetation was invaded by alien plants. This was followed by the Fynbos, Albany Thicket and
2521 Grassland biomes with 5.2, 2.8 and 2.5% cover of invasive taxa respectively. For the remaining biomes,
2522 cover was 1.1 % or less. The invaded area almost doubled in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt (78.8%)
2523 between the two surveys and there were also substantial increases in the Forest, Nama Karoo and
2524 Fynbos biomes (36, 23 and 20% respectively). On the other hand, the cover decreased in the Desert,
2525 Succulent Karoo and Albany Thicket biomes by 34, 18 and 12 % respectively.

2526 Holmes et al. (2020) reported that ecosystem recovery after clearing invasive plants in fynbos
2527 vegetation was possible under certain circumstances if thresholds (e.g., with respect to the density or
2528 duration of invasion) had not been crossed. In contrast, Baard et al. (2023) reported good autogenic
2529 recovery after several decades of pine afforestation following removal of the trees and burning of the
2530 site. Baard et al. (2023) concluded that the restoration potential of the montane grassy fynbos in the
2531 study area was superior to that previously documented in montane proteoid fynbos.

2532 Retief et al. (2024) reported successful restoration of sand fynbos vegetation after the removal of alien
2533 grasses, which was achieved by a combination of topsoil translocation, burning, sowing of seeds and
2534 transplantation of plants. This led to plant species richness resembling near-pristine plots. It was noted
2535 that the technique was potentially expensive and therefore probably only suited to use in small urban
2536 nature reserves.

2537 Ruwanza (2024) used repeat surveys in 2019 and 2022 to examine vegetation and soil recovery after
2538 removal of invasive *Eucalyptus grandis* (saligna gum) trees from savanna vegetation. Trees were either
2539 felled and removed, or felled, stacked and burned. The study found some vegetation and soil
2540 improvements between 2019 and 2022 in both the fell-and-removal and fell-and-stackburn cleared
2541 treatments and concluded that there was a positive vegetation and soil recovery trajectory towards
2542 the condition in uninvaded control plots.

2543 Romain and Ngwenya (2025) reported on the use of biomass from alien plant clearing projects. The
2544 intent of these projects is to generate income from a resource that would otherwise go to waste, to
2545 offset the costs of control, and in so doing provide additional opportunities for employment. Their
2546 report concluded however that the use of biomass from alien plant clearing programs involved, "*a*
2547 *complex governance of supply chains, without coordination with alien clearing programs, a diversity*
2548 *of models, and mixed reports about the fluidity of interactions with landowners*". There is also evidence
2549 from Kenya that a deliberate attempt to control the spread of *Neltuma* (formerly *Prosopis*) trees from
2550 Kenya failed to achieve this aim (Ng et al. 2017; Mbaabu et al. 2019). These studies therefore do not
2551 provide any evidence that the use of biomass from control interventions has (i) slowed or reversed

2552 the spread of invasive species; (ii) generated a surplus; and (iii) even if a surplus was generated, it is
2553 not known whether the surplus is re-invested into control efforts.

2554 The use of herbicides has led to some counterproductive outcomes. The DFFE was found to have been
2555 grossly negligent after its WfW employed unqualified contractors who used a toxic herbicide to clear
2556 alien vegetation. The North Gauteng High Court ruled that the DFFE was responsible for the
2557 contamination of dams on farms in the Alma district in Limpopo. In the ruling, the court found that,
2558 “...the plaintiffs suffered damage as a consequence of wrongful action...” and that “...the persistent
2559 nature of picloram toxicity implies that ... they may continue to suffer damage for an undefined period
2560 into the future.”. The court concluded that, “the Defendant is liable for the Plaintiff’s damages, both
2561 past and future”. The amount of compensation will be determined in a separate trial. Such cases
2562 should be reported where the treatments delivered counter-productive outcomes. [the DFFE has been
2563 approached to provide information on other such cases, should they exist]

2564 **4.10. High-level indicator: 4. Level of success in managing invasions**

2565 The level of success in managing invasions is ineffective. Extensive regulations are in place to prevent
2566 the entry of new species and to manage those that are here, but the capacity to fund management
2567 and ensure compliance with the regulations falls well below what is needed. Research studies have
2568 typically reported failures to contain invasions when assessed at wider scales. For half of the known
2569 pathways of introduction there is either no management, or management is ineffective or could not
2570 be estimated. Control efforts have not managed to stem the spread of invasive plants at a national
2571 scale, other than for some of those under biological control.

2572 **4.11. Trends in interventions since 2014**

2573 [work in progress]

2574

2575 **Box 4.1 South Africa’s approach to biosecurity**

2576 Biosecurity actions taken by South Africa’s government have historically been sector-specific, for
2577 example, the DFFE worked to prevent the introduction of environmental threats, while the DoA
2578 worked to prevent the introduction of agricultural pests. This approach has been the norm globally
2579 and was shaped by sector-specific international agreements and their standards and guidelines.
2580 However, given the issues, processes, and solutions are often the same across sectors there has
2581 been a growing call for a more integrated ‘One Biosecurity’ approach (Hulme 2020). In South Africa,
2582 biosecurity functions related to agriculture, the environment, and Port Health, amongst others, have
2583 over recent years been transferred to the Border Management Authority (BMA), which officially
2584 commenced operations on 1 April 2023 (Box Figure 4.1). Having these biosecurity functions under a
2585 single command enables closer working relations, sharing of information, and the integration of
2586 planning and execution of activities. For example, training occurs across the specialities, and all
2587 specialities now benefit from risk-based information, allowing for a move away from random
2588 selection for inspections.

2589 Several industry specific organisations are heavily involved in South Africa’s biosecurity system. For
2590 example, Citrus Research International (CRI) is the mandated research and technical service provider
2591 to the southern African citrus industry. As part of this work, CRI identifies priority biosecurity threats,
2592 conducts pest risk assessments, develops rapid response action plans for these threats, designs and
2593 implements early warning detection surveillance, and increases awareness. CRI surveillance activities
2594 include coverage of the most likely incursion routes. For example, the surveillance programme for
2595 *Diaphorina citri* (Asian citrus psyllid), the vector of Huanglongbing disease of citrus, operates in
2596 South Africa and neighbouring countries. CRI does this work in collaboration with the DoA, including
2597 through pest specific steering committees – a good example of biosecurity public-private
2598 partnerships. Similarly, Hortgro is an organisation that represents South Africa’s deciduous fruit
2599 industry. At Hortgro, the Crop Protection and the Trade and Markets teams are responsible for
2600 identifying biosecurity threats, coordinating surveillance, sharing knowledge with growers,
2601 promoting awareness, and developing management plans for threats to the industry. In 2022
2602 *Drosophila suzukii* (spotted-wing drosophila) was detected in South Africa for the first time based on
2603 a low-level surveillance project funded by Hortgro (in collaboration with Insect Science). In response
2604 to this detection, a multi-industry trapping network for this pest was set up across South Africa and
2605 the Monitoring Centre of Excellence at FruitFly Africa was established. The Monitoring Centre
2606 coordinates the monitoring and surveillance for *D. suzukii* and *Euwallacea fornicatus* (polyphagous

2607 shot-hole borer), but also assists in identifying other high risk pests such as *Bactocera zonata* (peach
2608 fruit fly) for which surveillance may be required.

2609 Another biosecurity initiative established in 2016 uses botanical gardens and arboreta as sentinel
2610 sites for tree health monitoring. The project—a collaboration between SANBI and the Forestry and
2611 Agriculture Biotechnology Institute (FABI)— aims to improve surveillance and identification of tree
2612 pests and provide training in biosecurity best practices. The project has played a key role in detecting
2613 new invasive species [e.g., *Euwallacea fornicatus* (polyphagous shot borer) in 2017 (Paap et al.
2614 2018)]; and identifying species that pose an increasing threat [e.g., *Dematophora necatrix* (white
2615 root rot fungus) recorded on native trees for the first time in surveys undertaken in 2022/2023
2616 (Balocchi et al. 2025)].

2617 **Box Figure 4.1.** *Eriocheir sinensis* (Chinese mitten crab) intercepted by the BMA at OR Tambo International
2618 Airport – Takalani Shakudyiwa.
2619

2620 **Box 4.2 Local and volunteer groups involved in invasive plant clearing**

2621 Many alien plant control projects are carried out by volunteer groups. The overall contribution of
2622 these groups to South Africa’s response to biological invasions is yet to be fully quantified, but the
2623 evidence is that the contribution is significant. Jubase et al. (2021) identified 52 volunteer groups and
2624 estimated that they cleared nearly 5 300 ha of land per year with estimated labour contributions of
2625 ZAR 5.1 million. The non-profit organisation Wild Restoration (www.wildrestoration.org) is incubating
2626 an action and learning network for local and volunteer groups and community organisations involved
2627 in invasive clearing within the Cape Floristic Region. The network’s goals include mapping and
2628 estimating the impact of these groups and sharing information and practices. Wild Restoration has
2629 identified and recruited 100 groups that focus on the greater CFR into its network. It is likely that there
2630 are many more groups active across the region and South Africa more widely.

2631 Volunteer groups include: informal hack groups; ‘Friends of’ and honorary rangers groups supporting
2632 nature reserves, river systems, and parks; outdoor sports clubs; student eco-clubs; the Botanical
2633 Society of South Africa; citizen science groups; residents and ratepayer’s associations; conservancies
2634 and private landowners; conservation societies; and specialist clearing non-profit groups. These
2635 groups conduct both initial clearing and follow-up in urban and rural areas, with a focus on the
2636 dominant invasive plant species in each area. Most use hand pulling and hand tools such as saws,
2637 loppers, and poppers, as well as chainsaws and battery-operated saws. Herbicides are frequently used
2638 to prevent resprouting. They operate on municipal and private land as well as in protected areas. Some
2639 work independently while others have collaborative arrangements with agencies such as South
2640 African National Parks, provincial conservation agencies, or municipalities. Most groups are motivated
2641 by protecting biodiversity in their local areas. As they are typically active over a long time in the same
2642 area, they are also well-placed and motivated to follow up and track ecosystem recovery.

2643 Some clearing groups have been operating consistently for more than three generations, and others
2644 have formed more recently. The groups range from small clearing teams of 3 people that operate once
2645 a month to teams of 60 volunteers with weekly outings, and organisations with multiple paid crews
2646 clearing 5 days a week. Not all are currently able to track activity and impact consistently, but Wild
2647 Restoration estimated that over 900 people were involved regularly in 2024, contributing over 20,000
2648 volunteer hours, around 300,000 paid work hours, and clearing over 8,500 hectares.

2649 Although a handful of groups secure some public sector funding for clearing activities (notably via
2650 LandCare), the majority are self-funded, with some limited support and in-kind contributions. These
2651 sources include local public donations, grants and philanthropic funding, member fees, auctions and
2652 fundraising events, ringfenced property levies, and improvement district budgets.

2653 A notable project is the 'Helihack Initiative' which is a specialist non-profit organisation that uses
2654 helicopters to reach invasive trees in inaccessible areas where they are felled by volunteers that have
2655 mountain climbing or tree felling experience. They are primarily funded by private foundations, and
2656 partner with local organisations and communities in some of their locations. Cape Nature and the
2657 Helihack Initiative recently signed an agreement to clear in inaccessible parts of protected areas.

2658 If biological invasions are to be addressed by a whole of society approach (particularly considering
2659 declines in central government funding), it will be important to ensure the contributions of such
2660 groups are recognised and appropriately supported.

2661 **Box Figure 4.2.** A sign erected to recognise the contributions of the late Edward Silberbauer who led a volunteer
2662 group that has removed invasive plants from the area in the background over several decades. This group is still
2663 very active in the Overberg region of the Western Cape.
2664
2665

2666 5. Monitoring Framework

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2670

2671 5.1. Overview and key findings

2672 The aim of this chapter is to highlight the monitoring that is currently on-going and what is required
2673 to better understand and manage biological invasions in South Africa. The different types of
2674 information currently available on biological invasions in South Africa are reviewed, noting the
2675 strengths and weaknesses of the various approaches to collect data (Section 5.2). Next, based on the
2676 theory of change approach, a proposed framework is presented that codifies interventions (Section
2677 5.3). The desired invasion-specific outcomes are specified and, from this starting point, the necessary
2678 outputs and inputs are identified. For a theory of change approach to be effective, however, it is
2679 essential that progress is monitored. The current system of interventions is reviewed and discussed,
2680 and information available and needed is summarised (Section 5.4). Options to mobilise monitoring
2681 data so such information is available to decision makers is then discussed (Section 5.5). The chapter
2682 closes with an evaluation of integrated governance in South Africa, i.e., how different organisations
2683 work or do not work together across scales and disciplines (Section 5.6).

2684 The key findings and gaps are:

- 2685 ● Significant resources have been invested to determine where invasive species are, but these
2686 efforts are not well co-ordinated. A systematic review of the information content of databases
2687 on South African alien taxa would facilitate the prioritisation of monitoring.
- 2688 ● South Africa has a sophisticated range of processes to address biological invasions. Integrating
2689 these processes and databases, and making them transparent, would result in significant gains
2690 in efficiency and understanding.
- 2691 ● The development of workflows to ensure data are mobilised would facilitate the prioritisation
2692 of future monitoring efforts; similarly, there are important gaps in the flow of information that
2693 if filled would allow for interventions to be evaluated.
- 2694 ● A theory of change approach would help to codify what additional monitoring is needed to
2695 determine the effectiveness of interventions. Specifically, a focus on invasion-specific
2696 outcomes and broader outcomes would assist with planning and reviewing interventions.

- 2697 ● There are currently few effective mechanisms for integrated governance of biological
2698 invasions [across scales (including neighbouring countries) and disciplines], noting the draft
2699 national strategy on biological invasions promises to address this.

2700 **5.2. Different types of survey data and existing sources in South Africa**

2701 Various data are collected on alien taxa in South Africa. These data vary in their type, in the methods
2702 followed for their collection, in their quality and scope, and in the extent to which they follow the FAIR
2703 data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). There are several datasets with
2704 occurrence records of alien taxa collected through structured surveys. These include projects where
2705 standardised, repeated sampling is done to determine spatio-temporal trends (e.g., Kalwij et al. 2015),
2706 and once-off surveys of areas to estimate distribution and abundance (e.g., Cheney et al. 2018). These
2707 datasets can provide high quality data that can be used to estimate status and track trends, but are
2708 generally set up to answer specific research questions, cover small parts of the country (e.g., a part of
2709 a protected area), and the data are often not widely available. The last review of South African lists of
2710 alien taxa and their information content was over a decade ago (Faulkner et al. 2015; see also
2711 Robertson et al. 2010 for a discussion on atlas data with South African examples). The following is a
2712 brief review of the situation, noting that an updated and systematic review of data sources would
2713 facilitate the prioritisation of monitoring efforts.

2714 Several, long-term national or regional atlas projects exist, with these projects either including data
2715 on alien species [e.g., Southern African Bird Atlas Programme 2 (SABAP2;
2716 <https://sabap2.birdmap.africa/>)] or are dedicated to the collection of data on aliens [the Southern
2717 African Plant Invaders Atlas (SAPIA)]. These datasets provide good quality data on the distributions of
2718 species as they follow pre-defined survey methodologies with surveys either performed by experts
2719 (e.g., SAPIA), or with the records undergoing a quality check (e.g., SABAP2). However, these surveys
2720 are not systematically repeated over time and are often spatially biased (Brooks et al. 2022). Survey
2721 effort data for SABAP2 and SAPIA are available, and notably there are some examples of sub-projects
2722 where surveys are systematically repeated [e.g., SABAP2's Hessequa systematic atlassing Subproject;
2723 see van Rooyen (2018), and van Rooyen and Underhill (2020)]. However, these projects vary in how
2724 and when data are made available. For example, SABAP2 data are uploaded every two weeks to the
2725 Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) (Brooks and Ryan 2023), but are also made available
2726 through the website for the project (<https://sabap2.birdmap.africa/>) and using the R package rabm
2727 (<https://github.com/davidclarence/rabm>). In contrast, SAPIA data are currently only available on
2728 request.

2729

2730 **Table 5.1** Different atlas projects in South Africa

Name	Focus	Sampling strategy	Duration	Status	Reference
Southern African Plant Invaders Atlas	Invasive plants outside of cultivation	Road-side in different areas of the country, additional submission by observers	1974–2021	Finished	Henderson (2007)
Southern African Bird Atlas Programme 2	Birds	BirdMap protocol conducted by citizen scientists	2007–current	On-going	Brooks et al. (2022)
South African National Survey of Arachnida	Arachnida	Standardised surveys in selected areas (mainly in Savanna and Grassland Biomes)	2008–2011	Finished	Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2015)
Southern African Butterfly Conservation Assessment (SABCA/LepiMAP)	Lepidoptera	Citizen science and expert input	2007 - current	On-going	www.lepsoc.africa.org/?p=projects&s=sabca
Atlas of Southern African Freshwater Fishes	Freshwater fishes	Citizen science	2006 - current	Ongoing	Scott et al. (2006)
Frog Atlas of Southern Africa (FrogMAP)	Amphibians	Citizen science	2004 – current	Ongoing	Minter et al. (2004)
Atlas for dragonflies and damselflies in Africa (OdonataMAP)	Odonata	Citizen science	2010	Ongoing	Dijkstra (2016)
Protea Atlas Project	Proteas	Citizen science	1991-2001	Finished	Rebello (1993)

2731

2732 Ad hoc records of alien species are collected through a wide range of initiatives; these include citizen
2733 science platforms like iNaturalist, collections of museum specimens, and barcoding projects. The
2734 digitisation of historical records and mobilisation of these data through platforms such as GBIF have
2735 made large amounts of these data readily available [for example, the Southern African Reptile
2736 Conservation Assessment (Bates et al. 2014) and Freshwater Biodiversity Information System (Dallas
2737 et al. 2022)]. However, these data often contain errors and are biased, and thus the extent to which
2738 the patterns they demonstrate reflect reality is unclear.

2739 An increasing number of studies have shown the potential for remote sensing to contribute to
2740 monitoring biological invasions (cf. Boxes 3.1, 3.2). As for atlas projects, it is important for such
2741 information to feed through to relevant databases and scoring indicators.

2742 Data on alien species can also be collected through initiatives for which such data is not the primary
2743 goal. For example, Google Street View archives have been shown to be a potentially useful tool in
2744 mapping and monitoring spread through historical images, e.g., to assess alien plant population
2745 changes (Adams 2024) and to trace the invasion of *Euwallacea fornicatus* (polyphagous shot hole

2746 borer, PSHB) in Johannesburg (PSHB appears to have been present since at least 2017; Mudede et al.
2747 2025). Similarly, the marine bryozoan *Amathia verticillata* was first recorded in South Africa from
2748 Langebaan Lagoon Marine Protected Area (MPA) in 2023, but images of birds taken in the area and
2749 uploaded to iNaturalist suggest that *A. verticillata* was present in the lagoon since at least 2021
2750 (Ackland et al. 2025).

2751 The various types of data collected have their strengths and limitations, and thus it is important to use
2752 data from a range of sources and techniques. However, actions should be taken to understand and
2753 improve data quality where possible, and, when survey effort data are available, corrections or
2754 estimates that consider survey effort should be derived [e.g., by estimating sample completeness (see
2755 Chao et al. 2020)].

2756 [Note to reader: once completed, a link to the issues identified in Chapter 6: Gaps will be made here]

2757 **5.3. Unified framework for management**

2758 Various frameworks have been developed for biological invasions that have been highly influential or
2759 at least highly cited (Wilson et al. 2020a, b). There are also very useful frameworks for specific
2760 management challenges [e.g., to track progress towards eradication (reviewed by Wilson et al. 2017)].
2761 For example, the invasion curve is an excellent communication tool to demonstrate the relative cost
2762 of interventions at different stages (e.g., Victorian Government 2010). And important guiding
2763 documents exist for the various activities involved in the management of biological invasions (e.g., a
2764 toolkit has been developed to assist countries in meeting Target 6 of the Kunming-Montreal Global
2765 Biodiversity Framework; CBD and IUCN 2024). But despite the conceptual appeal, attempts to map
2766 interventions onto the unified framework of biological invasions of Blackburn et al. (2011) have not
2767 provided useful tools. For example, specifying particular goals for particular invasion stages (e.g.,
2768 Robertson et al. 2020) produces appealing graphics, but in practice there are too many exceptions—
2769 the management context matters. For example, containment can be important for widespread
2770 invasions [e.g., preventing *Phytophthora* spp. from spreading from infested sites through biosecurity
2771 measures (Liew et al. 2023)]; and while eradication is possible for some widespread taxa [e.g.,
2772 smallpox (Fenner et al. 1988)], in other cases (particularly in marine settings) attempting to eradicate
2773 even limited incursions can be too costly and unlikely to succeed (Katsanevakis et al. 2023; IPES, 2024).

2774 One approach to more clearly articulate interventions is that of the theory of change
2775 (<https://www.theoryofchange.org/what-is-theory-of-change/>). The basic idea is that by being explicit
2776 about the goals in terms of impacts on biological invasions (i.e., invasion-specific outcomes), it is easier
2777 to clearly specify the necessary outputs, the activities needed to achieve the outputs, and therefore

2778 the required inputs (see example in Figure 5.1). For each component, indicators are proposed and
2779 assumptions specified (though not shown on Figure 5.1). Aligning the indicators with the indicator
2780 framework used in this report (Figure 0.2) will facilitate reporting [to address this, the indicator
2781 factsheets have been updated to link to the theory of change approach (Appendix 1)]. A theory of
2782 change framework for biological invasion interventions also: 1) separates the inputs and the activities
2783 required to achieve particular outputs; and 2) identifies general societal outcomes that the invasion-
2784 specific goals are feeding into. Importantly, while such an approach can be provided for managing
2785 biological invasions in general, it can also be used to define which interventions are needed rather
2786 than starting with an intervention and working out which goals it might achieve.

2787 To ensure that management is strategic and adaptive, there also needs to be a structured process of
2788 scoping, implementation, and assessment. During the assessment stage, if the activities are not
2789 resulting in the desired outputs, a change might be needed to the inputs. Activities can either be
2790 continued or revised, new activities proposed, and, if little progress is being made, it might be
2791 appropriate to develop more realistic outputs and outcomes. See Strydom et al. (2023) for an
2792 example of applying strategic adaptive management principles to the use of fire to reduce woody
2793 plant encroachment.

2794 The theory of change thus provides a framework for identifying necessary and sufficient interventions
2795 and what needs to be done to monitor progress. The approach has potential to inform the structure
2796 and implementation of planning at different scales, e.g., South Africa's national strategy on biological
2797 invasions; objectives and actions for private land-owners; and pathway action plans for state entities.

2798

2799

2800 **Figure 5.1** An example of the theory of change approach applied to the goal of eradicating *Acacia paradoxa* from South Africa. *Acacia paradoxa* is only known from the
 2801 northern slopes of Table Mountain in Cape Town. An attempt at eradication began in 2007 (Zenni et al. 2009; Moore et al. 2011) and is on-going. The plan is to ensure annual
 2802 search-and-destroy surveys are conducted every year in flowering season (i.e., before seed-set so reproduction can be prevented but while flowers are present to increase
 2803 detectability). The starting point is the invasion-specific outcome from which the other components are created. Progress is intended to be evaluated annually with the
 2804 management plan adapted depending on the situation (e.g., any fire in the area should trigger intense control operation in the following year as fire will stimulate the
 2805 germination of soil-stored seed-banks). The numbered indicators are from the indicator framework used in this report (Figure 0.1).

2806 **5.4. Monitoring effectiveness of interventions**

2807 The lack of monitoring of the effectiveness of interventions to address biological invasions has been
2808 highlighted as a significant gap in all reports to date. In South Africa, management effectiveness is
2809 rarely, if ever, monitored (cf. Chapter 4). A process is needed to ensure infield observations of what
2810 works feeds through into best practice guidelines and facilitates adaptive management. The collection
2811 of essential data is critical to enable progress to be tracked. Crucially this cannot happen if monitoring
2812 is not appreciated and funded as an essential part of control operations. This report is mandated to
2813 address very specific elements by the A&IS Regulations (See Section 0.1.2), but the overall system is
2814 much broader, and information is collected of many different types. To score the overall indicator '4.
2815 *Level of success in managing invasions*', the overall system needs to be understood and the
2816 corresponding information available. This is unpacked here by exploring different components of the
2817 system in series of flow diagrams (Figure 5.2), with the resulting information available and needed
2818 summarised (Table 5.3).

2819

2820 **Figure 5.2** Flow diagrams (A–J) outlining interventions to address biological invasions. The diagrams are idealised
 2821 and simplified. Links to greater detail are provided if available, with the resulting information requirements and
 2822 outputs highlight in italics in the figure legends and shown in Table 5.3. Inputs are the starting points for these
 2823 diagrams and end points are concluding decisions or declarations. The diagrams can, in some cases, flow into
 2824 each other, but each diagram is intended to be read on its own. Please note these diagrams are interpretations
 2825 of the situation and have no legal basis.

2826

2827 **Figure 5.2 [Cont.] A** At-border inspections to identify environmental threats. The process for BMA enforcement
 2828 has not been codified here, for the process of enforcement used by DFFE that may share some similar features
 2829 see Fig. 5J. The process requires access to the *Permit database* (to cross-check import permits) as well as a *List*
 2830 *of alien taxa that do not require a risk analysis for importation*. The process should add to the *Database of at-*
 2831 *border biosecurity interceptions* and potentially the *List of alien taxa in South Africa* and the *Prosecution*
 2832 *database*.

2833

2834

2835 **Figure 5.2 [Cont.] B** The at-border biosecurity process for evaluating plant products for the risk of contaminants
 2836 [adapted from Saccaggi et al. (2021)]. The process requires access to and should add to the *Interceptions on*
 2837 *plant product imports* (noting there is a separate process for additions to the *Database of at-border biosecurity*
 2838 *interceptions*). Interceptions of contaminants of plant products are not currently added to the *List of alien taxa*
 2839 *in South Africa* as the interception of a taxa at-border does not imply that live individuals or propagules of the
 2840 taxon are found post-border; though they clearly represent an important part of the invasion debt.

2841

2842 **Figure 5.2 [Cont.] C** The process to deal with new incursions. The intention is for a new report to always be
 2843 published, this might happen at different points in this flow diagram, and a publication might actually be the
 2844 new report itself. Updated from Wilson et al. (2013). The process requires access to and should add to the *List*
 2845 *of alien taxa in South Africa* and may add to the *SUSPECT list* and potentially the *NEM:BA A&IS Lists* (in the case
 2846 of emergency listings).

2847

2848 **Figure 5.2 [Cont.] D)** The process for listing tax under the A&S Regulations. There are a few additional
 2849 processes not shown here for simplicity, e.g., direct loops between DFFE and SANBI in terms of evaluating risk
 2850 analyses. ASRARP is the Alien Species Risk Analysis Review Panel; RAAT is the Risk Analysis for Alien Taxa
 2851 framework; and RARC is the Risk Analysis Review Committee. For full details of these processes see
 2852 Supplementary material 1 of Wilson and Kumschick (2024). The process requires access to and may result in
 2853 changes to the *List of alien taxa in South Africa*, the *List of taxa subjected to a risk analysis*, the *SUSPECT list*, and
 2854 the *NEM:BA A&S Lists*

2855

2856 **Figure 5.2 [Cont.] E)** The process to import an alien taxon. See legend to panel D for acronyms, and
 2857 Supplementary material 1 of Wilson and Kumschick (2024) for full details of these processes. The process
 2858 requires access to the *List of alien taxa that do not require a risk analysis for importation*. The process may add
 2859 to the *List of alien taxa in South Africa* and the *NEM:BA A&S Lists* as well as the *List of taxa subjected to a risk*
 2860 *analysis*. The process will add to the *Permit database*.

2861

2862 **Figure 5.2 [Cont.] F** The process to import and release a classical biological control agent (adapted from Ivey et al. 2021). NBCRACR: National Biological Control Release Application Review Committee; DoA is the Department of Agriculture. The decision by the biocontroller might be to not submit a report on risk for formal consideration (as the host specificity testing conclusively demonstrates an unacceptable risk). Nonetheless the project should still be written up and recorded both for posterity and for international collaborators. The process should add to the *Biological control agents and their statuses* and the *List of alien taxa in South Africa*. Note the permit issues here are not currently incorporated into the *Permit database* mentioned in Table 5.3.

2869

2870 **Figure 5.2 [Cont.] G** Applications for permits to conduct activities on taxa listed under the A&IS Regulations. The relevant part of the DFFE is the Issuing Authority / Permits Office. As part of assessing the validity of a permit there may need to be consultation with the provinces and an inspection of facilities (pre-permit inspections). On issuing a permit the information is captured in the permit database and sent to the DFFE Biosecurity Compliance. The process requires access to the *NEM:BA A&IS Lists* and will result in additions to the *Permit database*.

2875

2876 **Figure 5.2 [Cont.] H)** The development and implementation of management plans for species. The process
 2877 requires access to the *NEM:BA A&IS Lists* and will add to the *Database of species-specific management plans*.
 2878 The entities that coordinate implementation were historical called ‘Implementing Agents’ but the term ‘Service
 2879 Provider’ is now preferred; service providers include a wide range of governmental and non-governmental
 2880 institutions.

2881

2882

2883 **Figure 5.2 [Cont.] I)** The development and implementation of management plans for sites. The process requires
 2884 access to the *List of organs of state that require site-based control plans* and will add to or update the *Database*
 2885 *of site-based control plans*. The process will also produce *Report on progress with the implementation of control*
 2886 *plans*.

2887

2888 **Figure 5.2 [Cont.] J** inspections to assess compliance with the A&IS Regulations. Inspection workflows and the
 2889 following enforcement workflow can only end with compliance, noting decisions on compliance are made by
 2890 the DFFE Compliance, the DFFE Enforcement, the National Prosecuting Authority (NPA), and the courts. When a
 2891 complaint is received it is loaded onto the Environmental Crimes Electronic Case Management System (ECAS),
 2892 only a part of this is relevant to biological invasions. Complaints should be made via the environmental crimes
 2893 hot-line [or can be directed to an Environmental Management Inspector (EMI) of a relevant environmental
 2894 management entity (though this may delay the process as the official will then be required to refer the matter
 2895 for uploading on ECAS)]. The process of deciding on the level of non-compliance needs to be codified.
 2896 Environmental Management Inspectors deal directly with the regulated community and have the power to issue
 2897 lawful instructions. The process requires access to the *Sites that require inspection* and will result in additions to
 2898 the *Inspection database* and *Electronic case (ECAS) management system*.

2899

2900 **Figure 5.2 [Cont.] K** Enforcement activities regarding the A&IS Regulations. The initial processes can be run by
 2901 any of the EMI entities²⁴, noting that the responsibility to inspect permits for compliance resides with the permit
 2902 issuing authority; for the A&IS Lists that is DFFE (as shown here). Once a case docket has been opened the
 2903 process is handed over to the NPA (the National Prosecuting Authority) and potentially the courts. In emergency
 2904 situations the issuing of a pre-directive might not be appropriate, but in doing so it should be clear why corrective
 2905 measures could not be put in place (with the decision potentially challenged in court). The process requires
 2906 access to the *Electronic case (ECAS) management system* will add to the *Prosecution database*.

²⁴The DFFE, the Department of Water and Sanitation (DWS), the Department of Mineral Resources and Energy (DMRE), Provincial environmental departments, some local municipalities, and specific organs of state including Ezemvelo KZN Wildlife, Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Agency (MTPA), Cape Nature, Eastern Cape Parks & Tourism Agency (ECPTA), iSimangaliso, and SANParks.

2907 **Table 5.3** Information sources that facilitate or are needed to facilitate how biological invasions are addressed in South Africa under national regulations (cf. Figure 5.2).
 2908 While these information sources are necessary to score the indicator: '4. *Level of success in managing invasions*' several other sources of information are also required
 2909 (particularly regarding pathways). Several of these information sources do not currently exist, but are implied that they should exist based on the workflows or are needed
 2910 for decisions to be made (Figure 5.2). The order of rows in the table reflects the order in which documents are mentioned in the legends to Figure 5.2.

Information	Description	Status	Issues	Relevant indicators	Links and references
<i>Database of at-border biosecurity interceptions</i>	A list of at-border interceptions	Does not currently exist	Identification can be challenging	4.7. <i>Effectiveness of pathway treatments</i>	None
<i>Interceptions on plant product imports</i>	Information on imported plant products inspected by DoA laboratories between 1994 and 2019 and the contaminant organisms found on them	Database 1994–2019 published	No workflow to update published publicly available data base	4.7. <i>Effectiveness of pathway treatments</i>	(Saccaggi et al. 2021)
<i>List of alien taxa in South Africa</i>	A list of taxa for which there is evidence that they are present in and alien to South Africa The list includes some other taxa as it is required to by the A& IS Regulations (cf. Section 0.1.2). If a taxon is recorded as absent on this list, then it is likely a permit will be required to import it (noting this list has no formal legal status)	List has been created	Many sources not yet incorporated, particularly taxa in cultivation	2.1. <i>Number and status of alien species</i> [and many others in the ancillary data]	Appendix 6 (Fernández Winzer et al. 2025b; Zengeya et al. 2025, in press)

Information	Description	Status	Issues	Relevant indicators	Links and references
<i>List of alien taxa that do not require a risk analysis for importation</i>	<p>This has been described as a list of taxa that are legally in the country</p> <p>The purpose is to determine whether an import permit is required under A&IS Regulation 16. As per clause 16.4, alien taxa which were introduced to South Africa prior to 30 March 2016 need less detail for an import permit to be issued</p>	<p>No such list exists</p> <p>Decisions on the requirement for an import permit have, to date, been made on a case-by-case basis</p>	<p>Permits may also be required at the provincial level to introduce an alien taxon</p> <p>Historical data on imports and permits are not curated, mostly not digitised, and stored in several places (e.g., in provincial offices)</p> <p>Listing might be at species level but import at subspecific level</p> <p>There are no guidelines on what is necessary and sufficient evidence that a taxon has been legally introduced</p>	<p>1. <i>Rate of unregulated introduction of new species</i></p> <p>4.1. <i>Quality of regulatory framework</i></p>	<p>For discussion of the need for such a list see Wilson and Kumschick (2024)</p>
<i>SUSPECT list</i>	<p>A list of unregulated alien taxa that have been recorded as present in South Africa for which there is concern that a harmful invasion might occur (or be occurring)</p> <p>This list has no legislative status. The intention is that taxon are moved off the SUSPECT list following the completion of a risk analysis, and so a decision can be made to either regulate or not</p>	<p>No current valid version: under redevelopment</p>	<p>Need to finalise a process to add taxon to the SUSPECT list and set a goal and processes so no taxon is on the SUSPECT list for longer than 10 years</p>	<p>4.1. <i>Quality of regulatory framework</i></p>	<p>For previous process see Wilson et al. (2013)</p>

Information	Description	Status	Issues	Relevant indicators	Links and references
<i>NEM:BA A&IS Lists</i>	Regulatory lists	560 taxa listed	<p>Last update came into effect in March 2021</p> <p>The nomenclature of several of the taxa are outdated</p> <p>Regulatory lists are not tidy</p> <p>Currently no prohibited list</p>	4.1. <i>Quality of regulatory framework</i>	(Wilson 2025; Wilson and Kumschick 2024)
<i>List of taxa subjected to a risk analysis</i>	A list of risk analyses completed for taxa alien to South Africa in support of the A&IS Regulations. Each risk analysis is an evaluation of the likelihood and consequence of an alien taxon becoming invasive in South Africa with a recommendation for regulation in the context of the available options to effectively manage risk whilst retaining any benefits. Risk analyses are produced as per the Risk Analysis for Alien Taxa (RAAT) framework. They result in a recommendation for listing (or not listing). The intention is for all taxa listed under the A&IS Regulations to have a risk analysis conducted on them	<p>As of the end of 2025, 148 (26%) of taxa listed under the A&IS Regulations have a risk analysis. ~40 of these risk analyses have been considered by the RARC.</p> <p>None of these have been published</p> <p>The RAAT framework v1.0 was published in 2017, with the last update (v2.0) published 2025</p>	<p>Risk analyses are not currently in the public domain</p> <p>The process to deal with cases in which the decisions of the RARC does not align with recommendations of ASRARP has not been implemented to date</p> <p>As the regulatory lists were created before the development of the RAAT framework, most listed taxa still do not have a risk analysis</p>	4.1. <i>Quality of regulatory framework</i>	<p>Table S4.1</p> <p>(Kumschick et al. 2025; Wilson and Kumschick 2024)</p>

Information	Description	Status	Issues	Relevant indicators	Links and references
<i>Biological control agents and their statuses</i>	Which biological control agents have been considered and tested against which targets There are separate databases for biocontrol agents targeting plants and invertebrates	Much of the information is incorporated into the list of alien taxa (Appendix 6) though there are delays in data being copied across	Some agents have not been formally described so do not have a scientific name	1.2. <i>Introduction rates</i> 2.1. <i>Number and status of alien species</i> 4.8. <i>Effectiveness of species treatments</i>	Targeting plants: Zachariades (2021) Targeting invertebrates: Pretorius (2008)
<i>Permit database</i>	A list of permits that have been issued by DFFE to allow permit holders to conduct otherwise prohibited activities with taxa listed under the A&IS Regulations. This forms the basis for determining inspection activities to evaluate compliance with permits. The database also includes information on permits which have been applied for but denied and the reasons for the permit not being issued	As of the end of December 2022, 2906 permits have been issued for 267 valid taxa A tidy version of the permit database with each row being a specific permit for a specific taxon is in the public domain as part of this report cycle [information was provided by the DFFE, but these data are still to be processed and the file updated to the end Dec 2025]	It is not currently clear whether the provisions for any specific permit is being used (e.g., whether a taxon has been imported) The number of instances where a permit is required but has not been issued or applied for has not been estimated A process is needed to prioritise which permits should be inspected	1.2. <i>Introduction rates</i> 4.1. <i>Quality of regulatory framework</i> with insights to 4.8. <i>Effectiveness of species treatments</i>	Section 4.1.4 Appendix 9 (SANBI 2023)
<i>Database of species-specific management plans</i>	This database includes details of the plans and their evaluation	No species-specific management plans have been approved	If plans were approved, a process of regular updates and reporting on progress would also be needed	4.3. <i>Planning coverage (for species)</i>	None

Information	Description	Status	Issues	Relevant indicators	Links and references
<i>List of organs of state that require site-based control plans</i>	All organs of state must compile a site-based control plan addressing biological invasions This list would provide an indication of which organs of state require a plan, whether a plan has been developed, and an evaluation of the adequacy of the plan	It is unclear if an official list exists	It is unclear at which scale plans are needed	4.3. <i>Planning coverage</i> (for sites)	None
<i>Database of site-based control plans</i>	This database includes details of the plans	Database currently held by DFFE	Area covered by plan, and start and end dates not included in the database	4.3. <i>Planning coverage</i> (for sites)	None
<i>Report on progress with the implementation of control plans</i>	Reports on the efficacy of control and eradication measures in line with indicators in the plans	Not currently incorporated into this report	The inclusion of a standard set of indicators is needed	4.9. <i>Effectiveness of site treatments</i>	None
<i>Sites that require inspection</i>	Sites that should be subject to inspections for alien taxa of concern, to ensure appropriate measures are in place to limit invasions, and that the A&IS Regulations are being adhered to. A list of sites might be developed based on pathway action plans, species-specific management plans, or through identifying sites that have a high likelihood of harbouring alien taxa	There is no structured process for identifying sites	A process is needed to prioritise which sites are inspected	4.6. <i>Sites treated</i> 4.9. <i>Effectiveness of site treatments</i>	None
<i>Inspection database</i>	Information on inspections by the DFFE regarding compliance to the A&IS Regulations, including links to report on inspection visits Note this is separate from at-border inspections	Not currently incorporated into this report A new system to track inspections has been developed and information is to feed into future reports	Historical data were either not captured electronically or were not tidy. Significant work is needed to determine past efforts	4.3. <i>Planning coverage</i> 4.4. <i>Pathways treated</i> 4.6. <i>Sites treated</i>	None

Information	Description	Status	Issues	Relevant indicators	Links and references
<i>Electronic case (ECAS) management system</i>	<p>Information on all complaints received through the environmental crime hotline, inspection and outcome of the matter</p> <p>Information on compliance to selected permits, permit conditions following inspection and subsequent compliance processes</p> <p>Note the ECAS contains information on other environmental issues not just regarding alien taxa</p>	Not currently incorporated into this report	Need to establish protocols to determine which information must be redacted to comply with data protection rules and to respect privacy	<p>4.7. <i>Effectiveness of pathway treatments</i></p> <p>4.8. <i>Effectiveness of species treatments</i></p>	None
<i>Prosecution database</i>	A list of cases that were sent to the National Prosecuting Authority (NPA) with the current status of the case and the outcome as appropriate (acquittal, settle out of court, conviction, do not prosecute)	Awaiting feedback from the DFFE, noting provincial environmental departments will also need to be approached as they can and have instituted prosecutions independently of the DFFE	Inclusion of on-going cases might not be possible	4.1. <i>Quality of regulatory framework</i>	None

2911

2912 **5.5. Mobilising monitoring data**

2913 Monitoring data can inform indicators to track trends for national and international reporting, but the
2914 process is not always straightforward. An integration of data from different sources and techniques is
2915 important to ensure a wide coverage of monitoring data over time, for different taxa, noting that there
2916 is often a lag from when data are collected to when they are made accessible to inform indicators on
2917 biodiversity status and change. It is important for data to feed through to local and global databases
2918 to facilitate the mobilisation of monitoring data and to inform indicators as required, while accounting
2919 for sampling bias, uncertainty in the data, and including data quality filters. For example, data on alien
2920 species introductions need to be regularly updated to inform the indicator '*Introduction rates*' as
2921 required for the reporting on the status of biological invasions in South Africa and to calculate related
2922 indicators to measure progress towards meeting Target 6 of the Global Biodiversity Framework (CBD
2923 2022), however, there are often significant delays (Section 1.5). Regularly updated data from atlas
2924 projects or distribution surveys are also needed to inform the indicator '*Extent of alien species*'.

2925 The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF; <https://www.gbif.org>) has over 3 billion
2926 occurrence records from different sources, including data from peer-reviewed publications and
2927 citizen scientists, providing an invaluable platform for the mobilisation of monitoring data. Data from
2928 GBIF can be accessible on demand in a standardised and reproducible way through services offered
2929 by the Biodiversity Building Blocks for policy (B-Cubed) project— an important step for mobilising
2930 monitoring data in an analysis-ready format (<https://b-cubed.eu>; Groom et al. 2025) Ensuring that all
2931 monitoring data feed through to local databases and are integrated into GBIF data on a regular basis
2932 will be crucial for such data to be effectively mobilised, and for trends to be tracked.

2933 It is widely recognised that raw biodiversity observations often need careful interpretation for them
2934 to be useful for policy makers. Specifically models and corrections are often necessary to convert data
2935 into variables and ultimately into information in the form of indicators (Jetz et al. 2019). This report
2936 largely reports collated biodiversity observations. The next step will be to provide useful
2937 extrapolations or predictions from these. For example, sampling effort must be considered if the
2938 indicator '*1. Rate of unregulated introduction of new species*' is to inform reporting to Target 6 via the
2939 indicator '*Rate of invasive alien species establishment*' (Section S5.1; McGeoch et al. 2023). Survey
2940 effort can also be considered get predicted estimates for '*3.1 Alien species richness*' (Chao et al. 2020).
2941 Moreover, "*a globally coordinated approach is needed for biodiversity monitoring*" (Schmeller et al.
2942 2015), this need for integration is discussion in the next section.

2943 **5.6. Integrated governance across sectors and scales**

2944 The need for integrated governance was the key recommendation of the IPBES IAS Assessment to
2945 improve how biological invasions are managed globally (IPBES, 2023). From the IPBES IAS Assessment
2946 integrated governance requires efforts to:

- 2947 1. Enhance coordination and collaboration across international and regional mechanisms;
- 2948 2. Develop and adopt effective and achievable national implementation strategies;
- 2949 3. Shared efforts and commitments, and understanding of the specific roles of all actors;
- 2950 4. Improve policy coherence;
- 2951 5. Engage broadly across governmental sectors, industry, the scientific community, Indigenous
2952 Peoples and local communities and the wider public;
- 2953 6. Support, fund and mobilize resources for innovation, research and environmentally sound
2954 technology; and
- 2955 7. Support information systems, infrastructures and data sharing.

2956 The proposed strategic actions are enabled when the system-wide properties of governance are:

- 2957 i. Robust
- 2958 ii. Equitable and inclusive
- 2959 iii. Responsive
- 2960 iv. Focused on effective implementation

2961 Insights as to what South Africa is currently doing to address these in the context of the developing
2962 national strategy on biological invasion are discussed in Wilson et al. (2025). A few are highlighted
2963 here.

2964 There are significant gaps in information flow that would be addressed by effective integrated
2965 governance this is in part due to overlaps in legislation. For example, protected areas are required to
2966 produce a management plan under the National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act
2967 57 of 2003. There is no specific requirement that such a plan addresses biological invasions, though
2968 to be effective it would almost certainly have to and Section 76 of the NEM:BA instructs that invasive
2969 species control and eradication must be incorporated into protected area management plans.

2970 Whether having a separate site-based control plan for invasions is necessary is moot, but if a plan is
2971 developed such information should flow through to DFFE for evaluation of the '4.9 *effectiveness of*
2972 *site treatments*'

2973 [Note: to be added a discussion on the role of working groups, volunteer hack groups, international
2974 agreements]

2975 **5.7. Summary of progress to meet GBF Target 6**

2976 The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) was adopted by the CBD in December
2977 2022 with four 4 goals for 2050 and 23 targets for 2030, including target 6 on biological invasions

2978 *Target 6: Reduce the Introduction of Invasive Alien Species by 50% and Minimize Their Impact*
2979 *Eliminate, minimize, reduce and or mitigate the impacts of invasive alien species on biodiversity*
2980 *and ecosystem services by identifying and managing pathways of the introduction of alien species,*
2981 *preventing the introduction and establishment of priority invasive alien species, reducing the rates*
2982 *of introduction and establishment of other known or potential invasive alien species by at least 50*
2983 *per cent, by 2030, eradicating or controlling invasive alien species especially in priority sites, such*
2984 *as islands.*²⁵

2985 In October 2024 as part of the 7th national reports to the CBD²⁶, South Africa reported that the
2986 national target title was:

2987 *By 2030, prevent and reduce the rate of introduction and spread of alien invasive species [sic],*
2988 *manage the pathways and reduce the threat of alien invasive species [sic].*

2989 and that the main policy measures or actions that will be taken to achieve this national target were:

2990 *(1) Pathways responsible for the introduction and spread of (new and/or unregulated) invasive*
2991 *alien species are identified, prioritized, and managed to prevent/reduce the rate of introductions*

2992 *(2) Major negative impacts of priority invasive alien species have been prevented, eliminated,*
2993 *minimized, reduced and/or mitigated*

2994 *(3) Major negative impacts of invasive alien species on priority sites - including, sensitive,*
2995 *protected/pristine areas; are minimized/prevented/reduced to restore, maintain and enhance*
2996 *natures [sic] contributions to the people*

2997 *(4) Implementation of a range of interventions is accelerated through integrated governance at all*
2998 *levels for the management and control of invasive alien species*

2999 Additional financial resources were indicated as necessary or the attainment of this national target
3000 (cf. Section 4.2).

3001 Section S5.1 provides details of how information in this status report can contribute to a summary of
3002 progress to meet GBF Target 6.

3003

²⁵<https://www.cbd.int/gbf/targets/6>

²⁶<https://ort.cbd.int/national-targets/my-country/part-1/AA683CEB-86AA-143D-EC80-4098C4AAB7B1/view>
(accessed 27 Jan 2026)

3004 6. Gaps

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3008 **Process for identifying gaps and key findings**

3009 This chapter evaluates gaps using four approaches: 1) progress in collating information needed for the
3010 indicators used in this report was evaluated and gaps in this process noted (Section 6.1 and Table 6.1);
3011 2) the needs of stakeholders and end users of the report were evaluated through a questionnaire run
3012 in parallel with the external review of this report, with findings evaluated in terms of what is feasible
3013 for the report given different levels of resourcing (Section 6.2); 3) gaps identified in the third report
3014 (SANBI and CIB, 2023) (including gaps in information, management, and governance) were re-
3015 evaluated (Sections 6.3–6.7); and 4) gaps identified in the IPBES IAS Assessment were evaluated in the
3016 South African context (Section 6.8). The chapter concludes with Section 6.9: the way forward. Key
3017 findings are highlighted below:

- 3018 • Processes to identify information are increasingly available but incomplete, with workflows and
3019 protocols to ensure such information is collated and, as appropriate, reported on. This systematic
3020 collation and presentation of data via workflows will facilitate more regular and accurate updates
3021 on the status and management of biological invasions.
- 3022 • Indicators are crucial for interpreting information in a policy- and management-relevant manner.
3023 The indicators developed for this report have been evaluated against fundamental properties of
3024 indicators as part of updating indicators factsheets, and efforts are on-going to align indicators
3025 with national and international reporting processes. Much more is needed to test and refine the
3026 indicators, in particular, by expanding evaluations to explore how indicators are perceived and
3027 communicated so that they incentivise the appropriate behaviour.
- 3028 • There are major gaps in our knowledge on introduction rates, with pathways and dates of
3029 introduction missing for many introduced taxa, particularly plants and fungi. Estimates or useful
3030 proxies of search effort are required for more reliable estimates of rate of introduction and to
3031 report on Target 6 of the GBF.
- 3032 • Data on how invasive species move and are moved around South Africa (and potential methods
3033 to collect and curate such data) are needed if effective strategies to manage the spread of
3034 invasions are to be developed.

- 3035 • Data on the presence, distribution and abundance of alien species need to be systematically
3036 collected, collated, and integrated into national and global databases to facilitate the planning of
3037 interventions.
- 3038 • Information on the impacts of biological invasions needs to be systematically quantified and
3039 collated to facilitate the prioritisation of interventions, provide a defensible rationale to underpin
3040 government investment, and provide background to efforts to communicate the severity of the
3041 issue.
- 3042 • Interventions on biological invasions in South Africa are occurring in the absence of a
3043 comprehensive policy, and a strategy to guide and implement such a policy (noting existing and
3044 new policies only address part of the issue of biological invasions). A national strategy is under
3045 development that has the potential to significant increase the integrated governance, though
3046 other co-ordination structure might also be effective (e.g., on One Biosecurity).
- 3047 • Formal programs that monitor progress towards reducing the negative impacts of invasions
3048 (outputs and outcomes) are not available, but if established would allow for control measures to
3049 be compared and improved.
- 3050 • [Note: the following is a key finding from the previous report, it will be revised based on results of
3051 stakeholder questionnaire]. There has, to date, been no systematic evaluation of how the report
3052 is currently used, what can be done to improve uptake, and how the report can better address
3053 stakeholder needs. Broad stakeholder engagement exercises have been used very effectively in
3054 similar contexts.

3055 **6.1. Progress since the last report in terms of indicators**

3056 For each indicator, the evaluation of the progress made towards getting an accurate reflection of the
3057 actual situation was evaluated by the report authors based on the information contained in each
3058 chapter (Table 6.1).

3059 **Table 6.1** Progress on gathering information required to populate the indicators (cf. Figure 0.2) reported on in this report. Progress is scored as: regression—less information
 3060 is available than previously; none—the information is the same as in previous reports (with appropriate updates as needed); minimal—there has been some more information
 3061 or processes set up, but these are unlikely to be sufficient to affect the scoring of the indicators; moderate—additional information were obtained allowing for some changes
 3062 to be detected or necessitating a revised baseline; substantial—the processes have seen a step change in what information is available and/or the information that could be
 3063 obtained. Results from the previous reports are outlined in full in Table S6.1 as well as an updated evaluation of the consequences if the gap were not filled.

Indicator	Progress 2017–2019	Progress 2020–2022	Progress 2023–2025	Notes on progress 2023–2025
1. <i>Rate of unregulated introduction of new species</i>	minimal	moderate	moderate	A database on historical introductions of bark and ambrosia beetles was recently published, as were data from social media on bird escapes. A workflow to check sources for new introductions and to process these data has been developed (Appendix 2: ' <i>Workflow to check sources for new introductions</i> '). With new indicators being developed for reporting at international levels, there is a greater recognition of the need to separate search effort from observations (Section 0.2.2). This promises to be an area where substantial progress can be made.
1.1 <i>Introduction pathway prominence</i>	moderate	moderate	minimal	Recent research on some pathways of introduction means that our understanding of certain pathways, such as the aquarium trade, has improved significantly. But many pathways of introduction remain poorly studied. The workflow that supports this indicator (Appendix 2: ' <i>Introduction pathway prominence</i> ') was updated and automated where possible.
1.2. <i>Introduction rates</i>	moderate	moderate	moderate	While progress has been made (see indicator 1), there are still significant gaps, e.g., in terms of pathways and dates of introduction.
1.3 <i>Within-country pathway prominence</i>	none	minimal	minimal	There have been insights into a few pathways (e.g., due to research on the pet trade, plant uses), but little is still known about most pathways active within South Africa.
1.4 <i>Within-country dispersal rates</i>	none	moderate	minimal	A database of native-alien populations, including information on pathways, has been constructed. Information is also available for alien plants in South African National Parks. The pathways for other taxa dispersing within the country, however, remain unknown or the available information needs to be collated.
2. <i>Number of invasive species that have 'Major' impacts</i>	minimal	moderate	minimal	Impact assessments have been conducted for only a few alien taxa in South Africa. Complementary assessments using risk analyses and findings from the IPBES IAS Assessment confirm that these species cause widespread harm across multiple sectors of society. The need for more studies and assessments on the impact of invasive species remains a research priority.
2.1. <i>Number and status of alien species</i>	substantial	substantial	substantial	The process to compile the list alien species in South Africa has been substantially improved and documented. The focus for the next phase is to increase the number of data-sources incorporated into the list of alien taxa, and to implement protocol and workflow, e.g., for declaring a taxon alien, present, and assessing its degree of establishment (introduced, established, invasive)

Indicator	Progress 2017–2019	Progress 2020–2022	Progress 2023–2025	Notes on progress 2023–2025
2.2. <i>Extent of alien species</i>	minimal	minimal	minimal	There is limited data on the extent and abundance of alien species in South Africa. Citizen science continues to provide information on the extent of some species while several atlasing and remote sensing projects have provided estimates of the abundance of selected invasive plant taxa in water catchments and terrestrial biomes. There is however no national long-term structured monitoring project to track plant invasions across South Africa
2.3. <i>Abundance of alien species</i>	minimal	none	minimal	
2.4. <i>Impact of alien species</i>	minimal	minimal	minimal	
3. <i>Extent of area that suffers 'Major' impacts from invasions</i>	minimal	minimal	none	No progress made
3.1 <i>Alien species richness</i>	minimal	none	minimal	Significant increases were seen in various provinces and biomes, although without active surveillance this might be an artefact of more records being submitted to the citizen science platforms iNaturalist
3.2 <i>Relative invasive abundance</i>	minimal	none	minimal	At a national level, a 15-year monitoring study has been completed and published, and provides estimates of relative invasive abundance of 14 selected plant taxa in terrestrial biomes and water catchments. There are no reliable estimates for the relative abundance of invasive species at sub-national levels (for example protected areas) due to a lack of structured monitoring programs
3.3 <i>Impact of invasions</i>	minimal	moderate	none	Estimates of the impact of invasions have not been recently revised (section S3.3)
4. <i>Level of success in managing invasions</i>	minimal	none	none	The absence of robust information on pathways, species and sites treated, and the lack of systems to monitor the outcomes of these interventions, means that there has been little progress in clarifying the overall level of success with managing invasions. The report relies heavily on a small number of studies, usually reported in individual research papers (e.g., Kotzé et al. 2025; van Wilgen et al. 2025)
4.1 <i>Quality of regulatory framework</i>	moderate	moderate	minimal	While the implementation of the regulatory framework has been outlined (Figure 5.2); the information needed to evaluate it specified (Table 5.3); and a framework for considering such information developed (Figure 5.1); there have been few improvements in the flow of actual information itself (e.g., on inspections and convictions). By developing the structures, the intention is that future reports will be better placed to collate and evaluate information on the quality of the regulatory framework and how it is being implemented

Indicator	Progress 2017–2019	Progress 2020–2022	Progress 2023–2025	Notes on progress 2023–2025
4.2 <i>Money spent</i>	none	moderate	none	There are several issues that continue to limit the ability to track money spent on the management of biological invasions. Few estimates of money spent are received from organisations. The values that are provided often do not separate expenditures based on money received from government (e.g., the WfW programme) from other sources, nor is money spent on managing biological invasions separated from other activities. In many cases (private landowners and volunteer groups in particular) no records are kept, or inputs are in kind rather than financial. Economic methods would be needed to develop for robust and defensible estimates to be produced.
4.3 <i>Planning coverage</i>	minimal	minimal	minimal	There are no plans for pathways or species. For sites, the DFFE has recently established a database of plans and made a start with approving them. Few such site plans have been approved to date, noting neither the area covered by such plans nor and whether the plans are current is recorded. Such data are essential for estimating planning coverage
4.4 <i>Pathways treated</i>	minimal	minimal	none	Many government departments are involved in the management of pathways though such information is rarely made accessible (cf. Section 6.4). Data inspections for environmental threats continues to be made available despite the change in the entity responsible (was DFFE, now BMA)
4.5 <i>Species treated</i>	minimal	minimal	regression	Information on which species have been managed is incorporated into South Africa's list of alien taxa (Zengeya et al. in press) based on information from government or agricultural control or eradication programs, monitoring of biological control agents, and published studies. However, a major source of information (the Working for Water Management Information System, WIMS) is no longer used
4.6 <i>Sites treated</i>	none	minimal	regression	Information on the extent of site treatments is recorded for a few protected areas and in a few research studies; organisations seldom respond to requests for inputs on the location and extent of areas managed. A major source of recent information on sites managed (the Working for Water Management Information System, WIMS) is no longer used, and so the level of knowledge of sites treated has decreased
4.7 <i>Effectiveness of pathway treatments</i>	minimal	minimal	none	Information on at-border inspections for environmental threats, and the results of those inspections continues to be supplied. Whether these interventions reduce introduction rates is not estimated, and clear information on procedures followed is not available
4.8 <i>Effectiveness of species treatments</i>	none	minimal	none	Information on the effectiveness of species treatments is only routinely collected for a few taxa, specifically plants under biological control, some species that are targets for national eradication, and in some research projects
4.9 <i>Effectiveness of site treatments</i>	minimal	none	minimal	The results of a long-term project aimed at monitoring trends in priority woody species at a national level was recently published, with insights for the effectiveness of treatments across sites (Kotzé et al. 2025). However, given this project has been terminated and so the values will not be updated, the level of knowledge is expected to decrease and be limited to ad hoc research projects (cf. Table S4.4)

3065 **6.2. End user survey**

3066 A stakeholder questionnaire was developed with the aim of identifying topics that should be the focus
3067 of future reports and to identify how the report is used. The questionnaire was sent out on 30 January
3068 2026 with the first phase of the questionnaire closing 1 March 2026 (i.e., the same time period as the
3069 public request to review a draft of this report). See Section S6.2 for further details, and Table S6.2 for
3070 the questions).

3071 [Note: the results of the questionnaire and their implications will be discussed in the final report]

3072 **6.3. Indicators and workflows**

3073 From the last report, the need to link indicators to the Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) was
3074 highlighted, work on this is on-going recognising data limitations (cf. Sections 0.2.2, 1.5, Box 1.1). The
3075 indicator factsheets were updated (Appendix 1), and each indicator evaluated against essential
3076 properties for such indicators (Vicente et al. 2022).

3077 A continuing gap is the disconnect between information that is apparently available and that which is
3078 used in this report to evaluate the status and management of biological invasions in South Africa (e.g.,
3079 Table 6.1). There are various potential reasons for this: the information has not, in fact, been collected;
3080 the information is not stored in a manner that allows for sharing; organisations are unaware of their
3081 obligations to share data; organisations do not realise particular data are relevant; and there might be
3082 a reticence to share data.

3083 To address these issues several strategies have been used or are proposed:

- 3084 • Which data should be collected for required decisions to be made are now, at least in part,
3085 explicitly outlined as part of idealised flow diagrams for some interventions (Figure 5.2);
- 3086 • To encourage inputs, various stakeholder engagements have been held (Section 0.1.5), and a
3087 stakeholder survey has been sent out as part of this report (Section 6.2);
- 3088 • Data translation tables and tidy versions of data sets have been created to ensure data can be
3089 used [e.g., the list of alien taxa (Appendix 6), the metadata associated with the list of alien
3090 taxa (Appendix 8), and the permit database (Appendix 9)];
- 3091 • Various workflows have been established with specific protocols for obtaining information,
3092 e.g., *'Tracking data sources and adding data as published'* (Appendix 2); and
- 3093 • [Planned] standardised templates for data submission per indicator, per data sources (e.g., for
3094 particular institutions or individuals), or for particular groups (e.g., marine taxa) are to be
3095 prioritised as part of the next report cycle.

3096 It will also be important to evaluate the degree to which the indicators can be effectively
3097 communicated and promote desired behaviour.

3098 **6.4. Pathways**

3099 There are major gaps in our knowledge on *introduction rates*, with pathways being ‘unknown’ for 49%
3100 of introduced taxa, and dates of introduction or first record missing for 65% of introduced taxa. These
3101 data gaps are particularly prevalent for plants and fungi, but there are also substantial gaps for
3102 invertebrates (Figure S6.1). Such data gaps greatly impact our understanding of how and when alien
3103 species were introduced, our ability to direct interventions to where they are required, and our
3104 estimates of how effective those interventions are (cf. Chapter 5). Date of introduction data are likely
3105 not available for most taxa, however, for many taxa date of first record data should be available, and
3106 while for introduction pathways direct evidence seldom exists, pathways in most cases can be inferred
3107 (Essl et al. 2015). These gaps need to be addressed through directed research [e.g., introduction
3108 history studies such as those of Shepard et al. (2025)] and through efforts to improve the flow of
3109 information on records of new alien species into local and global datasets. In addition, introduction
3110 rates will need to be modelled based on dates of first record [as is currently recommended, see Buba
3111 et al. (2024)]. This will require survey effort data, which is currently lacking, or the identification of
3112 useful proxies. Additional capacity to do this is required as is a priority for future reports.

3113 There has been progress on a framework to categorise pathways within a country (Box 1.1), however,
3114 information on how species are dispersing within South Africa have not been collated. Without this
3115 information interventions to reduce such dispersal cannot be directed, invasive species will continue
3116 to spread rapidly, and impacts will increase.

3117 **6.5. Species**

3118 The process for collating a list of alien taxa for South Africa has been substantially improved and
3119 documented (Zengeya et al. 2025, in press). The development of repeatable workflows, following
3120 international best practices, ensures it is clear why a taxon is on the list and facilitates updates.
3121 Biological invasions are dynamic in nature, and therefore there is a need to regularly update the list
3122 of alien taxa. Therefore, the focus of future work is to increase the number of data-sources
3123 incorporated into the list, and to formalise processes for declaring a taxon alien, present (e.g., Matthys
3124 et al. 2025), and for assessing its degree of establishment (introduced, established, invasive).
3125 Processes have also been developed to incorporate new information as it becomes available (e.g.,
3126 Faulkner in press, Fernández Winzer et al. 2025a).

3127 Several challenges remain, such as significant gaps in knowledge of the presence and distribution of
3128 taxa not currently covered by specific atlasing projects. For example, the numbers of alien terrestrial
3129 plant species and vertebrate species are well documented, but there is less information for other
3130 groups such as invertebrates, soil organisms, and microorganisms (Janion-Scheepers et al. 2016,
3131 Janion-Scheepers and Griffiths 2020, Wood et al. 2017). There is ongoing development of frameworks
3132 and models assessing potential impacts and risks posed (e.g., Bacher et al. 2025, Boulesnane-
3133 Guengant et al. 2025). However, as only few taxa have been formally assessed, the need for more
3134 studies and assessments on the impact of invasive species remains a research priority for South Africa.

3135 **6.6.Sites**

3136 Citizen science continues to provide information on the extent of some species, with notable increase
3137 in observations around urban areas (e.g., Gildenhuis et al. 2025). However, there are no national long-
3138 term structured monitoring projects to track invasions across South Africa. As a result, the only reliable
3139 estimates on the extent and abundance of invasions across the country are from a few atlasing and
3140 remote sensing projects on selected invasive plant taxa in water catchments and terrestrial biomes
3141 (see Boxes 3.1 and 3.2). Previous reports noted that biological invasions continue to cause ‘Major’
3142 impacts on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human livelihoods. However, recent efforts to revise
3143 and update these estimates were unsuccessful (see Section S3.3). National and local scale estimates
3144 and maps of the impact of invasions are needed to appropriately prioritise interventions across sites
3145 and so that interventions can be adjusted to respond to invasions before such invasions are
3146 widespread and damaging.

3147 **6.7.Interventions**

3148 Interventions aimed at preventing the introduction of invasive species or reducing their impacts need
3149 to be carefully planned and monitored, within a framework of adaptive management, if they are to
3150 be effective. The absence of management plans for regulating the pathways of introduction and
3151 spread, and for dealing with priority species represents a significant gap. While some site management
3152 plans exist, the coverage of the plans is low, and many site plans do not have clear and realistic goals.
3153 Monitoring programs aimed at tracking progress towards goals, and taking corrective actions when
3154 progress is not satisfactory, are typically absent. The capacity and resources that would be needed to
3155 fund the development of such plans, to adequately and sustainably fund their implementation, and to
3156 monitor progress towards achieving their goals were not explicitly addressed in this report, but these
3157 gaps will continue to make the assessment of effectiveness of interventions difficult.

3158 South Africa's regulatory framework is based on the premise of regulating all harmful or potentially
3159 harmful alien taxa. However, this is not the only option. Rather than specifying what cannot be used
3160 it can be more effective to specify options that can be used. Kumschick et al. (2025) expanded on the
3161 concept of a 'safe list' that they defined as 'a list of taxa alien to the region of interest that are
3162 considered of sufficiently low risk of invasion and impact that the taxa can be widely used without
3163 concerns of negative impacts.'. They developed a generalised protocol for developing such lists.
3164 Potgeiter et al. (2025) applied these concepts to develop a workflow for identifying tree taxa that can
3165 be used without concerns of exacerbating invasions (either of the trees themselves or of pest and
3166 pathogens). In context of the outbreak of the *Euwallacea fornicatus* (polyphagous shot hole borer)
3167 they created such a list for Cape Town. On a similar note, Chetty et al. (2024) reviewed how 'sterile'
3168 cultivars of listed alien plants were addressed under the A&IS Regulations, and developed
3169 recommendations for how 'safe' cultivars could be identified and exempt from regulation. Regulation
3170 is, of course, legally binding, but comes at the costs of flexibility. Kumschick et al. (2025) also discussed
3171 voluntary options, including certification, codes of conduct, and informal lists to raise awareness. The
3172 WfW programme had a campaign of 'Plant me instead' to identify native alternative to listed alien
3173 ornamental plants. The value of such approaches in building relationships and the extent to which
3174 non-regulatory options are available and used could be an important addition to future reports, with
3175 the role of voluntary agreements potentially to be added to the evaluation of the regulatory
3176 framework.

3177 **6.8. Gaps identified in the IPBES IAS Assessment**

3178 Wilson et al. (2025) evaluated gaps identified in the IPBES IAS Assessment (IPBES 2023) in the context
3179 of the South African situation with suggestions for actions that can be adopted as part of the national
3180 strategy on biological invasions. An adapted version of the analysis is included in the supplementary
3181 material presented here (Table S6.2). The overall conclusion from the comparison was that:

3182 *Some gaps at a global level...were not as applicable to South Africa (South Africa has relatively good*
3183 *inventories when compared with many countries around the world). Many of the identified actions to*
3184 *fill gaps (e.g., the need for systems to track the effectiveness of interventions) have already been*
3185 *identified as part of the South African status reports ... and are under consideration in the draft national*
3186 *strategy. There also appears to be a need to integrate global and national needs. Nonetheless, the*
3187 *process helped us develop some specific actions that should be considered (e.g., the need to support*
3188 *general surveys of alien invertebrates and microorganisms; the need to promote transdisciplinary work*
3189 *and draw more on integrative social-ecological systems thinking; and actions to improve participation*
3190 *of communities in decision-making). Finally, there are a range of valuable South African specific*

3191 *databases and knowledge products (e.g., on research, policy, compliance and enforcement, and*
3192 *management best practice). Consolidating such information so it is findable, accessible, inter-operable,*
3193 *and reusable (i.e., FAIR; Wilkinson et al. 2016) and better co-ordination between the various*
3194 *organisations that collect and curate data will be essential if governance is to be integrated.*

3195 **6.9. The way forward**

3196 Given the mandate of this report arises from the NEM:BA (See Section 0.1.2) and the funding for it
3197 comes from the DFFE, the report is naturally focussed on environmental issues. However, it is
3198 increasingly recognised that addressing biological invasions would require integrated governance as
3199 the issues are cross-sectoral (IPBES, 2023). For example, an evaluation of biological invasions is
3200 essential for the One Health approach to be successful (e.g., thought consideration of One Biosecurity,
3201 Hulme et al. 2025; Box 1.2).

3202 Several future goals for the report have been proposed, noting that in each case the ability to address
3203 the goal will depend on resources [Note, this will be adapted based on stakeholder consultation].

- 3204 • Support strategic review of progress on the NISSAP;
- 3205 • Legal review of the legislation framework around biological invasions;
- 3206 • Link to the status of biological invasions in neighbouring countries;
- 3207 • Improved presentation of impacts and management in economic terms;
- 3208 • Impacts assessed for priority taxa;
- 3209 • Track progress made across goals from previous reports to changes over time (including
3210 developing workflows for all the indicators); and
- 3211 • Processes in place to work on impacts on sites

3212 Revisions to the A&IS Regulations that are underway as well as the development of the national
3213 strategy on biological invasions offer opportunities to refine the scope and expectations of this report
3214 (e.g., the proposal to move to decadal reports with annual updates provided as part of a dashboard
3215 of indicators; Table 0.1, Section 0.4). Additional mechanisms might be needed, however, if this report
3216 is to have the legitimacy and acceptability as a mechanism to promote integrated governance.

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3231

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3779 Links to appendices and supplementary material

3780 Copies of the files will be permanently available at the links below. For files that will be periodically
 3781 updated (e.g., the list of alien taxa) the doi link will resolve to the latest copy of the file, but other
 3782 versions will be visible at that link. If the reader wishes to get the specific copy of the document that
 3783 was linked to this report, please navigate to the appropriate version.

Item	Web-link	QR code
The status of biological invasions and their management in South Africa in 2025 [DRAFT FOR PUBLIC COMMENT]	http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17697657	
Supplementary Material	http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18314515	
Appendix 1: Indicator factsheets	http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17739011	
Appendix 2: Workflows [Note: as several workflows are still under development, updated versions of all workflows are not included here, the link points to the workflows of SANBI and CIB (2023)]	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433129	
Appendix 3: List of data sources	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17739442	
Appendix 4: Species level pathway data	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3582021	

Item	Web-link	QR code
Appendix 5: Pathways change tracker	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3947798	
Appendix 6: The list of alien taxa	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433102	
Appendix 7: References used in the list of alien taxa	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17185375	
Appendix 8: Metadata for the list of alien taxa	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433112	
Appendix 9: Permits issued under the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations 2014–2022 [Note: to be updated to 2023–2025]	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3947809	

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